
Legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil and biobased plastics for packaging

Deliverable 6.4

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

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	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
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ABBREVIATIONS

AAAS: American Association for the Advancement of Science

ACDV: French Association Chimie du Végétal

ADR: transport of hazardous materials treaty

CEN: European Committee for Standardization

CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging

Conai: Consorzio Nazionale Imballaggi

Corepla: Consorzio Nazionale per la Raccolta, il Riciclo ed il Recupero degli Imballaggi in Plastica

DI: Decree Law

Dlgs: legislative Decree

DM: Ministerial Decrees

EC: European Commission

ECHA: European Chemicals Agency

ECHA: European Chemicals Agency,

EEA: European Environment Agency

EEC: European Economic Community

EN: European Norms - Standards

EoW: End of Waste

EU: European Union

FCMs: Food Contact Materials

GATT: General Agreement on Trade and Tariffs

GHG: Greenhouse gas

HDPE: High density polyethylene

IPTS: Institute for Prospective Technological Studies

JRC: Joint Research Centre

LCIA: Life Cycle Impact Assessment

LDPE: Low density polyethylene

M: Multilateral Agreement

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
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	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

MOCA: Material and object in contact with food

MRF: Material recovery facilities

MS: Member States

MUD: Single Model of Environmental Declaration

NAFTA: North American Free Trade Agreement

NIR: Near Infra-Red

PARI: Packaging Waste autonomous management system

PBAT: Polybutylene adipate terephthalate

PC: Polycarbonate

PETE / PET: Polyethylene terephthalate

PHA: Polyhydroxyalkanoate

PLA: Polylactic acid

PMMA: Polymethyl methacrylate

POPs: Persistent organic pollutants

PP: Polypropylene

PPW: Packaging Plastic Waste

PS: Polystyrene or Polystyrene

PVC: Polyvinyl chloride

REACH: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and restriction of Chemicals

RoHS: Restriction of hazardous substances in EE equipment

SME: Small and medium-sized enterprise

SRW: Secondary Raw Materials

t: metric tonnes

UNECE: United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

VAT: Value-added tax

WFD: Waste Framework Directive

WMP: Waste Management Plans

WTO: World Trade Organization

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
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	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

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MBP: MATER-BIOPOLYMER SRL

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CRF: CENTRO RICERCHE FIAT SCPA

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PLASTIPOLIS: PLASTIPOLIS

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The main aim of this report is to analyse the framework of main legislation and policies in force at European, national and regional level, aimed to the identification of the main bottlenecks in the valorisation of biobased and fossil based plastic waste as secondary raw materials. Focus is dedicated to evaluating the opportunity to adopt EoW Criteria for plastics, and other potential chances to unlock the barriers towards circular economy models for plastics streams from the legislative point of view.

Three main conceptual parts constitute this document:

- EU legislative framework analysis;
- National and local insights for Italy, Spain, Turkey and Croatia; and
- Interviews focused on eight case studies.

In the first phase of the analysis the following relevant fields have been addressed:

- Waste Framework Directive;
- End of Waste Criteria;
- Bioplastic for Packaging; and
- Bilateral Agreements.

The investigation of policy framework at EU level allowed the team to identify several risks and chances useful towards the development of recommendations. The main general issues are below summarized:

- Not unique “definitions” or missing common “language”;
- Compatibility problems between new and existing policies in the MS internal legislation;
- Potential competition with food feedstock for bioplastic;
- Technological gaps between MS;
- Bilateral Agreements as alternative to EoW criteria;
- Possibility for MS to use national reduction targets.

As second phase of the analysis, the team performed a detailed investigation of the national legislative frameworks of Italy, Spain, Croatia and Turkey, in order to investigate how the EU policy on Packaging Plastic Waste and Circular Economy has been received, and in particular what is the impact of the legislation reflected on the actors of the Packaging Plastic Waste value chain at national/regional/municipal level. The National insights followed this path:

- National Overview;

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Legislation history;
- National Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages;
- Legislation ongoing;
- National approach to Circular Economy;
- EoW Criteria and transposition of EU policies;
- Interactions between the actors and legislation in the plastic packaging waste management.

The final part of this document is dedicated to a set of interviews that were developed for each investigated country, aimed to gather information from the direct experience of the actors who are involved in first-hand in the phases described above. In this way, the findings derived from desk-based review research were verified and enriched through actual experiences faced with respect to Packaging Plastics Waste related local legislation framework. Here below the main highlights found during the desk-based analysis and confirmed by the results of the case studies interviews, under the light of the hands-on experiences, are listed:

- Technological gap among the MS in collection, selection, treating and processing of PPW;
- EU policy not addressed to find “definitive” EoW Criteria for plastics (regulation), but instead to provide guidelines for MS in the management of the “no longer waste” materials;
- Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics;
- Packaging waste are not always collected separately and in compliance with legal framework;
- Other than EoW Criteria, the European Commission is also promoting bilateral agreements between MS;
- As the market for plastics secondary raw materials is growing, standardisation is needed for the traceability of recycled material;
- End-of-Waste Criteria for plastic can be oriented towards specific targeted applications to replaced fossil feedstock plastic with compostable bioplastics.

Such preliminary findings were useful to highlight the main issues to be investigated in the future developments of the research, through a wider survey embracing further key stakeholders of the value chains of PPW, towards the development of a set of relevant policy recommendations.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	1
1.1	Our methodological approach	2
1.2	Planning the next steps.....	5
2	EU Policy Framework analysis	6
2.1	Waste Framework Directive	7
2.1.1	Development of the Waste Framework Directive	7
2.1.2	Recycling society and waste hierarchy	8
2.1.3	Focus on Recovery.....	9
2.1.4	Prevention - National Waste Programmes	13
2.2	Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (EU) 2015/720	15
2.3	European Strategy for Plastics in the Circular Economy	21
3	End of Waste	24
3.1	End of Waste Status – Secondary Raw Materials	25
3.2	End of Waste Criteria.....	29
3.2.1	Definition.....	30
3.2.2	Procedure.....	32
3.2.2.1	Analysis of Waste Stream	32
3.2.2.2	Guidance to develop EoW Criteria	33
3.2.2.3	Impact Assessment.....	34
	Environment and health	34
	Economic Impact - others potential field.....	35
	Effect on the Market.....	36
	Legislative Impact.....	36
	Other socio-economic impacts	36
4	EoW Criteria and Packaging Plastic Waste	38
4.1	Management, production and trending of waste plastics	39
4.2	Waste plastic reprocessing and recycling.....	44
4.2.1	Collection	44
4.2.2	Sorting	46
4.2.3	Removal of contaminants	47
4.2.4	Cleaning process	47
4.2.5	Recycling.....	47
4.2.6	Use of the recycled waste plastics;.....	50
4.2.7	Structure of reprocessing industry.....	50
4.3	Legislative Aspects and Impacts.....	53
5	Bioplastics for Packaging	54
5.1	Bioplastic materials.....	55
5.2	Bioplastic Waste management.....	57
5.3	Bioplastics and EU Circular Economy	60

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

5.4	Relevant EU policies	62
5.5	EoW Criteria for Biodegradable waste and Biodegradable plastics.....	64
6	Bilateral and Multilateral trade agreements	66
6.1	General overview	67
7	Main Bottlenecks at EU Level and Drivers for Possible Solutions	71
8	National Insights	76
8.1	National Legislation – Italy.....	77
8.1.1	National overview	77
8.1.2	Legislation history.....	78
8.1.3	National Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages.....	81
8.1.3.1	The CONAi system: Packaging recovery in Italy.....	81
8.1.3.2	Corepla: Italian Consortium for plastic recycling	82
8.1.3.3	Co.N.I.P.: Plastic Packaging National Consortium	83
8.1.3.4	P.A.R.I system: Packaging Waste autonomous management system.....	84
8.1.3.5	MOCA: Material and object in contact with food [others plastic packaging “good practise”] 85	
8.1.3.6	Waste Regulation authority	86
8.1.3.7	MUD: Single Model of Environmental Declaration	86
8.1.3.8	SISTRi: System of Traceability and Control of Waste.....	86
8.1.4	Legislation ongoing – Italian approach to Circular Economy	87
8.1.5	EoW Criteria and transposition of EU policies	88
8.1.5.1	“Veneto” case study – Problems in regional application of EoW	89
8.1.6	Interactions between the actors and legislation in the plastic packaging waste management	90
8.1.6.1	Obligations on enterprises (D.lgs 152/06, art. 221).....	91
8.1.6.2	The obligation on the CONAi (D.lgs 152/06, art. 225)	91
8.1.6.3	The CONAi Environmental Contribution	91
8.1.6.4	Management of primary packaging waste (Urban Waste)	92
8.1.6.5	Management of the secondary and tertiary waste	92
8.1.6.6	Conclusion	92
8.1.7	Policy experiences from case studies	93
8.1.7.1	First interview – Fater Group.....	93
8.1.7.2	Recap of FATER opinion	94
8.1.7.3	Second interview – FCA (Fiat Chrysler Automobiles)	94
8.1.7.4	Recap of CFR opinion.....	95
8.1.7.5	Third interview – NOVAMONT	95
8.1.7.6	Recap of NOVAMONT opinion	95
8.2	National Legislation – Spain	97
8.2.1	National overview	99
8.2.2	Legislation history.....	101
8.2.3	National Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages.....	101
8.2.3.1	Traceability and waste control	103

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.2.4	Conclusions	103
8.2.5	Policy experiences from case studies	104
8.2.5.1	First interview - TECNOPACKAGING	104
8.2.5.2	Recap of TECNOPACKAGING opinion	104
8.2.5.3	Second interview - GRUPO SADA P.A.	105
8.2.5.4	Recap of GRUPO SADA P.A. opinion	105
8.2.5.5	Third interview - CALAF INDUSTRIAL	105
8.2.5.6	Recap of CALAF INDUSTRIAL opinion	105
8.3	Municipal and Regional Legislation – Croatia	106
8.3.1	Regional and municipal Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages	106
8.3.2	Municipal and Regional overview	107
8.3.3	Legislation history	109
8.3.4	Key Policy Measures in Force	112
8.3.4.1	Definition of Packaging - Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15, 78/16, 116/17)	112
8.3.4.2	Definition of plastic and plastic carrier bags - Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15, 78/16, 116/17	113
8.3.4.3	Main local regulation in the City of Rijeka - Waste Management Plan of the City of Rijeka for the period 2017 - 2022	114
8.3.5	Regional and municipal Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages	114
8.3.5.1	Regional/municipal Packaging recovery system	114
8.3.5.2	Regional/municipal Consortium for plastic recycling	115
8.3.5.3	Regional/municipal Plastic Packaging Consortium	116
8.3.5.4	Packaging Waste management system	116
8.3.5.5	Material and object in contact with food	117
8.3.5.6	Waste regulation authority	118
8.3.5.7	Packaging waste paperwork	119
8.3.5.8	Traceably and Control of Waste	119
8.3.1	Legislation ongoing	121
8.3.2	Impact of the legislation on the packaging plastics waste actors	121
8.3.2.1	Conclusion	125
8.3.3	Policy experiences from case studies	126
8.3.3.1	interview - MI-PLAST	126
8.3.3.2	Recap of MI-PLAST opinion	126
8.4	Municipal and Regional Legislation – Turkey	127
8.4.1	Municipal and Regional overview	154
8.4.2	Legislation history	155
8.4.3	Key Policy Measures in Force	156
8.4.3.1	Environmental Law	156
8.4.3.2	Metropolitan Municipality Law and Municipality Law	157
8.4.3.3	Regulation of Control of Packaging Waste	158
8.4.3.4	Regulation on Turkish Food Codex	161
8.4.3.5	Regulation on Water Intended for Human Consumption	163
8.4.3.6	Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food	164

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.4.3.7	Communiqué on the Principles and Procedures Related to Standard Practices That Must Be Complied within the Wholesale and Retail Trade of Vegetables and Fruits ..164	
8.4.3.8	Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals 165	
8.4.4	Regional and municipal Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages.....	167
8.4.4.1	Regional/municipal Packaging recovery system.....	173
8.4.4.2	Regional/municipal Consortium for plastic recycling.....	174
8.4.4.3	Material and object in contact with food	174
8.4.4.4	Waste regulation authority	174
8.4.4.5	Packaging waste paperwork.....	174
8.4.4.6	Traceably and Control of Waste	174
8.4.5	Legislation ongoing.....	174
8.4.6	Impact of the legislation on the packaging plastics waste actors.....	175
8.4.6.1	Import:	175
8.4.6.2	Collection:.....	175
8.4.6.3	Sorting:	176
8.4.6.4	Selling of sorted PPW:	176
8.4.6.5	Crashing:	177
8.4.6.6	The preparatory operation for reuse:.....	177
8.4.6.7	Export:	177
8.4.6.8	Transformation:.....	177
8.4.6.9	Re-use:	178
8.4.6.10	Feedstock recycling:.....	179
8.4.6.11	Conclusion	179
8.4.7	Policy experiences from case studies	181
8.4.7.1	First interview - TARHAN PLASTIC CORPORATION	181
8.4.7.2	Recap of TARHAN PLASTIC CORPORATION opinion	181
8.4.7.3	Second interview - VATAN PLASTIC	181
8.4.7.4	Recap of VATAN PLASTIC opinion	182
8.5	Conclusions.....	183
9	References	186
	Annex 1- Ordinary legislative procedure	188
	Annex 2 - Article 10 as amended.....	191
	Annex 3 - Plastic material for packaging	192
	Annex 4 - Legislation for Plastic materials as a product.....	194
	Annex 5 – Interview to Fater Group	199
	Annex 6 - Interview to Fiat Research Centre	201
	Annex 7 - Interview to Novamont.....	203

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Annex 8 - Interview to Tecnopackaging	214
Annex 9 - Interview to Grupo Sada P.A.....	216
Annex 10 - Interview to Calaf Industrial	218
Annex 11 - Interview to MI-PLAST.....	219
Annex 12 - Interview to Tarhan Plastic Corporation.....	222
Annex 13 - Interview to Vatan Plastic.....	224

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

1 INTRODUCTION

This document represents the first deliverable for the task 6.3 “Overcoming legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil-based and bio-based plastics for packaging” within the WP 6 “Cross Sectorial Validation, Replicability and Upscaling of Solution”.

The main aim of this deliverable it is to analyse the framework of main legislation and policies in force at European, national and regional level, aimed to the identification of the main bottlenecks in the valorisation of biobased and fossil based plastic waste as secondary raw materials.

Focus of the whole procedure is to evaluate the opportunity to adopt EoW Criteria for plastics, and other potential chances to unlock the barriers towards circular economy models for plastics streams from the legislative point of view at international, national and local level.

This document is the recipient of the first part of the activities developed in Task 6.3, aimed to collect information on the legislation and policy framework with respect to the valorisation of fossil and biobased plastic waste as secondary raw materials, and to provide first indications on potential risks and chances, based on CIRC-PACK partners’ experience.

This deliverable is therefore intended to:

- Highlight the **main barriers**, from legislative perspective, and **measures for their overcoming**, aimed to allow the recycling of Packaging Plastics Waste fraction and the actual realization of Circular Economy value chains;
- Understand the **potential for application of EoW Criteria** for Packaging Plastics Waste;
- Evaluate the possible **alternative routes** to facilitate the exchange of waste plastic as secondary raw materials.

The outcomes of this study will afterwards feed the consequent activities planned within Task 6.3, with the final objective to provide **policy recommendations for EU institutions**, aimed at unlocking and facilitating the recycling of bio/fossil plastics.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

1.1 Our methodological approach

Our methodological approach follows an iterative investigation process of the current legislative framework, in the collection of the best practices and the main barriers in the waste management, with the aim to draw up useful advice to adopt EoW Criteria for the waste plastics stream and further measures to unlock the potential for circular economy models for packaging materials (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Our methodological approach

RINA has developed this method to be used for a variety of topics and areas, and here adopted for the Packaging Plastics Waste issues.

Our approach starts with the analysis of the current legislative framework, collecting the input and documentation from literature and from stakeholders, for example as:

- Literature research
- Stakeholder interviews
- Survey on case studies
- Other channels/events.

On this basis, it is possible to iteratively define a set of relevant ongoing themes of discussion and of related outstanding issues, such as, in this case, EoW concept and Trade Agreements.

The process is aimed to highlight a series of “risks” and “chances.” In relation to the faced themes. These findings are the basis to identify and elaborate the related “barriers” and “drivers” with respect to the recycling of Packaging Plastic Waste.

In Figure 2 the cornerstones of our analysis starting from the investigation of EU Policy Framework towards the identification of the main policy issues, are shown.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 2: Main faced themes

The **EU Policy Framework** has been investigated by collecting information on the legislation and policies landscape, and compiling a commented overview of, respectively:

- Waste Framework Directive;
- Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive;
- European Strategy for Plastics in the Circular Economy.

The main characteristics of **EoW concept**, of **EoW Materials** and **Criteria** have been investigated, analysing the main issues correlated to the PPW. The main documents analysed have been:

- The JRC technical report, requested by the EU Commission to draft EoW Criteria guideline;
- The EoW Criteria for Plastic for conversion, not used as regulation (so far)
- And the EoW for biodegradable waste, interesting for the biodegradable fraction of the bioplastic.

Bioplastics related themes have been subject of a specific analysis, especially considering the issues correlated to the Biodegradable Plastic Waste and the potential to develop EoW criteria.

The desk-based analysis of the EU policies has also driven the team towards the themes linked to the **Trade Agreements**, as a sound alternative to the application as Regulation of the EoW Criteria.

Besides, the team performed a detailed analysis of the **National Legislative Frameworks of Italy, Spain, Croatia and Turkey**, useful to investigate how the EU policy on Packaging Plastic Waste and Circular Economy has been receipted, and what is the impact of the legislation on the Packaging Plastic Waste actors at national/regional/municipal level.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

In order to actualize the knowledge on the PPW policies, the team has also foreseen some **interviews to industrial case studies** for each National Legislative Framework analysed, with the aim to find any unexpected issues and to expand the perspective on the EoW themes to further possible routes to facilitate the recycling of fossil plastic packaging waste and the introduction of biobased plastics for circular economy models.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

1.2 Planning the next steps

In the end of this process, the main risks and chances highlighted for the valorisation of biobased and fossil-based plastics waste as secondary raw materials will be useful to establish the basis for the second part of activities of Task 6.3.

In the Deliverable 6.3, that will be the final recipient of the outcomes of the Task, the team will present the proposed set of **policy recommendations for EU institutions** that will be possible through:

- The **update of the legislative landscape**, built up in the Deliverable 6.4;
- The **analysis of surveys and interviews** to stakeholders not directly involved in the project;
- **The new barriers and drivers** retrievable from the updated analysis.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

2 EU POLICY FRAMEWORK ANALYSIS

The aim of this section is to analyse the main pillars of the policy framework related to recycling of fossil and bio-based plastic materials at EU level, to pave the way for the successive national and local regulatory framework analysis. The following sections contain an overview of, respectively:

- Waste Framework Directive;
- Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive;
- EU Strategy for Plastics in the Circular Economy.

To understand the main interactions between the EU organisms with the MS legislation, in “Annex 1- Ordinary legislative procedure” a short summary of the main EU procedures and legislative route is provided.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

2.1 Waste Framework Directive

2.1.1 Development of the Waste Framework Directive

In 2006, Directive 75/442/EEC on waste has been codified, replacing all the previous versions and until its revision in 2008, the codified Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2006/12/EC) was the only legally valid version of the Waste Framework Directive.

However, in 2005 the Commission already proposed to start a revision aimed to update the waste legislation, with a view to facilitating the Regulation by the EU MS.

The revised Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC on waste) has been adopted by the Council on 20 December 2008, after the application of several amendments and published in the Official Journal of the European Union on 22 November 2008, entering into force on 12 December 2008.

The deadline for the transposition of the revised Waste Framework Directive into national legislation of the Member States passed on 12 December 2010. From this date, The Directive replaced:

- Directives 75/439/EEC on the disposal of waste oils,
- Directive 91/689/EEC on hazardous waste
- Directive 2006/12/EC on waste

Following the proposal of the Communication of the European Commission COM (2015)/05951, the Directive 98/2008/EC is amended by the Directive (EU) 2018/8512.

The main stages of the Waste Framework Directive revision are shown in the figure below:

Figure 3: WFD history from 1975 to 2018

It must be pointed out that the development of CIRC-PACK project lies under Directive 2008/98/EC, but the amendments entered in force only in an advanced phase of the

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52015PC0595>

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018L0851>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

project. For this reason, the deliverable is primarily based on the Directive in its 2008 version, and, when necessary, the relevant highlights on the effects of the amendments are provided. Indeed, despite legislative modifications, the general concepts that are described in this document concerning the Waste Framework Directive are still valid at the date of drafting of this document.

2.1.2 Recycling society and waste hierarchy

This paragraph describes the main concepts introduced within the latest version of the WFD.

Firstly, Article 3 of the WFD reports the key definitions and principles regarding waste and waste management. In detail, it defines waste as “**any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard.**”

Subsequently, the concept of waste hierarchy is further investigated. The waste hierarchy is a priority order for prevention and waste management operations, which aims to minimize adverse environmental effects from waste and to increase resource efficiency in waste policy.

The waste hierarchy already appeared in the version of 2006, in which the European Commission suggested, with a first legislative proposal on waste, a 3-step hierarchy for waste management operations:

1. Prevention and Reuse;
2. Recycling and Recovery;
3. Disposal.

In this version of the hierarchy, Recycling and Recovery were at the same level. This issue will be a critical turning point of the WFD of 2008.

Indeed, in the Directive 2008/98/EC, a new hierarchy of waste, shown in Figure 4 1, is defined in article 4 as follows:

1. **Prevention** (preventing and reducing waste generation);
2. **Preparing for reuse** (giving the products a second life before they become waste);
3. **Recycling** (any recovery operation by which waste materials are re-processed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes composting and it does not include incineration);
4. **Other recovery** (some waste incineration based on a political non-scientific formula that upgrades the less inefficient incinerators);
5. **Disposal** (processes to dispose of waste to land filling, incineration, pyrolysis, gasification and other finalist solutions)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 4: Waste Hierarchy according to Directive 2008/98/EC

Compared with the previous version, the point of view of the Directive 2008/98/EC changed. It defined the principles for the waste management, by establishing a new understanding of waste, recycling and recovery.

The application of waste hierarchy is compulsory in all the MSs that must take measures to encourage the options that deliver the best overall environmental outcome in policy and legislation. Deviation from the waste hierarchy is allowed if justified on grounds of “life cycle thinking” concerning environmental impacts.

The concepts of preparation for reuse, recycle and recovery in general can be seen as starting points to introduce the definition of **End of Waste (EoW)** status, to specify when certain waste ceases to be waste and obtains a status of a product, which is, to distinguish between waste and by-products. The concept related to EoW status and the criteria necessary to define it will be dealt with in paragraph 3.1.

In addition, article 11 sets various quantitative recovery targets to be achieved by 2020. The Directive introduces also the extended producer responsibility (article 8), that is the principle according to which the manufacturer/importer of a product has the responsibility of its disposal and should implement measures such as acceptance of returned products, and the polluter pays principle (article 14), according to which the producer of the waste is responsible for the costs related to waste management.

To conclude, article 28 and article 29 set the requirements for **Waste Management Plans** and **Waste Prevention Programmes** (see paragraph 2.1.4), which must be developed by Member States.

2.1.3 Focus on Recovery

Recovery is among the key issue of the WFD and it is a pillar of CIRC-PACK project. In this paragraph, an overview on the meaning of “recovery” and on how it is faced within the WFD is given.

A preliminary step towards this aim is to clarify and define the terminology used in this report, which is based on the definitions given within the Waste Framework Directive. Indeed, it is common to find incorrect uses of these terms, due both to the difficult interpretation of official definitions and to the fact that they belong to common language that has been used in reports and research studies without relying on the recent definitions.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 5: WFD Vocabulary

As shown in the previous figure, at the end of its life, a product becomes **waste** and undergoes a waste **treatment**, which can be either **recovery** or **disposal**.

In detail, according to the WFD, “**recovery means any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function, in the plant or in the wider economy.**” In this sense, recovery includes preparing for re-use, recycle, other recovery (for example, energy recovery) or other operations aimed at valorisation of the waste. It is highlighted that “reuse” is not a waste treatment operation, but rather a form of waste prevention. On the other hand, “disposal means any operation which recovery is not even where the operation has as a secondary consequence the reclamation of substances or energy.”

According to article 10 of the WFD 2008 (Annex 2 - Article 10 as amended), “Member States shall take necessary measures to ensure that waste undergoes recovery operations (..)” and “(..) waste shall be collected separately if technically, environmentally and economically practicable (..).”

Main Effects of the Amendments

The recent amendments considerably enlarge article 10.

In the new version, conditions that can allow derogations from separate collection of waste are specified.

Furthermore, it is stated that, in general, Members States shall take measures to ensure that waste that has been separately collected is not incinerated and to remove hazardous substances (before or during recovery) to potentially allow their subsequent treatment in accordance with the waste hierarchy principles, without harming human health or environment.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

In general practice, recovery is characterised by the following consequential steps:

- Collection;
- Storage;
- Valorisation;
- Secondary raw material;
- Marketing.

Recovery thus represents the last passages of the life cycle of the product. The reintroduction of the waste materials in the production processes, which is the aim of the recovery operation, must be aligned to the legislative frameworks and to the market demand. At this point, it becomes necessary to define when a product ceases to be a waste and becomes a product again, putting itself back into the market. This concept is described in the definition of End of Waste Status and the consequent elaboration of End of Waste Criteria.

Article 11 further investigates aspects related to recovery. The core of Article 11 of the WFD 2008 is the promotion of reuse, preparing for reuse and high-quality recycling activities. In addition, it sets the following recovery targets:

- **50% (by weight)** preparing for re-use and recycling of certain waste materials from households;
- **70% (by weight)** preparing for re-use, recycling and other recovery of construction and demolition waste.

Article 11 as amended

1. Member States shall take measures to promote preparing for re-use activities, notably by encouraging the establishment of and support for preparing for re-use and repair networks, by facilitating, where compatible with proper waste management, their access to waste held by collection schemes or facilities that can be prepared for re-use but is not destined for preparing for re-use by those schemes or facilities, and by promoting the use of economic instruments, procurement criteria, quantitative objectives or other measures.

Member States shall take measures to promote high-quality recycling and, to this end, subject to Article 10(2) and (3), shall set up separate collection of waste.

Subject to Article 10(2) and (3), Member States shall set up separate collection at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass, and, by 1 January 2025, for textiles.

Member States shall take measures to promote selective demolition in order to enable removal and safe handling of hazardous substances and facilitate re-use and high-quality recycling by selective removal of materials, and to ensure the establishment of sorting systems for construction and demolition waste at least for wood, mineral fractions (concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics, stones), metal, glass, plastic and plaster.

2. In order to comply with the objectives of this Directive, and move to a European circular economy with a high level of resource efficiency, Member States shall take the necessary measures designed to achieve the following targets:

(a) by 2020, the preparing for re-use and the recycling of waste materials such as at least paper, metal, plastic and glass from households and possibly from other origins as far as these waste

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

streams are similar to waste from households, shall be increased to a minimum of overall 50 % by weight;

(b) by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery, including backfilling operations using waste to substitute other materials, of non-hazardous construction and demolition waste excluding naturally occurring material defined in category 17 05 04 in the list of waste shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;

(c) by 2025, the preparing for re-use and the recycling of municipal waste shall be increased to a minimum of 55 % by weight;

(d) by 2030, the preparing for re-use and the recycling of municipal waste shall be increased to a minimum of 60 % by weight;

(e) by 2035, the preparing for re-use and the recycling of municipal waste shall be increased to a minimum of 65 % by weight.

3. A Member State may postpone the deadlines for attaining the targets referred to in points (c), (d) and (e) of paragraph 2 by up to five years provided that that Member State:

(a) prepared for re-use and recycled less than 20 % or landfilled more than 60 % of its municipal waste generated in 2013 as reported under the Joint Questionnaire of the OECD and Eurostat; and

(b) at the latest 24 months before the respective deadline laid down in point (c), (d) or (e) of paragraph 2, notifies the Commission of its intention to postpone the respective deadline and submits an implementation plan in accordance with Annex IVb.

4. Within three months of receipt of the implementation plan submitted pursuant to point (b) of paragraph 3, the Commission may request a Member State to revise that plan if the Commission considers that the plan does not comply with the requirements set out in Annex IVb. The Member State concerned shall submit a revised plan within three months of receipt of the Commission's request.

5. In the event of postponing the attainment of the targets in accordance with paragraph 3, the Member State concerned shall take the necessary measures to increase the preparing for re-use and the recycling of municipal waste:

(a) to a minimum of 50 % by 2025 in the event of postponing the deadline for attaining the target referred to in point (c) of paragraph 2;

(b) to a minimum of 55 % by 2030 in the event of postponing the deadline for attaining the target referred to in point (d) of paragraph 2;

6. By 31 December 2024, the Commission shall consider the setting of preparing for re-use and recycling targets for construction and demolition waste and its material-specific fractions, textile waste, commercial waste, non-hazardous industrial waste and other waste streams, as well as preparing for re-use targets for municipal waste and recycling targets for municipal bio-waste. To that end, the Commission shall submit a report to the European Parliament and to the Council, accompanied, if appropriate, by a legislative proposal.

7. By 31 December 2028, the Commission shall review the target laid down in point (e) of paragraph 2. To that end, the Commission shall submit a report to the European Parliament and to the Council, accompanied, if appropriate, by a legislative proposal.

The Commission shall assess co-processing technology that allows the incorporation of minerals in the co-incineration process of municipal waste. Where a reliable methodology can be found, as part of this review, the Commission shall consider whether such minerals may be counted towards recycling targets.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Main Effects of the Amendments

The amendments to Article 11 are worth being highlighted as, along with other measures, they also include specific provisions and requirements for construction and demolition waste. Selective demolition is explicitly promoted in order to facilitate reuse and high-quality recycling.

2.1.4 Prevention - National Waste Programmes

The development of national programmes for waste management and prevention is one of the main objectives of the Directive.

Waste Management Plans (WMP) are compulsory in MSs under current WFD. They can be drawn up either by national, regional or local authorities, but, overall, they must cover all the Country's geographical territory. The main aim of a WMP is to analyse the current status of waste management and to develop environmentally friendly measures to improve both recovery and disposal of waste. An evaluation of how the plan supports the implementation of EU objectives must be performed. WMP are evaluated at least every 6 years and it is desirable that stakeholders, authorities and general public have the opportunity to participate in elaboration of the Plans.

The main detailed information included in the WMP shall include at least the type, quantity and source of waste generated, existing major disposal and recovery installations and collection schemes and general waste management policies, covering also planned waste management technologies and methods.

The Commission has published a methodological Guidance Note to support and assist competent authorities in the preparation of WMPs.

Waste Prevention Programmes (WPP) are compulsory in MSs under current WFD, with the aim to move up the waste hierarchy. They **are evaluated at least every six years and can be integrated into other measures** (for example waste management plan or environmental policy), but **they must be always clearly identifiable**.

The Programmes set waste prevention objectives and identify measures to pursue these objectives. **The States can follow the examples list of measures indicated in Annex IV of the Waste Framework Directive** or add other measures, which they consider appropriate. In order to monitor progresses related to waste prevention objectives, Member States shall describe the measures in place and the degree of usefulness and effectiveness, also thanks to suitable targets, indicators, benchmark values. In addition, a guidance document for the development of WPP has been made available by the Commission.

Table 1. Examples list of measures (Annex IV WFD)

Annex IV - Examples of Waste Prevention Measures referred to in Article 29

Measures that can affect the framework conditions related to the generation of waste

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

1. The use of planning measures, or other economic instruments promoting the efficient use of resources.
2. The promotion of research and development into the area of achieving cleaner and less wasteful products and technologies and the dissemination and use of the results of such research and development.
3. The development of effective and meaningful indicators of the environmental pressures associated with the generation of waste aimed at contributing to the prevention of waste generation at all levels, from product comparisons at the Community level through action by local authorities to national measures.

Measures that can affect the design and production and distribution phase

4. The promotion of eco-design (the systematic integration of environmental aspects into product design with the aim to improve the environmental performance of the product throughout its whole life cycle).
5. The provision of information on waste prevention techniques with a view to facilitating the implementation of best available techniques by industry.
6. Organise training of competent authorities as regards the insertion of waste prevention requirements in permits under this Directive and Directive 96/61/EC.
7. The inclusion of measures to prevent waste production at installations not falling under Directive 96/61/EC. Where appropriate, such measures could include waste prevention assessments or plans.
8. The use of awareness campaigns or the provision of financial, decision making or other support to businesses. Such measures are likely to be particularly effective where they are aimed at, and adapted to, small and medium sized enterprises and work through established business networks.
9. The use of voluntary agreements, consumer/producer panels or sectoral negotiations in order that the relevant businesses or industrial sectors set their own waste prevention plans or objectives or correct wasteful products or packaging.
10. The promotion of creditable environmental management systems, including EMAS and ISO 14001.

Measures that can affect the consumption and use phase

11. Economic instruments such as incentives for clean purchases or the institution of an obligatory payment by consumers for a given article or element of packaging that would otherwise be provided free of charge.
12. The use of awareness campaigns and information provision directed at the general public or a specific set of consumers.
13. The promotion of creditable eco-labels.
14. Agreements with industry, such as the use of product panels such as those being carried out within the framework of Integrated Product Policies or with retailers on the availability of waste prevention information and products with a lower environmental impact.
15. In the context of public and corporate procurement, the integration of environmental and waste prevention Criteria into calls for tenders and contracts, in line with the Handbook on environmental public procurement published by the Commission on 29 October 2004.
16. The promotion of the reuse and/or repair of appropriate discarded products or of their components, notably through the use of educational, economic, logistic or other measures such as support to or establishment of accredited repair and reuse-centres and networks especially in densely populated regions.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

2.2 Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (EU) 2015/720

Within the analysis of the policy framework related to packaging waste, without doubt one of the most important documents on this matter at EU level is the “Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (EU) 2015/720”.

The Directive covers all packaging placed on the Community market and all the material streams linked.

Figure 6. Packaging waste generated by packaging material, EU, 2015³

The Directive obligates member states to meet targets for the recovery and recycling of packaging waste, including plastics packaging waste. Targets are set as a percentage of packaging flowing into the waste stream. In general, the main issues faced are:

- **targets** for recovery and recycling;
- encouragement of the **use of recycled packaging materials** in the manufacturing of packaging and other products;
- **minimization of packaging volume and weight**, and the **design to reuse or recovery**;
- **prevention** of packaging waste;
- measures to **encourage the re-use** of packaging.

This objectives and targets have been updated down the years.

Below the main steps of the history of the EU policies on the management of packaging waste are summarized:

³ Source: Eurostat

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- In 1980, the Directive 85/339/EEC set rules on the production, marketing, use, recycling and refilling of containers of liquids for human consumption and on the disposal of used containers.

Some MS, to address the environmental aspects of packaging and packaging waste, started introducing their own measures with a consequence **diverging between the national legislation**. The following legislative intervention of EU Commission was addressed to harmonize the MS policies on PPW.

- In 1994, the Directive 94/62/EC was adopted to harmonize the legislation at European level, with the aims to provide a high level of environmental protection and avoid the obstacles to the internal market.
- In 2004, the Directive was amended to provide Criteria clarifying the definition of the term 'packaging' and increase the targets for recovery and recycling of packaging waste.
- In 2005, the Directive was revised again to grant new MS transitional periods for attaining the recovery and recycling targets.
- In 2013 Annex I of the Directive containing the list of illustrative examples of items that are or are not to be considered as the packaging was revised to provide more clarity by adding several examples to the list.
- The latest revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive occurred on 29 April 2015 with the adoption of Directive (EU) 2015/720 of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 94/62/EC as regards the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags.

Figure 7. The Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive history

The EU Commission included some basic definitions:

- **plastic** shall mean a polymer within the meaning of Article 3(5) of Regulation (EC) N° 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council (9), to which additives or other substances may have been added, and which is capable of functioning as a main structural component of carrier bags;

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **plastic carrier bags** shall mean carrier bags, with or without handle, made of plastic, which are supplied to consumers at the point of sale of goods or products;
- lightweight plastic carrier bags shall mean plastic carrier bags with a wall thickness below 50 microns;
- **very lightweight plastic carrier bags** shall mean plastic carrier bags with a wall thickness below 15 microns which are required for hygiene purposes or provided as primary packaging for loose food when this helps to prevent food wastage;
- **oxo-degradable plastic carrier bags** shall mean plastic carrier bags made of plastic materials that include additives which catalyse the fragmentation of the plastic material into micro-fragments;

Risk:

Not unique definitions or a missing common language can generate problems in the writing and application of policies.

Moreover, the Directive defines requirements for the MS on the thematic of the plastic carrier plastic. The MS shall take measures to achieve a sustained **reduction in the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags** on their territory.

Chance:

Those measures may include the use of **national reduction targets**, maintaining or introducing **economic instruments** as well as **marketing restrictions**, these restrictions are proportionate and non-discriminatory.

Such measures may vary depending on the environmental impact of lightweight plastic carrier bags when they are recovered or disposed of, their composting properties, durability or specific intended use.

The measures taken by MS shall include either or both of the following:

- the adoption of measures ensuring that the annual consumption level does not exceed **90 lightweight plastic carrier bags per person by 31 December 2019** and **40 lightweight plastic carrier bags per person by 31 December 2025**, or equivalent targets set in weight. Very lightweight plastic carrier bags may be excluded from national consumption objectives;
- the adoption of instruments ensuring that, **by 31 December 2018, lightweight plastic carrier bags are not provided free of charge** at the point of sale of goods or products, unless equally effective instruments are implemented. Very lightweight plastic carrier bags may be excluded from those measures.

From 27 May 2018 MS are asked to report on the annual consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags when providing data on packaging and packaging waste to the Commission in accordance with Article 12.

By 27 May 2016, the Commission committed to adopt an implementing act laying down the **methodology for the calculation of the annual consumption** of lightweight plastic carrier

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

bags per person and adapting. This commitment was recently acknowledged by the Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/896 of 19 June 2018 laying down the methodology for the calculation of the annual consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags and amending Decision 2005/270/EC (notified under document C (2018) 3736).

Chance:

MS may take measures such as **economic instruments** and **national reduction targets**, as regards any kind of plastic carrier bags.

Chance:

The Commission and the MS shall **encourage public information** and awareness campaigns concerning the adverse environmental impact of the excessive consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags.

In the Article 8 a specific measure for **biodegradable and compostable plastic carrier bags** are defined to permit the easy identification by the consumers.

The Commission is adopting an implementing act laying down the specifications of **labels or marks to ensure Union-wide recognition of biodegradable and compostable plastic carrier bags** and to provide consumers with the correct information about the composting properties of such bags (more detail about the label system for bio and biodegradable plastics will be faced in the chapter 5.1)

MS shall ensure that biodegradable and compostable plastic carrier bags are labelled in accordance with the regulatory procedure referred to in Article 21(2).⁴

The Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive was subject to review of waste policy and legislation in 2014, covering a review of key targets and related elements.

The European Commission adopted in 2018 a Circular Economy Action Plan, in this perspective, alongside the EU Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC and the Landfill Directive 1999/31/EC, the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive was subject to review of waste policy and legislation in 2014, covering a review of key targets and related elements common for EU MS:

For all packaging:

- By 2025 a **minimum 65% of all packaging waste** will be prepared for reuse and recycled, and **70% by 2030**.

For plastic:

- No later than 31 December 2025 a **minimum 50 % of plastic contained in packaging waste** for preparing for reuse and recycling will be met, the target is **55% by 2030**.

⁴ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01994L0062-20150526>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Risk:

These targets are not to be met by each type of plastic individually.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

In general, for the municipal waste Member states will have to meet the following targets as they increase the reuse and recycling⁵:

- **by 2025 a minimum of 55%**
- **by 2030 a minimum of 60%**
- **by 2035 a minimum of 65%**

Furthermore, by 31 December 2023, **bio-waste is either collected separately** or recycled at source (e. g. home composting). This is in addition to the separate collection which already exists for paper and cardboard, glass, metals and plastic.

Targets faced in the other directives are reported below:

- recycling 65% of municipal waste by 2030;
- recycling 75% of packaging waste by 2030;
- A binding landfill target to reduce landfill to maximum of 10% of municipal waste by 2030;
- A ban on landfilling of separately collected waste;
- Promotion of economic instruments to discourage landfilling;
- Simplified and improved definitions and harmonised calculation methods for recycling rates throughout the EU;
- Concrete measures to promote re-use and stimulate industrial symbiosis –turning one industry's by-product into another industry's raw material;
- Economic incentives for producers to put greener products on the market and support recovery and recycling schemes (e.g. for packaging, batteries, electric and electronic equipment, vehicles).

Chance:

The packaging design and material should be designed to minimise the volume and weight of the packaging used, whilst still being fit for purpose. The use of volume and weight as criteria is not intended to indicate a preference to lower weight or volume materials i.e. plastics over glass, but rather the overall environmental impact and reuse, recovery or recycling potential in choosing a packaging material, whilst reducing the volumes or material used⁶.

⁵ <http://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2018/05/22/waste-management-and-recycling-council-adopts-new-rules/>

⁶ <http://www.seafish.org/media/Publications/SeafishGuidetoPackagingandWaste.pdf>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

2.3 European Strategy for Plastics in the Circular Economy

European Commission on 16th January 2018 presented the “European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy”. This strategy has the aim to protect environment, reduce marine litter, greenhouse gas emissions and the European dependence on imported fossil fuels.

The strategy involves not only the recycling process but all the life cycle phases of plastic:

- better design of plastic products;
- higher plastic waste recycling rates;
- more and better quality of recycled plastics, and;
- boosting the market for recycled plastics.

Main issues on PPW grown up in the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions a European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (COM/2018/028 final) are focused on a smart, innovative and sustainable plastics industry, where design and production fully respects the needs of reuse, repair, and recycling, brings growth and jobs to Europe and helps cut EU's greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on imported fossil fuels⁷:

- Plastics and products containing plastics are designed to allow for greater durability, reuse and high-quality recycling. By 2030, all plastics packaging placed on the EU market is either reusable or can be recycled in a cost-effective manner.
- Changes in production and design enable higher plastics recycling rates for all key applications. By 2030, more than half of plastics waste generated in Europe is recycled. Separate collection of plastics waste reaches very high levels. Recycling of plastics packaging waste achieves levels comparable with those of other packaging materials.

The communication to citizens, government and industry must support more sustainable and safer consumption and production patterns for plastics. Many entrepreneurs see the need for more resolute action on plastics waste prevention as a business opportunity. New companies are growing, providing circular solutions such as reverse logistics for packaging or alternatives to disposable plastics, also exploiting the benefits from digitisation.

Plastics packaging is a priority area when it comes to design for recyclability. Today it accounts for about 60 % of post-consumer plastic waste⁸ in the EU, and product design is

⁷<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1516265440535&uri=COM:2018:28:FIN>

⁸ Source: Plastics Europe

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

one of the keys to improve recycling levels. It has been calculated that design improvements could halve the cost of recycling plastic packaging waste⁹.

In the previous years, the EU had already taken steps by setting requirements for Member States to adopt measures to cut the consumption of plastic bags¹⁰ and to monitor and reduce marine litter¹¹. EU funding is also being deployed to understand and combat the rise of marine litter¹², supporting global, national and regional action. EU rules supporting higher recycling rates and better waste collection systems are also important in helping to prevent leakage. In addition, through its upcoming legislative proposal for a revision of the Drinking Water Directive, the Commission will promote access to tap water for EU citizens, therefore reducing packaging needs for bottled water. The criteria for the Ecolabel and Green Public Procurement also promote reusable items and packaging¹³.

Additional measures at EU and national levels can be developed to reduce the unnecessary generation of plastic waste, especially waste from single-use items or over-packaging, and to encourage the reuse of packaging. Analytical work, including the launch of a public consultation, has already started to determine the scope of a legislative initiative on single-use plastics at EU level to be tabled by this Commission, following the approach used for light-weight plastic bags and examining relevant evidence from behavioural science¹⁴. Furthermore, the Commission will explore the feasibility of introducing measures of a fiscal nature at the EU level.¹⁵ Finally, the Commission will also investigate the issue of over-packaging as part of the future review of the essential requirements for packaging.

In line with the issued strategy, in May 2018, the EU commission proposed a new EU directive for single-use plastics, in order to target the 10 most common products found on Europe's beaches and seas. With the lost and abandoned fishing gear, these products and waste

⁹ Ellen MacArthur Foundation, The New Plastics Economy: Catalysing action, January 2017.

¹⁰ Directive 2015/720/EU amending Directive 94/62/EC as regards the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags.

¹¹ Directive 2008/56/EC establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy.

¹² For instance, in the Arctic Region, the "Circular Ocean" INTERREG project is testing new opportunities for reusing old fishing nets, including a material to remove pollutants from water (<http://www.circularocean.eu/>). In the Baltic Sea Region, the BLASTIC project maps potential litter sources in urban areas and monitors litter levels in the aquatic environment (<https://www.blastic.eu/>). Both projects are supported by the European Regional Development Fund.

¹³ For example, the Ecolabel criteria for tourism and the Green Public Procurement criteria for food and catering restrict the use of single-use plastics in catering.

¹⁴ The Joint Research Center conducts in-house behavioural research in various policy areas, helping to better understand both the drivers of behaviour and the relative effectiveness of alternative solutions.

¹⁵ The modalities of such a potential fee would have to be decided on the basis of the assessment of its contribution towards meeting the strategy goals. On top of that, in the context of the preparation of the post-2020 Multiannual Financial Framework, it could be considered as one of potential options to generate revenues for the EU budget.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

constitute 70% of all the marine litter items¹⁶. The main issues regarded the most common product found on Europe's beaches and seas: i.e. the cotton buds. The Directive bans single use cotton buds made with fossil-plastic and promote their replacement with sustainable alternatives on the market. Furthermore, single use cutlery, plates, straws & stirrers made with fossil plastic, will also be banned, encouraging the replacement with more sustainable alternatives.

¹⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/plastic_waste.htm

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

3 END OF WASTE

As reported in the section 2.1.2, the WFD introduced the concept of End of Waste (EoW) material and the consequent necessity to develop a set of criteria.

The Task 6.4 includes an evaluation of the opportunity to adopt EU EoW criteria for plastic streams. For this purpose, it is necessary to evaluate and analyse the main characteristics, requirements, and interactions that the adoption of a EoW criteria as Regulation may involve.

The following sections have the aim to introduce what it is a EoW material and how is possible to develop a EoW criteria.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

3.1 End of Waste Status – Secondary Raw Materials

The definition of “Secondary Raw Materials” comes out from a long road chosen by the European Commission that adopted in 21st December 2005 the **Thematic Strategy on the Prevention and the Recycle**, with the aim to prevent the waste generation in the UE MS and to review the Waste Framework Directive to clarify **when a material ceases to be waste** and can be considerate as a new secondary raw material.

The concept of “Secondary Raw Material” is defined from the first aim of the EU waste legislation: **protect the human health and the environment** by a right management and disposal of waste.

EU waste policies have the goal to increase the EU’s resource efficiency and reduce the negative environmental and health impacts, with the "Strategy" adopted in 2005, the Commission sets a long-term goal for the EU:

- **Becoming a recycling society;**
- **Avoiding waste;**
- **Using waste as a resource.**

The Strategy sets out key actions to modernize the existing legal framework and to promote waste prevention, reuse and recycling, with **“waste disposal only as last resort.”**

- To reduce the amount of waste generated;
- To maximise recycling and re-use;
- To limit incineration to non-recyclable materials;
- To phase out landfilling to non-recyclable and non-recoverable waste;
- To ensure full implementation of the waste policy targets in all Member States. (IPTS, END OF WASTE CRITERIA, Final Report, 2008)

From these principles, the Revised Waste Framework Directive adopted by the European Parliament and the Council of the EU on 20th October 2008, describes with the Article 6 a new concept of **End of Waste status**, and introduce the need to define **criteria** to establish **when waste ceases to be waste and becomes a secondary product**.

Table 2. End of Waste status definition (Article 6, WFD)

<p>Article 6 – End of Waste status</p> <p>1. Certain specified waste shall cease to be waste within the meaning of point (1) of Article 3 when it has undergone a recovery, including recycling, operation and complies with specific Criteria to be developed in accordance with the following conditions:</p> <p style="margin-left: 20px;">a. the substance or object is commonly used for specific purposes;</p> <p style="margin-left: 20px;">b. a market or demand exists for such a substance or object;</p> <p style="margin-left: 20px;">c. the substance or object fulfils the technical requirements for the specific purposes and meets the existing legislation and standards applicable to products; and</p>
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	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

d. the use of the substance or object will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.

2. The Criteria shall include limit values for pollutants where necessary and shall take into account any possible adverse environmental effects of the substance or object. The measures designed to amend non-essential elements of this Directive by supplementing it relating to the adoption of the Criteria set out in paragraph 1 and specifying the type of waste to which such Criteria shall apply shall be adopted in accordance with the regulatory procedure with scrutiny referred to in Article 39(2). EoW specific Criteria should be considered, among others, at least for aggregates, paper, glass, metal, tyres and textiles.

3. Waste which ceases to be waste in accordance with paragraphs 1 and 2, shall also cease to be waste for the purpose of the recovery and recycling targets set out in Directives 94/62/EC, 2000/53/EC, 2002/96/EC and 2006/66/EC and other relevant Community legislation when the recycling or recovery requirements of that legislation are satisfied.

4. Where Criteria have not been set at Community level under the procedure set out in paragraphs 1 and 2, Member States may decide case by case whether certain waste has ceased to be waste taking into account the applicable case law. They shall notify the Commission of such decisions in accordance with Directive 98/34/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 June 1998 laying down a procedure for the provision of information in the field of technical standards and Regulations and of rules on Information Society services (24) where so required by that Directive.

Here below the four main conditions set up in Directive 2008/98/EC to consider waste as potential EoW materials are reported:

- a) the substance or object is commonly used for **specific purposes**;
- b) a **market or demand exists** for such a substance or object;
- c) the substance or object fulfils the technical requirements for the specific purposes and meets the existing **legislation and standards applicable to products**; and
- d) the use of the substance or object will not lead to overall adverse **environmental or human health impacts**.

Risk:

The first two conditions **hinder the possibility to establish EoW Criteria** for materials for which **a use and a market are not yet defined**.

This is an implicit barrier in the Directive: a market or the use for certain materials depend from the policy framework itself, that permits to consider them not only waste but actual raw materials to treat them as such.

The third condition underlines the fundamental concept that an EoW material must not require special measures or treatment compared with the **equivalent primary raw material**.

Furthermore, the **EoW material must be considered as a raw material** and not more like waste, and therefore the same policies and standards shall be applied.

In the fourth condition, it is clear that if a substance ceases to be waste, it does not need to rely on the waste legislation to ensure the human health and the environmental safety, but **all the risks are covered by the products legislation**.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Risk / Chance:

From the analysis of documents and other references on the waste issues, it is evident that language and definitions represent a key barrier and at the same time a key driver to develop a structured and effective strategy on the plastic packaging waste policies.

To avoid misunderstanding it is necessary to clarify one of the main concepts related to the waste life cycle recycling process. With **Recovering**, the end-point of the waste life cycle chain is meant, i.e.: all the necessary operations that link the disposal phases with the recycling.

Here the definition of the Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) is quoted: “any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function, in the plant or in the wider economy. Annex II of the Directive sets out a non-exhaustive list of recovery operations.”

Recovering is characterised by some consequential steps:

- Collection;
- Storage;
- Valorisation;
- Secondary raw material; and
- Marketing.

Only through this pathway it is possible to re-introduce the waste in the economy cycle, with different purposes:

- Re-use;
- Recycling;
- Recovery (for energy for example) and Disposal.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 8: Waste life cycle

The “Recovery for energy” and the “Disposal” will not be treated, the final aim of the document in fact is find the right policies recommendation to favourite a **circular economy approach with the aim to increase “Re-use” and “Recycling.”**

The re-introduction of the waste materials in the production processes as products, need a market demand, but also a legislative framework.

It becomes necessary to define clear criteria to decide when a material ceases to be waste and becomes a product again, putting itself back on the market. This concept is described in the **definition of EoW Material.**

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

3.2 End of Waste Criteria

In the investigation of the process towards the definition of a set of EoW Criteria, two different European documents must be mentioned:

- The Thematic Strategy on the Prevention and Recycle;
- the Article 6 point 1 and 2 of the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC.

The underlying rationale for the European Commission in this process is to protect, preserve and improve the environment, implementing policies that ensure an elevated level of environmental protection, preserving the **EU citizens quality of life**.

The process started with the initiative of the **Directorate-General for Environment**, the European Commission department responsible for EU policy on environmental issues.

As a first step, the **Directorate-General for Environment** requested to the **Institute for Prospective Technological Studies** (IPTS) to write a Technical Report about the main EoW material issues.

The Institute for Prospective Technological Studies or IPTS, located in Seville, Spain, is one of the seven institutes of the **Joint Research Centre** (JRC) for European Commission's in-house science service, which helps the European Commission (EC) in the European Union policymaking process.

The Institute's main competencies consist in providing policy options analysis and policy impact assessment, analysing the socio-economics of new technologies, delivering techno-economic tools and platforms to their customers, and managing information exchange and consensus-building among policy-makers and stakeholder on highly complex techno-economic issues.¹⁷

The aim was to provide **evidence-based scientific support** to the European policy-making process in the field of the EoW material and with the proposal to **draft guidelines and a general methodology** to develop EoW Criteria for the main waste stream in the EU. In parallel has been developed the study of three pilot case studies (aggregates, compost and aluminium and steel scrap) in support of the methodology.

The European Commission can adopt the technical proposal as Regulation. So far, the Criteria have been laid down for:

- **iron, steel and aluminium scrap** (see Council Regulation (EU) No 333/2011)
- **glass cullet** (see Commission Regulation (EU) N° 1179/2012)
- **copper scrap** (see Commission Regulation (EU) N° 715/2013)

A **Regulation**, differently from a Directive that needs to be transported into the national law, becomes **immediately enforceable as Law in all the Member States**.

¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Institute_for_Prospective_Technological_Studies

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Risk:

A “flat” application of common policies can produce, for example, compatibility problems between new and existing policies in the MS internal legislation.

Chance:

A “flat” application of common policies is useful for example when common warrantees are needed at EU level for imported goods from non-European states or between the Member States each other.

3.2.1 Definition

As introduced in the previous sections, the overall objective at EU level is to **facilitate the movement of the trade flows**, excluding any risk for the human health and for the environment, but existing legal issues for some MS are not aligned with other national waste legislation and EoW policy.

Risk:

In some cases, a material produced in a location, where is not considered waste, cannot be carried or reused in another country because the policies are not aligned.

Chance:

The writing of EoW criteria could define in each MS in the same way, how and when a material ends to be waste and become again a resource, favouring the perspective of the EU to become a recycling community.

In the “END OF WASTE CRITERIA Final Report”, IPTS defined the EoW Criteria as:

“all the requirements that should be fulfilled by a material derived from waste, and which ensure that the quality of the material is such that its use is not detrimental for human health or the environment. (IPTS, END OF WASTE CRITERIA, Final Report, 2008)”

From this definition, a guideline has been created to develop EoW Criteria. An analysis must be undertaken for **each category of waste**, considering specific material flows.

Another key concept in the WFD it is that:

“the Criteria shall include limit values for pollutants where necessary and shall take into account any possible adverse environmental effects of the substance or object. (Directive 2008/98/EC, 2008)”.

This introduces the concept of the **quality of the material** candidate to a EoW Criteria. The monitoring of pollutant levels and of physical and chemical characteristics are not the only

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

required parameters to ensure the safety and the quality of a material. In a holistic perspective, the control **over each step** of the reuse process is needed:

- input materials;
- processes and techniques;
- quality control procedures;
- product quality;
- potential applications or uses.

This approach ensures a high level of control of the process, the protection of human health and environment and of economic aspects. Defining a EoW Criteria for certain materials can help to resolve **incompatibility or inequalities** in the different national frameworks, on issues such as recovery and re-using of the secondary materials. Some national legislations consider some waste as products and not waste, but when these materials are transported and used in other country where are not legislated, are considered waste without a correct waste management control. This represents one of the **main obstacles to the secondary raw materials flows through the MS and non-European states**.

Chance:

The EoW Criteria can resolve gaps and increase the quantity of recovered waste and the related trade, **improving the functioning of the internal market**. Furthermore, the EoW Criteria can clarify all the uncertainties about waste, **increasing** also the **recycling capacity**, avoiding other waste treatment.

Another point is **the removal of unnecessary administrative burdens**, which cannot be motivated for waste with low risk.

Risk:

Sometimes, the status improvement from waste to secondary raw material, if not necessary, means more costs and it is not an incentive to the recycling and the re-use.

The **promotion of the secondary raw materials** is necessary. It is important to let consumers know the high levels of quality of the products from EoW material, through the sharing of product information and characteristics.

Increasing the users' confidence with these quality standards, it is possible to **improve the products from EoW material perception**, with the result of a higher **use of secondary raw materials instead of primary materials**.

Chance:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

A right promotion of the EoW material can increase the market demand and have a positive impact on the recycling rates.

3.2.2 Procedure

The guideline to elaborate a procedure to determinate an EoW Criteria is described in a Technical Report written by IPTS, as required by European Commission.

3.2.2.1 Analysis of Waste Stream

The “analysis of the specific waste stream” is the first step to draft EoW Criteria. This process requires a large amount of information and details. To establish a EoW Criteria is needed to consider every step of the EoW material life cycle, trying to figure out all the touched different fields of interest:

- Technical
- Economic
- Trading
- Legislative (waste and non-waste)
- Environmental
- Health

A set of background data is needed to study each waste stream.

1. Firstly, the **material flows** must be described in these aspects:
 - a. identification of material sources and characteristic of the composition;
 - b. quantities during several years divided per country and per material sub-class.
 - c. any other information about the external collection of the material and the amount used per type of application.
2. Focus on the **potential uses** for the EoW material, the suitability, the Technical limitations and the potential to substitute primary or alternative materials (by collecting quantities used, for each Member state). It is important to **individuate the environmental and health risk** linked to the recycled/secondary materials. In the end, evaluate the new life cycle including the “second life” of the EoW material.
3. List of **applied processes** (with the technical description, emission levels and waste streams) in the production of the EoW material.
4. Collection and understanding of all the **relevant legislation**, involving the material both as waste and as non-waste. Analyse the current **quality assurance schemes** and **standards** to produce equivalent raw material.
5. Description of the **current and potential market**. Starting with the demand in the different geographic zones, the competing materials used in the same fields, list of the different users and the liked demand. The price, also in comparison with the primary materials substituted. The Import and export flows with the aim to identify the various countries that were involved. The potential and the price of the eventual transport streams. Finally, it is necessary to analyse the aspect trends the timing of application and the critical factors for the EoW material market.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

3.2.2.2 Guidance to develop EoW Criteria

The data collection represents the basis to elaborate the main steps towards EoW Criteria.

Risk:

The high level of complexity forces to consider each analysis element on a case by case basis, with the risk to lose the sight of a holistic scenario.

The management of the **material source** and **quality control** is the first step to elaborate an EoW Criteria, with the limitation of the **input waste material sources** it is possible to reduce the risks of pollutants or contaminants, and consequently individuate the main hazardous substances linked to each input stream.

If an EoW material comes from a production process that respects **quality standards**, a control system is not needed.

Control over process can guarantee technical requirements for physical and chemical characteristics; also, it guarantees high levels of insurance for human health and the environment. By use of standards the waste can be labelled for:

- Suitable purposes;
- Inappropriate purposes;
- Conformity with the destination market standards; and
- Conformity with the established EoW Criteria standards.

Chance:

When the material ceases to be waste, becoming a normal product, it starts to be related to the normal product legislation in terms of environment and human health safety as well as pollution control.

The **conformity record of each step of the production chain** with the **control of the quality procedures** and standards equates EoW material with a normal product, extending the producer responsibility in certifying the quality and the fitness for use of the produced material.

Chance:

The **quality control procedures** can be certified by the standard of quality management system like, for example, ISO 9000.

However, is impossible to define a quality assurance scheme within EoW Criteria, valid for all materials streams, finding the critical steps and verify the compliance with the EoW Criteria.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

3.2.2.3 Impact Assessment

Before that the EoW Criteria can be forwarded as a proposal to the EU Commission, it is necessary to carry out an impact assessment in different fields of interest.

Environment and health

The Article 6 (d) of the revised WFD requires the human health and environmental safety. The introduction of new EoW Criteria should develop best practices in waste management finalized to improve the safety levels, reducing the impacts of the products with new pollution limits. This reflection shall be applied in the different EU Countries in the different geographic conditions, in the different use of the product (also outside of those identified by the EoW Criteria).

The introduction of the Criteria and the pollutant concentration limits [in many cases covered by the Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC) Directive] have direct and indirect effects on the health and the environment:

- influencing the quality;
- reducing emission in the production processes;
- increasing the recycling;
- producing quality assurance.

Chance:

The use of EoW Criteria can also be useful for:

- overwriting the different interpretations or gaps of legislation;
- forcing the application of the Law;
- increasing the control also over the non-EoW materials;
- reducing the environmental and the human health risk.

The way to approach the **Impact Assessment** (in all the fields) is to **compare “end of waste Criteria scenario” with a “no action scenario”**.

The **Life Cycle Impact Assessment** should be used to considerate the entire material “use and recovery chain”, also the processes not directly linked.

The typical categories used in an **LCIA** for EoW Criteria cover:

- all the **main environmental media**, especially soil, water and air;
- the analysis of the **impact on ecosystems**;
- **human well-being** and **resources productivity** and
- the chain in the **end-point**.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Risk:

Lacks in the legislation can involve risks for human health and environment, that are linked to aspects associated to the new streams of storage, to the transport, the processing and the reuse. The waste materials must respect standards and legislation for non-waste material, and not only the waste legislation.

The balance for the proposed EoW Criteria with the no-action scenario must be positive, otherwise, the EoW Criteria drafting should be reviewed.

Economic Impact - others potential field

Generally, the approach to the **Economic Impact** can be compared with the one that is used for Environmental and Health Impact. The main variations affect the **recovery chain** (see Figure 9). As showed in the previous sections, the recovery represents the phase between the production and the reallocation of the waste material. The main direct costs consequent to the EoW Criteria adoption, can be attributed to:

- The **new adopted processes**;
- The product **quality increasing** and assurance;
- **Administration and regulation** compliance.

Figure 9. Recovery chain

Risk:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

All the costs linked to the alignment of the company to the new legislation can be hardly faced by the small and medium-sized enterprise; besides, the operation costs linked to the quality management and procedures can be hardly amortised.

Effect on the Market

The EoW Criteria can have an effect on the market, creating or removing a segmentation, changing the preferences in the investment management, in the waste field, in the direction of alternative treatments.

The market impact assessment must consider some important spots:

- The **effect on the market of the introducing the EoW Criteria**;
- If the market is ready to **absorb the new material** production;
- The modification in the **equilibrium** of the market of the other materials (which are substituted by the new EoW materials).

Legislative Impact

The legislative effects are linked to all previous part of the impact assessment, from the environmental and health aspects to the market and economic field.

Until the EoW Criteria have an effect, in all the MS the waste legislation applied to the material as waste is no longer valid. For all intents and purposes, with the new EoW Criteria introduction, the material cases to be waste and become a secondary raw material.

The **Legislative Impact Study** deepens the **MS capability to align their existing legislation** (e.g. introducing complementary measure) with the new EU EoW Criteria Regulation.

Risk:

Some MS have already in force a National Legislation that defines EoW Criteria. Besides, such legislative frameworks must be updated after the EU EoW Criteria introduction.

Other socio-economic impacts

It is important to include in the assessment all the other potential field of interest where the introduction of EoW Criteria can have effects, such as, for example, **social aspects** or **political consequences**.

A schematic flow diagram of the proposed operational procedure guideline for study and the implementation of EoW Criteria for a specific material stream, is reported below.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 10. EoW Criteria drafting process¹⁸

¹⁸ (IPTS, END OF WASTE CRITERIA, Final Report, 2008)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

4 EoW CRITERIA AND PACKAGING PLASTIC WASTE

The main document here analysed to face out the main issues on the drafting of a EoW for the Packaging Waste Plastics (PPW) stream is the **JRC Technical Report** entitled “**EoW Criteria for waste plastic for conversion**”. It can be interpreted as a guideline and can be taken as starting point around the EoW waste plastic theme, by focusing on PPW.

This technical report defines a possible set of EoW criteria, developing a comprehensive techno-economic analysis of the waste plastic production chain and an analysis of the economic, environmental and legal impacts when such waste plastic ceases to be waste. All the steps described in the “END OF WASTE CRITERIA Final Report” (see 3.2) are taken into account with a specific focus on waste plastic.

The first part of that report presents an overview of plastic waste, its composition, the types and sources, and their processing, grading and recycling. The chapter contains information on the fulfilment of the four conditions set out in Art. 6 of the Directive, namely the existence of a market demand and a specific use for plastic waste, the identification of health and environmental impacts that may result from a change of status, the conditions for conformity with standards and quality requirements, and the legislative framework of waste plastic inside and outside waste legislation.

For the aim of this deliverable, only the issues linked to the **PPW stream have been analysed**, with the aim to find barriers and opportunities for drafting EoW criteria for this specific waste stream.

To complement and provide additional info useful for the understanding of the specific issues for EoW of PPW, firstly an overview of the material stream characteristics is included, followed by updated market data and statistics. Finally, the main features of the technical proposal are showed and commented.

Within the activities of Task 6.3 of CIRC-PACK, on 25th October 2017, Hans Saveyn from the JRC-IPTS was contacted, to gather updated news about the status of EoW Regulation for waste plastics: at that time, no initiative of the EU Commission to draft an EoW Regulation for waste plastic was declared to be on-going.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

4.1 Management, production and trending of waste plastics

The most common polymer types used for packaging plastics products is LDPE (32%), followed by HDPE (19%), PP (19%) and PET (16%) in 2010, in total approximately 18 million of tonnes.¹⁹

The vast variety of the plastics material used can help to understand the complexity of this particular material stream. The most used plastic materials in the packaging production are reported in Annex 3 - Plastic material for packaging.

Below, an interesting table about the main polymers types in a household packaging application is presented.

Applications		Most common polymers used
Bottles	Dairy products	HDPE
	Juices, Sauces	HDPE, barrier PET, PP
	Water, Soft Drinks	PET, barrier PET
	Beer and alcoholic beverages	Barrier PET
	Oil, vinegar	PET, PVC
	Non-food products (cleaning products, toiletries, lubricants, etc.)	HDPE, PET, PVC
	Medical products	PET
Closures	Caps and closures of bottles, jars, pots, cartons, etc.	PP, LDPE, HDPE, PVC
Bags and sacks	Carrier bags	LDPE, HDPE
	Garbage bags	HDPE, LDPE, LLDPE
	Other bags and sacks	LDPE, LLDPE, HDPE, PP, woven PP
Films	Pouches (sauces, dried soups, cooked meals)	PP, PET

¹⁹ EoW Criteria for Plastic

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

	Overwrapping (food trays and cartons)	OPP, bi-OPS
	Wrapping, packets, sachets, etc.	PP, OPP
	Wrapping (meat, cheese)	PVDC
	Collection shrink film (grouping package for beverages, cartons, etc.)	LLDPE, LDPE
	Cling stretch wrap film (food)	LLDPE, LDPE, PVC, PVDC
	Lidding (heat sealing)	PET, OPA, OPP
	Lidding (MAP and CAP foods)	Barrier PET, barrier layered PET/PE and OPP/PE
	Lidding (dairy)	PET
Trays	Microwaveable ready meals, puddings	PP, C-PET
	Ovenable-ready meals	C-PET
	Salads, desserts	A-PET, PVC
	Vegetables	PP, EPS
	Fish	PP, PVC, A-PET, EPS
	Confectionery	PVC, PS
	Dairy products	PP, PS
	Meat, poultry	A-PET, PVC, EPS
	Soup	PP, A-PET
Others	Blisters	PET, PVC
	Pots, cups and tubs	PP, PS
	Service packaging (vending cups, etc.)	PS
	Protective packaging ('clam' containers, fish crates, loose filling, etc.)	EPS

It is possible, from the analysis of the list of the plastic materials used for packaging, to understand the great and complex variety of this waste stream. Considering the whole

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

plastic waste stream, the plastic packaging constitutes approximately 62% of total waste generated.

Figure 11. Total post-consumer plastic waste by application (EU27+2 - 2010)

More than the half part of wasted plastics consists of plastic packaging. Until 2015, LDPE was the most recovered polymer for Packaging uses, but in the last years, others plastic material such as PP and PET are increasing. This can change the management of the waste plastics streams.

Figure 12. Plastic PACKAGING waste treatment in 2016 (EU28+NO/CH)²⁰

²⁰ Source: Conversion Market & Strategy GmbH

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 13. Plastic PACKAGING waste recycling rate in 2015 (EU28+NO/CH)²¹

Figure 14. Plastic PACKAGING waste recycling rate trade (EU28+NO/CH)²²

²¹ Source: Eurostat

²² Source: Eurostat

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Chance:

Some MS do not have the technology or financial resources to treat waste plastics at the local level, then they export a significant part of waste plastics for treatment. The gap can be filled with private/public common projects to share the “know-how” between the MS.

For a domestic generation, the biggest exporter of plastic packaging waste is Luxembourg (39%), followed by Belgium (27%) and Sweden (18%). Furthermore, Ireland and Bulgaria import more plastic than it is exported. These MS handle an additional plastic packaging waste amount from other countries.

In general, total imports from the MS to the other MS is higher than the imports from non-European states. USA is the most important non-European source, principally for the PE, PP and PVC.

Risks:

China and Hong Kong are the main waste plastics importers. This means that, up to date, not all the plastic waste can be re-processed between the EU MS.

Currently, a high share of plastic waste is exported from EU and re-processed elsewhere.

Pre-consumer waste plastic streams are not well recorded like the post-consumer waste plastic. These wastes are produced and directly reused in the industrial processes or sold to companies involved in the recycling stages. It is important to remember that **pre-consumer waste plastic generation for thermoplastics is very low,**

Chance:

All the plastic scraps from the production are reprocessed without leaving the facilities (not considered as waste)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

4.2 Waste plastic reprocessing and recycling

Figure 15. Waste plastic reprocessing and recycling cycle²³

The steps of the plastic waste toward the recycling start from the “**Reprocessing**” that we can define as the sum of all the steps between the **final user and the plastic recyclers/converters**.

4.2.1 Collection

The streams of plastics waste are split into two main categories: from **industrial/commercial** use and from the **domestic user**.

Figure 16: PACKAGING plastic waste generated in 2016 (EU28+NO/CH)²⁴

When the **industrial and commercial plastic waste** is collected through agreements between the parties, the level of homogeneity and commercial potentiality have high levels.

²³ Elaborated from EoW Criteria for Plastic

²⁴ Packaging Europe Ltd.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Regarding the collection of plastic waste by **municipalities** two main waste streams can be found, from industrial (in general with higher added value) or from a **household** that will collect in two main ways:

- **Kerbside or door-to-door collection:** The citizens are the first actor in the separation of the recyclable materials. This is the most effective way to collect household waste plastics (Typically, 40 to 60% return from this type of collection). The Door-to-door collection has a low level of contamination and also, it's easier obtaining a "mono-material collection".
- **Drop-off locations or collection points:** The citizens bring their collected waste to specific collection points. The level of recyclable waste is typically lower than the previous method (10% -- 30%). The typical type of collection is a Multi-material collection.

When the waste plastic is collected with mixed municipal solid waste, it can be separated from other dry recyclables but the resulting materials are very contaminated and need treatments.

Chance:

Mono-materials can be recovered from refill/deposit systems. It is a great opportunity for closed-loop recycling as the PET bottle, or for other uses (as in the textile industry). The return rates of this approach are high and can arrive around 90%.

Until now, this practice is popular in the north Europe MS, but more and more common in the others one. Furthermore, EU MS combine a selective collection system of the plastic packaging waste with "**green-dot system**".

Figure 17. green-dot symbol

The Green Dot is a system born in Germany in the 1990s, promoted by the environment minister driven by the Packaging Waste Directive. The basic idea of the Green Dot is that consumers who see the logo know that the manufacturer of the product contributes to the cost of recovery and recycling. This can be with household waste collected by the authorities (e.g. in special bags - in Germany these are yellow), or in containers in public places such as car parks and outside supermarkets.

The system is financed by the green dot licence fee paid by the producers of the products. Fees vary by country and are based on the material used in packaging (e.g. paper, plastic,

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

metal, wood, cardboard). Each country also has different fees for joining the scheme and ongoing fixed and variable fees. Fees also take into account the cost of collection, sorting and recycling methods.

In simple terms, the system encourages manufacturers to cut down on packaging as this saves them the cost of licence fees.

Chance:

A good collection system can prevent and simplify the sorting process, also the cost savings. It is possible to collect high-quality packaging waste **avoiding the treatment costs and transportation costs**.

Chance:

Improve communication between householder and industries.

4.2.2 Sorting

The recycling of the waste plastics is generally better than the incineration, from the environment standpoint (avoiding of raw material) and from cost comparison.

Chance:

It is useful to improve and invest in the technologies that can develop sorting methods.

The choose among these technologies depends on the type of input material and requested purity of output material. Furthermore, the **sorting operation can be acted manually** or by using **automated systems**.

Two are the main techniques based on the fiscal properties of waste plastics:

Density	Air Classifier
	Flotation sorting
	Centrifuge
	Cyclone and hydro cyclone
Optical proprieties	NIR (Near Infra-Red) spectroscopy
	Raman spectroscopy (monochromatic laser light)

The most common method to sort packaging waste is the **NIR spectroscopy**, but better results can be obtained through the combination of different techniques.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Generally, **specific facilities conduct the sorting operation** (Material Recovery Facilities), in fact, the separation and selection phases are highly sensitive and need of specific competencies.

A wrong method of sorting could be a risk for health and safety. The PVC and PET, for example, if mixed in the recycling phase, can release harmful substances (hydrochloric gases) or compromise the quality of the final product.

Chance:

A correct and efficient collection process can help the sorting phase, avoiding costs for the complex splitting of similar and common plastic materials as PVC and PET.

4.2.3 Removal of contaminants

Waste plastics from complex streams need to be decontaminated from macro and microscopic contaminations. High levels of purification can be obtained through a long and expensive process like desorption.

Chance:

“Non-pure” waste plastics can be used for harmless uses, as not-food contact fibres.

4.2.4 Cleaning process

The main aim of the cleaning process is removing the waste plastics from “oils”, in fact, a lot of the principal types of plastic are **fat-soluble**.

The simplest and most common way to clean the waste plastics is washing them with hot water that can include detergents. In this way, it is easy to remove glue, paints and food.

Risk:

Residues of oils can affect the quality of the final recycled materials.

The washing process consumes a lot of water and energy (used to warm and agitate the water).

4.2.5 Recycling

64% of the post-consumer plastic packaging waste is generated from households, the remaining 36%, comes from the trade/ industry segment. The recycling rate for trade and

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

industry sector reached 46.5% (42.8% in 2014), while recycling for the household segment obtained 37.8% (37.7%).²⁵

This information is important considering that the recycling methods of the packaging plastics waste depends especially on the streaming origin.

Figure 18: PACKAGING plastics waste recycling in 2016 (EU28+NO/CH)²⁶

Two kinds of recycling processes for plastic materials can be discerned:

1) Mechanical recycling consists of physical actions that preserve the chemical propriety. This recycling way is easier when the collection and sorting phases are efficiently done. This step, usually acted by MRF (material recovery facilities), are **not needed for pre-consumer waste plastics**.

2) **Feedstock recycling**, called also **chemical recycling**, obtains varied by-products as new monomers or hydrocarbon, that permits to produce **new plastic materials and fuels**. In the latter case, the process is considered as energy recovery and not as recycling.

The feedstock is used typically for mixed or contaminated waste plastics. The choice of this path is the **last chance** in a perspective of a sustainable recycling process.

In a pyramidal structure of plastic recycling, its position is just before the energy valorisation.

²⁵ <https://packagingeurope.com/plastic-packaging-waste-statistics-2016-recycling/>

²⁶ Packaging Europe Ltd.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 19. Pyramidal structure of plastic recycling²⁷

Chance:

Improvement in sorting and separation can help mechanical recycling, less resource-consuming than feedstock recycling.

Chance:

Smart design techniques can avoid virgin plastics needs.

In food-application, for example, the sandwich structure is a technique that permits the contact of the food with the virgin plastic material of which chemical proprieties are known and controlled, using the non-pure recycled plastic as overburden of the final packaging.

Additives in waste plastics are very hard to remove or separate during the recycling. Also, they can affect not just the proprieties of the final product but also can be dangerous for health and environment.

Risk:

Some additives can migrate from the waste plastics if in contact with solvents or fats.

Chance:

The use of additives can have positives aspects, under the control of the legislation (REACH/CLP) through risk and exposure assessments.

²⁷ Elaborated from EoW Criteria for Plastic

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

4.2.6 Use of the recycled waste plastics;

Below, the main uses of the recycled waste plastics are summarized.

<i>High-density polyethene (HDPE)</i>	<i>Containers, toys, housewares, industrial wrapping and film, gas pipes</i>
<i>Low-density polyethene (LDPE)</i>	<i>Film, bags, toys, coatings, containers, pipes, cable insulation</i>
<i>Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)</i>	<i>Fibres, bottles, film, food packaging, synthetic insulation</i>
<i>Polypropylene (PP)</i>	<i>Film, battery cases, microwave containers, crates, car parts, electrical components</i>
<i>Polystyrene (PS)</i>	<i>Electrical appliances, thermal insulation, tape cassettes, cups, plates</i>
<i>Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC)</i>	<i>Window frames, pipes, flooring, guttering, applications not related to the original use (traffic signals, shoes, etc.)</i>

Risk:

The food-contact material needs of high level of purity. This is impossible to obtain outside a **closed-loop system** (as PVC recycling for beverage packaging), without decontamination treatments (expensive and resource-consuming).

4.2.7 Structure of reprocessing industry

As described before, the reprocessing industry includes different actors and is largely bound to the national authorities. Each of the reprocessing activities (depicted in the previous sections) can be undertaken by different actors, public, private or the same company that produce the waste plastic. Principally, **SMEs** are involved, as specific facilities that sell services for the different reprocessing phases.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 20. Structure of reprocessing industry²⁸

After a first introduction of the waste plastics stream, the EoW technical report collects data process about the main fields of interest:

- Economic and market aspects of plastic recycling:
 - Costs of plastic recycling, management and administration work;
 - Prices.
- Market characteristic, size, potential, suppliers and users;
- Technical specifications and standards for recycled plastics and uses (quality control);
- **Legislative aspects:** waste legislation and for recycled plastics as products; and
- Environmental and health data and information.

After the data collection about the waste plastics stream, the JRC-IPTS described the main requirements to adhere to the EoW Criteria:

- Product quality:
 - The content of contaminants: non-plastic components and non-targeted plastics;
 - Detection of hazardousness and alignment with REACH/CLP/POPs.
- Input materials:

²⁸ Elaborated from EoW Criteria for Plastic

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Restriction of sources.
- Treatment processes and techniques;
- Provision of information.

As the last item, the JRC-IPTS drew up a description of impacts about the main aspects:

- Environment and health;
- Legislation;
- Economics and Market.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

4.3 Legislative Aspects and Impacts

Some national policies in force for waste plastics, de facto define some reprocessed product as a non-waste product.

"This recognition is frequently the result of case-by-case agreements between the producers and the authorities (local/regional/national) with competences in activity licensing and the determination of waste/non-waste status. This situation would clearly benefit from harmonisation at EU level, as it is currently dependent on national rules that may be diverging and currently favour some more lenient markets in detriment of others where Criteria are applied more strictly." (IPTS, End-of-waste criteria for waste plastic for conversion, 2014)

It is necessary to consider that when the EoW Criteria are respected, the material ceases to be waste, consequently it will be necessary to consider all legislation that regulates the marketing and use of the plastic material as a product:

- Restriction of hazardous substances in EE equipment (RoHS) Directive;
- REACH Regulations
- CLP Regulations;
- Legislation on plastics intended for food contact;
- The Persistent Organic Pollutant (POP) Regulation
- VAT.

Risk:

To reach the EU objective of unifying the national MS policies with a EoW Criteria for waste plastics is more difficult than expected because the waste plastics stream is too complex at level of variety of material sources, commercial chains, and national legislation that are too structured to find a midpoint between all the EU State Members, taking in account the non-European markets.

A general overview of the relevant characteristics of the main legislation considered for plastic products, are reported in Annex 4 - Legislation for Plastic materials as a product.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

5 BIOPLASTICS FOR PACKAGING

Bioplastics materials need a specific analysis, since the issues linked to them are “not traditional” and the development of these materials registered a great expansion in the last years. Nowadays it is generally acknowledged that it is possible to find a valid bioplastic alternative for almost each fossil-based plastic and use.

As introduced in the previous sections, the analysis of legislative framework regarding bioplastics and their management, is started before the last amendments of the WFD. The team reported findings on the previous version of the Directive but also the issues of last update.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

5.1 Bioplastic materials

It is important to underline that **biobased is not equal biodegradable**. Biodegradability is a propriety of the plastic material and does not depend by the resource from which the plastic material was produced, but only by the chemical composition and structure.

- The term **biobased** means that the material or product is (partly) derived from biomass (plants). **Biomass used for bioplastics** stems from e.g. corn, sugarcane, or cellulose.²⁹
- **Biodegradable Plastics** are characterised by **biodegradation**, that is a **chemical process** during which microorganisms that are available in the environment convert materials into natural substances such as water, carbon dioxide, and compost (**artificial additives are not needed**). The process of biodegradation depends on the surrounding environmental conditions (e.g. location or temperature), on the material and on the application.³⁰

We can assume three main typologies of Bioplastics, **biobased**, **biodegradable**, or **both**:

- **Biobased or partially biobased non-biodegradable** plastics such as biobased PE, PP, or PET (so-called drop-ins) and biobased technical performance polymers such as PTT or TPC-ET;
- **Plastics that are both biobased and biodegradable**, such as PLA and PHA or PBS;
- **Plastics that are based on fossil resources and are biodegradable**, such as PBAT.

Figure 21. Biodegradable and Biobased plastics³¹

²⁹ Source: European Bioplastics

³⁰ Source: European Bioplastics

³¹ Source: European Bioplastics

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Chance:

With the **same proprieties of the fossil-based plastics**, bio-based plastic boasts a **reduced carbon footprint** and additional waste management options such as **composting**, but they can be **mechanically recycled in existing recycling streams**.

Currently, bioplastics represent about one per cent of the about 320 million tonnes of plastic produced annually, but 85 percent of plastics could technically be substituted with biobased plastics (according to ProBIP, 2009)³².

*Global production capacities of bioplastics 2017
(by material type)*

*Bio-based PP and PEF are currently in development and predicted to be available in commercial scale in 2020.

Source: European Bioplastics, nova-Institute (2017).

More information: www.bio-based.eu/markets and www.european-bioplastics.org/market

Figure 22. Global Production capacities of bioplastics (2017)³³

Chance:

New materials such as PLA, PHA, cellulose or starch-based materials offer new functionalities such as **biodegradability** and **compostability**.

³² Source: European Bioplastics

³³ Source: European Bioplastics, nova-Institute (2017)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

5.2 Bioplastic Waste management

Better use of compostable plastics can help to divert organic waste from landfills and incineration to organic recycling.

This is possible through the development of targeted policies that address new perspectives for bioplastic materials.

Chances:

- Including organic recycling (in the form of composting and anaerobic digestion and in the WFD's definition of recycling)
- Including waste with biodegradability properties in the bio-waste definition of the WFD.
- Obliging MS to separately collect bio-waste;
- Requesting MS to support the organic recycling of bio-waste;
- Obliging MS to separately collect recyclable plastic.

One of the fundamental concepts regards the creation of equal access to sustainably grown and affordable bio-based feedstock for bio-based products, so that EU MS can attract investments from global bioplastic companies:

- Recommending that supporting instruments at European level are equally bestowed to industries using biomass;
- Assess the use of biodegradable and compostable plastics in applications where contamination with food or other types of residues make plastics hard to recycle.
- Recognising and promoting the properties bio-based, biodegradability and composability, where applicable, in upcoming product design requirements under the Eco-design principles.
- Implementing Green Public Procurement legislation including Criteria regarding the bio-based content of a product. Furthermore, waste management options such as organic recycling should be considered regarding relevant product categories.
- Continuing the development of standards for bio-based products and implementation of standards available.³⁴

Chances:

"Do not use" concept: in the design of some plastic packaging it could optimize the use and the scrap.

³⁴ Source: European Bioplastics

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Bio-based plastics can contribute towards emissions reduction.

Risks:

The standards impose, for example for food packaging, stringent rules.

Bio-based plastics are an innovative industry with a dynamic growth rate and an immense environmental, social and economic potential. With the right framework conditions in place, bio-based plastics produced in the EU could grow to more than 5 million tonnes per year (approximately 10% of plastics production in the EU)³⁵, which would translate in job opportunities. Furthermore, **Bio-based plastics can contribute towards the EU 2020 emissions reduction targets** and beyond. Especially when considering that by 2030 20% of the global oil production is estimated to be used for plastics production.³⁶

Bio-based plastics are made from various bio-based feedstock such as sugar beet, corn or cellulose, but the growing of feedstock for bio-based plastics' global annual production relies on **only 0.01 of the global agricultural area**.³⁷

The major share of bio-based plastics produced is **suitable for existing mechanical recycling** streams (PE / PET), and some bio-based plastics are also compostable i.e. industrial compostable in corresponding facilities.

Compostable plastic bags help to collect more bio-waste, **diverting it from other waste streams such as landfill and incineration**, moreover, compostable plastics can contribute to stronger secondary raw material markets (compost) with a **focus on organic recycling**. About 100 million tonnes of bio-waste are not collected. Compostable plastics can help to collect this unused potential and thereby creating 20.000 jobs in the waste management sector.³⁸

CEN has developed a range of standards defining bio-based products such as bio-based plastics (e.g. EN 16137 bio-based content testing) and composability of plastics (e.g. EN 13432 industrial composting). **Corresponding certifications ensure that products deliver what they promise**.³⁹

Chances:

³⁵ Source: European Bioplastics

³⁶ Source: European Bioplastics

³⁷ Source: European Bioplastics

³⁸ Source: European Bioplastics

³⁹ Source: European Bioplastics

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Better design of plastics for less toxicity, more durability and easier recycling.
- More information to raise awareness and encourage responsible behaviour
- Actions to encourage the use of recycled plastic
- Stronger incentives to collect, sort and recycle all plastics

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

5.3 Bioplastics and EU Circular Economy

As anticipated in section 2.3 of this Deliverable, the EU Commission has undertaken an ambitious Circular Economy policy that introduce important issues on the bio-economy.

The European bioplastics industry has a strong record for developing innovative technological solutions and aligning industrial objectives with environmental sustainability. For Europe to reinforce its position as a front-runner of resource efficiency and green growth, forward-looking sectors with strong environmental credentials and growth potential, such as bioplastics, need to be promoted.

Materials used for industrial and commercial purposes should safely (re-)enter re-use, mechanical or biological recycling systems by design or intention. Therefore, a new, more ambitious Circular Economy Package should address a range of economic sectors and:

- Introduce concrete provisions to **stimulate the Bioeconomy** and use of biobased materials.
- Increase waste management efficiency by promoting the **separate collection of bio-waste** for organic recycling.
- Introduce **additional economic measures** to promote the market introduction of biobased products, including Green Public Procurement and an EU-wide Eco-label, both of which consider a certain biobased content of products.

With the right framework conditions in place, the European bioplastics industry could realise its **immense employment growth potential** while helping to lower the impact on the environment within the EU. It is estimated by 2025:

- Production capacities of bioplastics within the EU will have grown twentyfold to 5.7 million tonnes; this amounts to **around 10% of general plastics production**.
- Up to **160,000 high skilled jobs** will have been created.
- The most efficient renewable feedstock, sustainably grown, will be readily available and will be chosen on a case-by-case basis.
- Biobased plastics will have contributed decisively to **reach the EU's 2020 GHG-reduction targets**.
- Biodegradable and compostable plastics will be supporting efficient waste management by facilitating separate bio-waste collection for organic recycling.⁴⁰

There is no doubt that the chemical industry has been investing in the bio economy and **the production of bioplastics in recent years**. Main focus of the industry's initiative within the bio economy lies on advanced bio refineries, which use chemistry to convert renewable resources into sustainable chemicals, materials and fuels.

Just as traditional refineries, bio refineries maximize the use and value of feedstock and exploit all the elements of the feedstock, recycling secondary products and wastes into valuable products, often using bi-products, which fuel the production process. Nevertheless,

⁴⁰ http://docs.european-bioplastics.org/2016/publications/pp/EUBP_PP_Circular_Economy_Package.pdf

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

there is a decisive difference between refineries and bio refineries: the first one uses non-renewable, fossil materials, the second bases its production on **renewable feedstock**.

Bio refineries have wider benefits. They can contribute to achieving national and international energetic objectives (using fractions of biomass for the energy necessary for the production process) and environmental targets, such as the **reduction of GHG emissions** and the **production of sustainable products**. They also facilitate the **development of standards and certification schemes**.⁴¹

Chances:

A supportive policy framework for the circular and bio-based economy along the value-chain is crucial to the development of a strong and robust bioplastics sector.

- Improving waste management efficiency by promoting the separate collection of bio-waste and recyclable plastic;
- Address legal and market barriers hampering the uptake of bioplastics

⁴¹ http://docs.european-bioplastics.org/2016/publications/pp/EUBP_PP_Circular_Economy_Package.pdf

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

5.4 Relevant EU policies

The EU MS are confronting with the availability decrease of non-renewable raw materials like oil, coal and ores are depleting, and the consequential prices increase. The developing of new and more efficient industrial process, as well as a conversion to renewable resources are the main stones where the EU policies are facing.

The legislative issues are central to a right market penetration of biobased plastics products. For this reason, the EU Commission faced the theme of biobased products in various EU strategies. One of which is undoubtedly the **Circular Economy Package**, already addressed in section 2.3.

All intents are aimed to allow biobased plastic to enter all waste collection and treatment systems, **including mechanical recycling and energetic recovery**, in order to equate the plastic waste from fossil sources to renewable sources.

Chances:

- Products certified compostable according to EN 13432 should gain unhindered access to bio-waste collection systems.
- Improve the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD, 94/62/EC) by **clarifying the definition of biodegradable and compostable plastics** through strengthening the link to the harmonised European standard EN 13432.
- **Ban on landfilling for plastic products** and supporting measures in order to increase recycling and recovery of plastic waste.
- Allow EU Member States flexible use of **economic incentives** (e.g. tax exemptions, funding mechanisms) for bioplastics during the market introduction phase.

Impact of the policies is crucial for business in relation with market aspects. For instance, manufacturers of biobased products and bioplastics can either indicate the '**biobased carbon content**' or the '**biobased mass content**' of their products. As these units of measurement differ, the typical numeric percentage value will differ, too, and must be taken into account, **especially when drawing comparisons**.

An example of well-established methodology to measure the biobased carbon content in materials or products is the **14C-method** (EU standard: CEN/TS 16137, corresponding US-standard: ASTM 6866). **Certification schemes and derived product labels** based on the European and the U.S. standard are available – for example by the Belgian certifier Vinçotte or German certifier DIN CERTCO.⁴²

A material or product can also be specified as biobased by **indicating its biobased mass content**. This method is complementary to the 14C-method and takes chemical elements other than the biobased carbon into account, such as oxygen, nitrogen, and hydrogen. The French Association Chimie du Végétal (ACDV) has introduced a corresponding

⁴² <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics/materials/biobased/>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

certification scheme and the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) is currently developing a standard for this particular method.⁴³

Such instruments are all useful in the perspective to develop a structured standard procedure to compare and evaluate the products which derive from the bioplastics and biobased industries.

Chances:

- Improve the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD, 94/62/EC) by **clarifying the definition of biodegradable and compostable plastics** through strengthening the link to the harmonised European standards.
- **Ban on landfilling for plastic products** and supporting measures in order to increase recycling and recovery of plastic waste.
- Allow EU Member States flexible use of **economic incentives** (e.g. tax exemptions, funding mechanisms) for bioplastics during the market introduction phase.

Risks:

- Encouraging MS to **implement measures that promote packaging made from bio-based materials**,
- Promote a **genuinely competitive** and highly innovative bio-economy.
- Improve environmental friendly food packaging (including an assessment of the feasibility of gradually replacing food packaging with biased and/or biodegradable, compostable material in accordance with European standards).⁴⁴

⁴³ <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics/materials/biobased/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics/materials/biobased/>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

5.5 EoW Criteria for Biodegradable waste and Biodegradable plastics

The Commission publicised in 2014 the Technical proposal developed by JRC-IPTS on EoW Criteria for biodegradable waste subjected to biological treatment (compost & digestate).

The proposal is in accordance with **Article 6 of Directive 2008/98/EC** of the European Parliament and of the Council on waste (the Waste Framework Directive), including a possible set of end-of-waste criteria, and guidelines based on a comprehensive techno-economic analysis of:

- the biodegradable waste;
- derived compost/digestate production chain and;
- analysis of the economic, environmental and legal impacts.

The final aim of an end-of-waste criteria, as explained in the chapter 3.2, is to avoid confusion about the waste definition and to clarify when certain waste that has undergone recovery ceases to be waste.

Recycling should be supported by creating legal certainty and an equal level playing field and by removing unnecessary administrative burdens. The end-of-waste criteria should provide a high level of environmental protection and an environmental and economic benefit, considering the EoW material as a product.

The structure of the proposal follows the model of the final report on End of Waste Criteria developed by JRC-IPTS and it shows up as set of guidelines on how to apply Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Thinking to planning the management of bio-waste.

The document contains all the issues that include biodegradable waste in order to assist decision-makers in making the best use of biodegradable waste in line with the waste hierarchy, but it does not report special key points on the issues on biodegradable plastic waste.

The Bio-waste is defined as biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, restaurants, caterers and retail premises, and comparable waste from food processing plants. It does not include forestry or agricultural residues, manure, sewage sludge, or other biodegradable waste such as natural textiles, paper or processed wood. It also excludes those by-products of food production that never become waste.

The proposal points out how the environmental threat from bio-waste (and other biodegradable waste) is the production of **methane from such waste decomposing in landfills**, which accounted for some 3% of total greenhouse gas emissions in the EU-15 in 1995. The Landfill Directive (1999/31/EC) obliges MS to reduce the amount of biodegradable municipal waste that they landfill to 35% of 1995 levels by 2016 (for some countries by 2020).

The Landfill Directive does not prescribe specific treatment options for the diverted waste.

The most significant benefits of proper bio-waste management - besides avoided emissions of greenhouse gases - would be **the production of good quality compost and bio-gas** that

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

contribute to enhanced soil quality and resource efficiency, as well as a higher level of energy self-sufficiency, avoiding option such as incineration or landfilling.

As motioned in the previous chapters the landfilling is the worst waste management option for bio-waste. However, for the management of biodegradable waste diverted from landfills, there seems to be **several environmentally favourable options**.

While the waste management hierarchy also applies to the management of bio-waste, **in specific cases it may be justified** to depart from it as the environmental balance of the various options available for the management of this waste depends on a number of local factors:

- collection systems,
- waste composition and quality,
- climatic conditions,
- the potential of use of various waste-derived (products such as electricity, heat, methane-rich gas or compost).

Therefore, **national strategies for waste management is needed**, basing on a structured and comprehensive approach (for example Life Cycle thinking approach).

The subject of the reprocessing in the production cycle of biodegradable waste, especially of plastic origin, is not addressed if not in a generic way by the proposal. This underlines how the issues linked to the biodegradable plastics material is underestimated and that there is a substantial procedural lack at European level on the recycling and reutilization of these potential second raw resources.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

6 BILATERAL AND MULTILATERAL TRADE AGREEMENTS

In the previous chapters the EoW has been analysed as a possible solution to overcome the legislative barriers in the European Framework. Besides, within the desk-based analysis, a further legislative instrument already used by MS, which allows the overcoming of legislative differences and the transit of products and materials, including waste, i.e. the **Bilateral and Multilateral trade agreements** have been investigated

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

6.1 General overview

Towards the objective to improve the international commercial flow of waste plastics, the MS can stipulate trade agreements. **Bilateral and Multilateral trade agreements** are commerce treaties between two or more nations.

Risk:

Since they are many countries involved, agreements are difficult to negotiate

Chance:

The agreements **reduce tariffs** and make it easier for businesses to **import and export**.

Multilateral agreements make all signatories treat each other the same. This means that no country can give better trade deals to one country than it does to another. That levels the playing field. It is especially critical for **emerging market countries**. Many of them are smaller in size, making them less competitive.

Chance:

The possibility of standardizes commerce Regulations for all the trade partners allow the companies to save legal costs since they follow the same rules for each country.

Risk:

Bilateral trade agreements tend to favour the country with the best economy.

The biggest disadvantage of multilateral agreements is that they are complex. That makes them difficult and time-consuming to negotiate. Sometimes the length of negotiation entails that it will not take place at all. It is common to any trade agreement that some companies and regions of the country suffer when trade borders disappear. Smaller businesses cannot compete with giant multi-nationals.

Risk:

The negotiations are particular to trade and business, for this they are object of pressures, controversy and protests.

For example, some regional trade agreements are multilateral. The largest is the North American Free Trade Agreement which was ratified on January 1, 1994. NAFTA is between the United States, Canada and Mexico.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Furthermore, all global trade agreements are multilateral. The most successful one is the General Agreement on Trade and Tariffs. One hundred fifty-three countries signed GATT in 1947. Its goal was to reduce tariffs and other trade barriers.

On 15 April 1994, the 123 participating governments signed the agreement in Marrakesh, Morocco. That created the World Trade Organization. It assumed management of future global multilateral negotiations.

The WTO's first project was the Doha round of trade agreements in 2001. That was a multilateral trade agreement between all 149 WTO members, But the high complexity and the strength interests let that the WTO abandoned the Doha round in June 2006.⁴⁵

At European level the standard procedure to conclude a Multilateral Agreement is reported below.⁴⁶

- 1) The initiating country contacts the secretariat and informs it of its intention to initiate a multilateral agreement, the draft of which it transmits by e-mail or by mail.
- 2) The secretariat registers the title of the draft agreement and assigns it a serial number which it communicates immediately to the initiating country.
- 3) The initiating country includes the serial number in the heading of the draft agreement (e.g. "Multilateral agreement M252") and then proposes it to the other Contracting Parties to ADR.
- 4) As soon as the initiating country has reached agreement with the parties concerned on the final version of the clauses of the multilateral agreement, it transmits its signed copy to the secretariat in hard copy and electronically and transmits unsigned copies to the other Contracting Parties to ADR.
- 5) Each signatory country returns its signed copy to the initiating country and transmits a signed copy to the secretariat.
- 6) As soon as the secretariat receives the copy signed by a second signatory, the agreement is entered in a database which may be consulted on e-mail/Internet.
- 7) Each Contracting Party which revokes an agreement shall immediately so inform the secretariat.
- 8) The final clause of a multilateral agreement should be worded as follows:

"This agreement shall be valid until (...)a for the carriage on the territories of those ADR Contracting Parties signatory to this agreement. If it is revoked before then by one of the signatories, it shall remain valid until the above-mentioned date only for carriage on the territories of those ADR Contracting Parties signatory to this agreement which have not revoked it. (date ...) b The competent authority for ADR of (Signature)".
- 9) Where a signatory country signs a multilateral agreement with reservations regarding its application, these reservations shall be expressly mentioned in the copy which it transmits to the secretariat.

⁴⁵<https://www.thebalance.com/multilateral-trade-agreements-pros-cons-and-examples-3305949>

⁴⁶ <https://www.unece.org/ro/trans/danger/multi/multi.html>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Notes

a) Date of expiry of the multilateral agreement which must be indicated by the initiating country in the final version it transmits to the secretariat and to the other Contracting Parties in accordance with paragraph (4) above. This date of expiry must correspond to a maximum period of validity of five years as from the date of signature by the initiating country.

b) Date of signature for each country concerned.⁴⁷

Examples of Multilateral agreements between European MS on the carriage of packaging or waste are reported below:

- M192 Carriage in packagings to which packing instruction P801 applies - Expired on 1 January 2009
- M268 Carriage of packagings, discarded, empty, uncleaned (UN 3509) - Expired on 1 January 2015
- M287 Carriage of certain wastes containing dangerous goods, signed by Austria, Czech Republic, Liechtenstein and Italy - Date of Expiry: Applies from 2 August 2015 up to 1 August 2020

An excellent example of a European agreement on the Transport of materials with special characteristics is the European Agreement concerning international carriage of dangerous goods by road (ADR).

ADR, by the French Accord européen relatif au transport International des marchandises dangereuses par Route, is the European Agreement on the International Transport of dangerous Goods by road, signed in Geneva on 30 September 1957 and ratified in Italy by law 12 August 1962 N. 1839.

Most of the provisions are listed in annexes A (General provisions on hazardous materials and articles) and (B) (provisions on transport equipment.) The rules relate to:

- Classification of hazardous substances in relation to road transport;
- Determination and classification as hazardous of individual substances;
- Conditions of packaging of goods,
- Characteristics of packaging and containers;
- Constructive methods of vehicles and tanks;
- Requirements for means of transport and transport, including travel documents;
- Enabling drivers, the means carrying dangerous goods;

⁴⁷ <https://www.unece.org/trans/danger/multi/multi.html>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Exemptions from compliance with the rules of the agreement.

Chances:

The example of ADR can be applied, as for such a controversial topic as the transport of hazardous waste, to the PPW theme, and is a concrete possibility to resolve one of the main problems in the management of the PPW, the carriage between MS.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

7 MAIN BOTTLENECKS AT EU LEVEL AND DRIVERS FOR POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

Owing to the analysis of legislative framework described in previous sections, a wide number of chances and risks offered by main issues related to the recycling of fossil based plastic waste and biobased plastics has been highlighted.

It is important to emphasize that this document is aimed to report the preliminary results of the activities of Task 6.3, which are based on desk-based research followed by a number of case-study interviews. The "weaknesses and threats" and "strengths and opportunities" derive directly from the "risks" and the "chances" encountered in the previous chapters, in which they have been contextualized and studied.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Legislative weaknesses and threats

From the analysis of documents and other references on the waste issues, it is evident that the **inconsistency in language and definitions is a primary barrier** and a fundamental issue to be solved in order to develop a structured and effective strategy on the plastic packaging waste policies. This lack is evident in the common language related to the waste management, but also in the main legislative pillars.

In the Waste Framework Directive:

- **Not unique “definitions” or missing common “language”** can cause misunderstandings (Despite updates to the 2018 directive, some definitions remain pending, such as “EoW material”).
- **Targets for re-use and recycling are not defined per each material individually.**
- In the prospective to develop EoW Criteria, in the Waste Framework Directive the first two conditions that determinate when an End of waste material can be defined as a bottleneck. In fact, **it is not possible to establish EoW Criteria for materials for which a use and a market are not yet defined.** This is an implicit barrier in the Directive, a **market or the use for certain materials depend from the policy framework itself**, that permits to consider them not only waste but actual raw materials to treat them as such.

In the application of End of waste criteria for PPW:

- An EoW criteria, if adopted, comes in force as Regulation. Differently than a Directive (that needs to be transported into the national law), Regulation becomes immediately enforceable as Law in all the Member States. This “flat” application of common policies can produce, for example, **compatibility problems between new and existing policies in the MS internal legislation.**
- Sometimes, the improvement of the status from waste to secondary raw material, if not necessary, means more costs and it is not an incentive to the recycling and the re-use.
- The high level of complexity forces to the considerate each **analysis element on a case by case basis**, with the risk to lose the sight of a holistic scenario.
- Changes in the regulatory can **involve risks for human health and environment** that are linked to aspects associated to the new streams of storage, to the transport, the processing and the reuse.
- **The EoW materials must respect standards and legislation for non-waste material**, and not only the waste legislation.
- The application of EoW criteria can **impact on costs** linked to the **alignment of the company to the new legislation.**

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **Small and medium-sized enterprise** can amortise more difficultly these costs, together with operation costs linked to the quality management and procedures.
- Special **attention is needed for food-contact material**, in order to guarantee high level of purity.

For biobased and biodegradable plastics:

- Use of biodegradable and compostable plastics in applications where **contamination with food or other types of residues make plastics hard to recycle**.
- Bio-based plastics are made from various bio-based feedstock such as sugar beet, corn or cellulose, this can give of **potential competition with food feedstock**, a clear legislative framework is needed.
- Producers of biobased bioplastics must **not either indicate the 'biobased carbon content' or the 'biobased mass content'** of their products.

In Trade Agreements:

- **Difficulty in negotiation among different countries.**
- Bilateral trade agreements tend to favour the country with the best economy.
- The negotiations are particular to trade and business, for this they receive lots of press, controversy and protests.

The main bottleneck found by the team regards **carriage of potential secondary raw material** (with or without EoW criteria). In some cases, a material produced in a location, where is not considered waste, cannot be carried or reused in another country because the policies are not aligned.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Legislative strengths and opportunities

The main strengths and opportunities found during the desk-based research on the legislative framework are here below summarized.

In the Waste Framework Directive:

- The **MS can use national reduction targets**, maintaining or introducing economic instruments as well as marketing restrictions to reach the Directives targets.
- It will be useful to **adopt a European methodology for the calculation of the annual consumption of plastic packaging**.
- The Directive (Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive) encourages **public information on the impact** of the use of plastic packaging.

In the application of End of waste criteria for PPW:

- “Flat” application of common policies can **control proprieties and safety of imported goods** from non-European states or between the Member States each other.
- The writing of EoW criteria could define in each MS in the same way, how and **when a material ends to be waste and become again a resource**, favouring the perspective of the EU to become a recycling community.
- The EoW Criteria can **resolve gaps** and increase the quantity of recovered waste and the related trade, improving the functioning of the internal market. Furthermore, **the EoW Criteria can clarify all the uncertainties about waste**, increasing also the recycling capacity, avoiding other waste treatment.
- A right **promotion of the EoW material can increase the market demand** and have a positive impact on the recycling rates.
- **Improving communication between householder and industries**, in order to facilitate the EoW materials entrance in the daily use and in the economy.
- **EoW materials must be considered normal product**, in terms of environment and human health safety as well as pollution control.
- **The quality control procedures can be certified** by the standard of quality management system like, for example, ISO 9000.
- **Improve collection system** in order to prevent and simplify the sorting process, also the cost savings. It is possible to collect high-quality packaging waste avoiding the treatment costs and transportation costs.

For biobased and biodegradable plastics:

- With the same proprieties of the fossil-based plastics, biodegradable plastic is associated to a reduced carbon footprint and **additional waste management**

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

options such as composting, but it can be mechanically recycled in existing recycling streams.

- New materials such as PLA, PHA, **cellulose or starch-based materials offer new functionalities** such as biodegradability and compostability and new opportunities for “mono-use” products (with an opportune attention to the ban and limitation in the current legislation).
- **Recognising and promoting** the properties bio-based, biodegradability and composability in upcoming product design requirements.
- **Incentives to collect, sort and recycle all plastics**, included the biobased and biodegradable ones.
- **Measure the carbon content considering the LC**, in order to compare plastics from different sources and promote the **biobased plastics**.

In Trade Agreements:

- **The agreements reduce tariffs** and make it easier for businesses to import and export.
- **Standardize commerce regulations for all the trade partners.**
- **Companies save legal costs** since they follow the same rules for each country.

It is immediately evident that the legislative framework is transversal to all issues involving PPW. Starting from practical difficulties it is possible to deduce the policy measures able to support them.

The findings here summarized constituted the basis for the project team to carry out the insights and interviews that are reported in the next chapters.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8 NATIONAL INSIGHTS

The team performed a detailed analysis of the National Legislative Frameworks of Italy, Spain, Croatia and Turkey, in order to investigate how the EU policy on Packaging Plastic Waste and Circular Economy has been received, and in particular what is the impact of the legislation on the Packaging Plastic Waste actors at national/regional/municipal level.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.1 National Legislation – Italy

In Italy, production of household waste is constantly increasing. It has risen from almost 27,000,000 tonnes in 1997 to around 30,000,000 tonnes in 2012. This means that each private citizen produced today around 504 kg of waste per year.

The average composition of municipal waste is: paper and card 23%, plastic 12%, glass 7%, wood 4%, metal 4%, organic 35%, textiles 5%, other 10%. There are no precise data on packaging, but the proportion is estimated at 20-25%.⁴⁸

The European Commission promotes the first European strategy on the plastic. The strategy was long overdue. Approved on 16th January 2018, by the European Commission in Strasburg, it provides for the only use of recyclable materials for all the packaging in use in the EU by the year 2030. Furthermore, the use of microplastics and of the single-use packaging will be limited.

The Commission has pledged to develop a system of labels for biodegradable and compostable plastics.

In this perspective, with the amendment to the Law on budgetary rules of December 2017, Italy banned the non-biodegradable cotton buds from 2019 and prohibited the use of microplastics in cosmetics from 2020.

Furthermore, the amendment provided the requirement of a clear explanation of the methodology to dispose of the cotton buds on the packaging, in fact, the cotton-bud sticks produced in no-biodegradable plastic material, are highly polluting.

8.1.1 National overview

Firstly, it is important the main legislative pillars on the theme of packaging in Italy are summarized.

The legislative Decree Dlgs 3rd April 2006, n° 152 re-writes, in parallel with the waste legislation, the rules on environment that concern the packaging management and the packaging waste.

The new rules, which replace from the 29th April 2006 (date of the entry in force of the legislative Decree “Dlgs 152/2006”) those of the legislative Decree “Dlgs 22/1997” (so-called “Decreto Ronchi” abrogated from the same date), contained in the “fourth part” of the legislative Decree “Dlgs 152/2006”. In particular, in the articles from 217 to 226 in annexe E, fourth part.

The Directive 2015/720/EU modified the historical Directive on the packaging 94/62/CE opening to the possibility of reducing and removing the use of the plastic light bags, in order to decrease their impact on the environment.

⁴⁸ CONAI - 2013

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

With the Decree Law “**DI 91/2017**”, converted by the Law **123/2017**, Italy transposed Directive EU of 2015, inserting the existing legislation on the environment (decree Law “**DL 2/2012**”, transposed by the Law **28/2012**) in the fourth part of the environmental code, named legislative Decree “**Dlgs 152/2006**”, and dictating new rules on the “lightweight” bags, not legislated before.⁴⁹

8.1.2 Legislation history

This section reports a summary of the Italian legal experience on policies on Packaging, waste and environment, from the perspective of plastic materials issues.

Figure 23: Legislation history of main Italian laws regarding PPW

- 6th July 1995, Decree of the President of the Council of the Ministries. Approval of the **single model for the environment (MUD)** according to with the Law 25th January 1994, n° 70.
- 5th February 1997, Legislative Decree n°22, (named “Decreto Ronchi”). Implementing of the Directive 91/156/CEE on waste, the 91/689/CEE on **hazardous waste and the 94/62/CS on packaging and packaging waste**.
- 15th July 1998, Environment Ministerial Decree. The statute of Plastic Packaging National Consortium.
- 13th May 1999, Law n° 133. **Incentive with ecologic finality**.

⁴⁹ <http://www.reteambiente.it/normativa/imballaggi/>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- 3rd April 2006, Legislative Decree n°152, on the environment, part IV. **Waste and packaging management** and on sites clean-up.
- 5th April 2006, Environment Ministerial Decree n° 186. **Not-hazardous waste individuation subject to simplified procedures for recovering.**
- 18th May 2010, Ministerial Decree n°113, on bottles of recycled polyethene terephthalate (PET)
- 24th March 2012, Law n°28, conversion in Law of Legislative Decree 2/2012 on extraordinary and urgent measures on the environment, back-fill and biodegradable bags.
- 20th September 2013, Ministerial Decree on Health n.134, on bags and tubs in recycled polyethene terephthalate (PET)
- 2013, M268 **Carriage of packaging**, discarded, empty, uncleaned (UN 3509) - Expired on 1 January 2015
- 6th June 2014, Directorial Decree of Ministry of Environment. Provisional approval (accepted with the Directorial Decree of Ministry of Environment 8th April 2016, prot. N° 28) on the Co.N.I.P. system of recycling, recovery, collection and reuse of the plastic pallets.
- 4th August 2014, Directorial Decree of Ministry of Environment. P.A.R.I. system approval, for the second project elaborated and proposed by the company Aliplast Spa.
- 26th May 2016, Environmental Ministerial Decree. Guidelines to calculate the percentage of the separate **collection of the municipal waste**
- 2017: Ministerial Decree 3rd July 2017 n° 142. Regulation with rules on the experimentation of a new system of returnable packaging for water and beer for public use.
- 3rd August 2017, Law n°123. Conversion in Law of the Decree Law 20th June 2017, n° 91. **Disposition on plastics bags** and changes in annexe D, part IV "Dlgs 152/2006" on the **classification of the waste**.
- 4th August 2017, Law n°124. Exemption from payment of the environmental contribution for the packaging producer who will participate in an autonomous consortium.
- 27th December 2017, Law n° 205 named "Legge di Bilancio 2018". Increasing of mixed recycling of plastics waste from separate collection instead of the use of them for energy recovering.

European Directive 2004/12/EC on packaging and packaging waste (which amended and supplemented Directive 94/62/EC) **was transposed into Italian law under Legislative Decree No 152/06** (pursuant to Legislative Decree No 22/97). Article 218 (definitions), paragraph 1, states that: "The following definitions shall apply for the purposes of this Title:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **packaging:** all products made of any materials to be used for the containment, protection, handling, delivery and presentation of goods, from raw materials to finished products, from the producer to the user or the consumer, including non-returnable items used for the same purposes;
- **sales packaging or primary packaging:** packaging conceived so as to constitute a sales unit to the final user or consumer at the point of purchase;
- **grouped packaging or secondary packaging:** packaging conceived so as to constitute at the point of purchase a grouping of a certain number of sales units whether the latter is sold as such to the final user or consumer or whether it serves only as a means to replenish the shelves at the point of sale, and which can be removed from the product without affecting its characteristics;
- **transport packaging or tertiary packaging:** packaging conceived so as to facilitate handling and transport of goods, from raw materials to finished products, or of a certain number of sales units or grouped packaging to prevent physical handling and transport damage, excluding containers for road, rail, sea and air transport”.

Moreover, Annex E, point 2, of Legislative Decree No 152/06 states that the definition of “packaging” shall be based on the following criteria:

- items shall be considered to be packaging if they fulfil the definition above without prejudice to other functions which the packaging might also perform, unless the item is an integral part of a product and it is necessary to contain, support or preserve that product throughout its lifetime and all elements are intended to be used, consumed or disposed of together;
- items designed and intended to be filled at the point of sale and disposable items sold, filled or designed and intended to be filled at the point of sale shall be considered to be packaging provided they fulfil a packaging function;
- packaging components and ancillary elements integrated into packaging shall be considered to be part of the packaging into which they are integrated. Ancillary elements hung directly on, or attached to, a product and which perform a packaging function shall be considered to be packaging unless they are an integral part of this product and all elements are intended to be consumed or disposed of together.

The Ministerial Decree of 22 April 2014 (which transposed European Directive 2013/2/EU in Italy), published in the Official Gazette on 14/06/2014, updated the illustrative examples for the interpretative criteria.

The Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive EU 2015/720 is generic about how the MS must reduce the plastic bags use. They can do it in different ways, such as national reduction targets, with economic instruments or restrictions on the marketing (if according to the principle of the free movement of goods).

The Directive harmonizes the methods to certify if a plastic is biodegradable with the standard EN 13432, with the aim to help the commercial streams between the MS.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

All the MS should have transposed the Directive no later than 27th November 2017, but the Italy, that anticipated the Directive in the 2012 with the Law n°28, didn't transpose with a formal act the Directive.

The EU opened for Italy a procedure of infraction (2017-0127) for the missing transposition of the Directive 2015/720 EU on the use reduction for light plastic bags. With the entry into force on 3rd August 2017 of the Law n°123, the EU interrupted the infraction procedure.

The Law transposed the Directive, by imposing the use of **biodegradable plastic for the "ultra-lightweight" bags from the 1st January 2018**, with other limitation and rules for the plastic bags:

- Marketing ban of the not-biodegradable plastic bags, also for thickness over 50 microns
- Ban of free provision of the biodegradable plastic bags regardless of the thickness.
- The plastic packaging under 15 microns ("ultra-lightweight" bags), directly in contact with foods and used for hygienic reasons (not for carriage), must be:
 - Paid,
 - Biodegradable,
 - Compostable, and
 - with a minimum % of renewable raw material (% that will increase over time).
- The ultra-lightweight bags must be biodegradable and 100% compostable (completely used as compost when it decays), and composed of 40% of renewable raw materials and 60% of the petrochemical material.
- The % of renewable will increase in 2020 at 50% and in 2030 at 60%.

Plastic packaging for hygienic use, with thickness over 15 microns (as the transparent sheet or trays) is not concerned by the Law.

There are also biodegradable plastics from fossil resources that have excellent biodegradable characteristics (such as PBS that decomposes naturally into water and CO₂), but they do not fall in those allowed.

8.1.3 National Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages

8.1.3.1 The CONAi system: Packaging recovery in Italy

The European Directive on packaging and packaging waste (CE/62/94) was drawn up with a view to sustainable development and the definition of the environmental and social responsibilities of business enterprise, public authorities and private citizens.

It was later acknowledged by Italian law in 1997 with Decree 22/97, amended in 2006 by Decree 152/06. With the aim of achieving the recovery and recycling targets set by the

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Directive, Italian law set up CONAI, the national packaging consortium, with obligation of adhesion on the part of all packaging Producers and Users.

CONAI is a non-profit private consortium with an enrolment of over 1,200,000 companies (2012). For the recovery and recycling operations of individual materials CONAI coordinates the activities of the Material Consortia (steel, aluminium, paper, wood, plastic and glass), also set up by the decree.

CONAI funds itself through the "CONAI Environmental Contribution" applied to packaging sold by Producers to Users.

Packaging recovery rose from around 3,500,000 tonnes in 1998 to over 8,400,000 tonnes in 2012, reaching and exceeding the targets set by law.

This achievement was also made possible by the **ANCI-CONAI agreement** (ANCI is the national association of Italian municipalities), which institutionalised the **funding of Italian municipalities for the separate collection of packaging**, by means: of payment to be affected by CONAI through the "environmental contribution".

After "prevention" i.e. minimising the production of waste, CONAI held the solution most effective in dealing with the problem consists in setting up an integrated waste management scheme, which can summarily be described as follows:

- development of an economic, effective and efficient system of selective collection;
- adequate treatment capacity (storage, sorting, etc.) for materials collected;
- development of a recycling industry;
- development of incineration with energy recovery, especially with RDF (refuse-derived fuel/solid recovered fuel) combustion, in order to recover (in heat or electricity) dry waste not collected separately, waste from sorting and treatment, and other typologies of waste as prescribed by law;
- preparation of sites for the management of residual material rendered inert, that is no longer exploitable in other ways.

Producer and User obligations are both responsible for the correct environmental management of the packaging and packaging waste produced by their products.⁵⁰

8.1.3.2 Corepla: Italian Consortium for plastic recycling

Corepla: National Consortium for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages was established in November 1997 in accordance with law decree 22/97, taking over from the former Replastic Consortium, which only dealt with liquid containers, in accordance to the European legislation 94/62 concerning packing material and waste from packages in a different material. The Consortium is now regulated by Law Decree 152/06.

⁵⁰ CONAI website

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

It is part of the "CONAI System" (National Packaging Consortium) and is a no-profit private system with a social character, financed by:

- the Environmental Contribution CONAI concerning packaging on the national market, (produced in Italy or imported, both empty and full) defined and managed by the companies through the same CONAI, therefore it is not subject to the public tax system;
- proceeds from sales of waste after recycling.

At the beginning of 2012 it had 2685 member companies, belonging to the entire life-cycle of plastic packaging (for B and C categories participation is entirely voluntary):

- Category A: companies producing plastic material for the production of packaging
- Category B: companies producing plastic packaging
- Category C: companies using plastic packaging
- Category D: companies that recycle or recover plastic packaging waste after use

It operates according to principles of efficacy, efficiency and cheapness in order to conform to law and achieve the recycling objectives concerning all types of plastic packaging on the market:

- sustaining Municipalities in the development of plastic packaging recycling services and grant them economical compensation to cover the main costs sustained in implementing these services, according to a national agreement established between CONAI and ANCI (National Association of Italian Municipalities);
- guaranteeing recycling start-up of material collected and taking charge of all the necessary preliminary work in order to make it technically feasible and economically sustainable, as well as implementing the energy recovery of the share of collected packages not suitable for the recycling market;
- providing companies that use plastic packaging not managed by the public collection service platforms their free inserting into appropriate receptacles and correct recovery process, moreover with exclusively subsidiary functions in respect to the market;
- making citizens, institutions and companies aware of the best plastic packaging management: pointing them towards a sustainable use and eco-design in order to avoid waste, communicating the qualitative-quantitative increase in recyclable materials, research to develop industrial and recycling market opportunities and applications of recycled plastic.⁵¹

8.1.3.3 Co.N.I.P.: Plastic Packaging National Consortium

The National Plastic Packaging Consortium is a **voluntary consortium** which was established in 1998 in accordance with article 38, sub-paragraph 3, letter a, of the legislative decree 22/97 with the approval of the "Osservatorio Nazionale sui Rifiuti".

⁵¹ <http://www.corepla.it/en/company-profile>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Its aim is to reduce environmental impact by recycling its own polyolefin secondary and tertiary rigid packaging waste.

8.1.3.4 P.A.R.I system: Packaging Waste autonomous management system

The PARI system is an autonomous management system for the “own” packaging waste, as required by the Legislative Decree 152/06, in article 221. PARI has been developed by Aliplast, in quality of PE-LD (film) packaging producer, and it’s based on the company capacity to collect and recovery at least the 60% of the own plastic packaging released for consumption.

The PARI system permits to **develop a circular economy channel** from the packaging to waste and back to packaging in a sector typically characterised of a linear economy model, by ensuring the placing of new raw materials from waste.

The **main requirements** which the legislation requests observing to obtain a recognition of **autonomous system** are:

- implementation of an **efficient system, effective and economic**;
- ability to reach **targets** of recycling and recovery;
- efficacy to **inform the users** on the methods adopted;
- the ability of a **national coverage**;
- the ability to **track** packaging waste of the autonomous system.

The compliance of the requirements above and the activities linked to each phase of the packaging life have allowed to PARI to be recognised by the legislation.

Figure 24: Product with the PARI mark

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

During the commercial relationship, the client/user is informed on the adopted system mode through specific documentation and personal support provided by the PARI staff to promote the added value of the use of recycled and recyclable plastic packaging.

The PARI packaging, in the production phase, is **characterized by a mark** that permits:

- To the final user obtaining information and support to organize the collection
- Recognize and quantify during the collection and the recycling phases the PARI waste from the others.⁵²

8.1.3.5 MOCA: Material and object in contact with food [others plastic packaging “good practise”]

"**Materials and objects in contact with food**" (MOCAs) those materials and Objects Intended to come into contact with food (kitchen utensils and tableware containers and containers, machinery for food processing, **packaging materials**, etc.). This term also indicates the materials and objects that are **in contact with water**, excluding the fixed public or private systems of water supply.

The MOCAs are governed both by national and European measures.

As regards Community rules, Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 (framework rule) lays down the general requirements to be answered by all the materials and articles concerned, while specific measures contain detailed provisions for individual Materials (**plastics**, ceramics, etc.). **Where no specific EU laws exist, Member States may establish national measures.**

In particular, the Regulation stipulates that all materials and articles must be produced in accordance with good manufacturing practice and, under normal or foreseeable conditions of use, shall not transfer in quantities to:

- **Pose a danger to human health**
- Procure an **unacceptable change in the composition of food products**
- Result **deterioration of the organoleptic characteristics.**

In order to ensure the safety of MOCAs and to promote the free movement of goods, the European Union (EU) has a number of legal requirements and forms of control.

Article 11 of the Act of 30 April 1962, no 283 leaves the Minister of Health with the task of establishing by his own decree the conditions, **limitations and tolerances of use** for substances which may be disposed of by **packaging**, receptacles and tools to Food.

The spirit of the legislation is based on the so-called "**positive lists**" of substances, which can be used in the production of such materials with any restrictions and restrictions, as well as on how to control suitability for contact Food.

⁵² <http://www.aliplastspa.com/sistema-pari/il-sistema>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.1.3.6 Waste Regulation authority

The Regulation Authority for Energy, networks and environment, in addition to the tasks in the field of energy and service management, it has task also on waste, as required by the Law n°205 of 27th December 2017 (named "**Legge di Bilancio 2018**"). In particular:

- **Definition of the type schemes of service contracts** for the custody of the waste service;
- Preparation of the **tariff method for the waste Integrated services**;
- **Setting criteria for access tariffs to treatment plants**;
- Approval of **service tariffs**.

In order to finance the operation of the authority, the payment of a contribution by the operators of the Waste Management Service is foreseen.

8.1.3.7 MUD: Single Model of Environmental Declaration

Single Model of Environmental Declaration (MUD) identifies a whole set of declarations, presented annually by subjects as landfills, transporters and waste producers, to the relevant chamber of commerce. Usually the deadline for the presentation is fixed on April 30, although this date may vary slightly from year to year.

In This declaration, the wastes are grouped by typology (by numerical codes called CERs), by producer and provenance.

The statement is the annual budget of the waste loading and unloading registers.

Since 2006, with the entry into force of D. Lgs. 152/2006 No. 152/2006, for the sole producers of non-hazardous waste, the presentation of MUD is no longer mandatory.

With the entry into force of Legislative Decree No. 16/01/2008 N. 4 which amended the new Environmental Code ([Lgs. 152/2006]), the **obligation to introduce MUD for companies producing special non-hazardous waste is reintroduced**, but only for companies with a number of Employees exceeding 10.

The D. Lgs. 205/10 has eliminated the obligation of transmission of MUD for companies, as they are obliged to adhere to the **system of control of the traceability of the waste (SISTR)**.

However, until the SISTR is fully operational, the obligation to prepare the MUD to be presented before 30 April remains in force.

8.1.3.8 SISTR: System of Traceability and Control of Waste

The SISTR (System of control of the traceability of the waste) was born on the initiative of the Ministry of the Environment and the protection of the Territory and the sea, to allow the **computerization of the traceability of the special waste** at the national level and the waste Urban areas of the Campania region.

Combating lawlessness in the special waste sector is a priority for the government to avoid the proliferation of actions and behaviour that do not conform to existing rules and, in

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

particular, to put a **data-collection system** in place to facilitate the tasks entrusted to the supervisory authorities.

In order to control the handling of the special waste throughout the whole chain is fully brought back into the SISTRI system, from intermodal transport to waste disposal, placing particular emphasis on the final phase. Electronic systems are used in order to give visibility to the **incoming and outgoing flow of vehicles in landfills**.

8.1.4 Legislation ongoing – Italian approach to Circular Economy

In November 2017, the document "**Towards a model of circular economy for Italy**" was published, drawn up jointly by the Ministry for the Environment and Protection of the Territory and the Sea (MATM) and by the Ministry of Economic Development (MISE), with the objective of providing a **general framework for the circular economy** and defining **strategic positioning**, is the first step in achieving what will be the real "**national action plan on the circular economy**".

Following the solicitations received from companies, trade associations, consortia, representatives of public administrations, MATM and MISE, with the technical and scientific support of ENEA, have initiated a technical "**working table**" with the aim of identifying appropriate **indicators to measure and monitor the circularity of the economy** and the efficient use of resources at:

- macro (country system);
- medium (region, district, sector, etc.); and
- micro level (single enterprise, organization, Administration).

The indicators elaborated by the technical "working table" and illustrated in the document "**Circular economy and efficient use of resources-indicators for the measurement of the circular economy**" are not, however, to be considered exhaustive but are the basis of departure to arrive, in the future, to the identification of the best solution available for the Italian system in terms of **maximising the economic benefits and safeguarding of resources**.

About the ongoing Italian legislative measures on PPW, aligned with the issues previously outlined and with the EU perspective, are reported below.

- Proposal for a EU Commission directive on the **reduction of the incidence of certain plastic products on the environment**, submitted by the EU Commission on 28th May 2018
- Proposal for a decision EU Council on the financial framework 2021-2027 - own resources for **non-recycled plastic emissions and packaging**, submitted by the EU Commission on 2nd May 2018
- EU Council regulation laying down implementing measures for the European Union's own resources **system-taxation on amounts for non-recycled plastic packaging**, submitted by the EU Commission on 2nd May 2018

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

All the above-mentioned texts have, as a common element, the **reduction of the incidence of non-recyclable plastic** materials in the packaging. It is obvious that this is necessary as much as it is to promote the use of biobased, recycled or biodegradable plastics.

8.1.5 EoW Criteria and transposition of EU policies

In Italy, the Community Directive 2008/98/EC was transposed by Legislative Decree No. 205/2010, which amended part IV of Legislative Decree No. 152/06.

In particular, art. 184-TER reports the **technical criteria for the determination of the cessation of the qualification of waste**, the **flows of material** which must be previously governed and the **procedures to follow** for the amendment of the implementing rules.

However, the Italian legislator, as well as the community legislature, has **postponed to a subsequent discipline the definition of the specific criteria** on the basis of which it will be possible to **decide whether a material ceased to be waste**.

In fact, paragraph 2 of art. 184-ter of D. Lgs. No. 152/06 stipulates that "in the absence of community criteria, case by case for specific types of waste (is provided) through one or more decrees of the Minister for the Environment and the protection of the Territory and the sea, in accordance with article 17, paragraph 3, of the Law 23 August 1988, no 400".

In the transitional period, pending the abovementioned measures, paragraph 3 of art. 184-ter of Legislative Decree No. 152/06, the legislator has ordered that the criteria defined by the Ministerial Decree of 5 February 1998, Ministerial decree of 12 June 2002 N. 161 and D.M. 17 November 2005 N. 269 and art. 9-bis, lit. a) and b) of the Decree-Law of 6 November 2008, no 172, converted, with modifications, by the law of 30 December 2008, N. 210".

This means that in the absence of the measures taken under the new regime, the provisions on the recovery of pre-existing waste to D. Lgs. N. 152/06 will continue to apply also with regard to the production of EoW, the term which it has replaced, in the Italian order, the best known of "Mps", or **secondary raw materials, already present even before the directive was issued**.

The Ministry of the Environment and the protection of the Territory and the Sea, with the note prot. 10045 on 1st July 2016 of the Directorate-General for Waste and Pollution, has provided some **clarifications concerning the application modalities of art. 184-ter**, specifying that: "Finally, **three ways of defining EoW** criteria are identified, hierarchically ordered.

The criteria laid down in **European regulations** prevail, within their respective scope, on the criteria defined by **Ministerial Decrees**, where they have the same types of waste. The criteria defined by Ministerial Decrees prevail, except for a specific transitional regime laid down by the respective Ministerial Decree, on the criteria which the **Regions - or the bodies of these delegates** - define in the ordinary authorisation phase of Waste recovery facilities, provided that the respective ministerial decrees are subject to the same types of waste.

Moreover, in the same note, MATTM pointed out that authorisations for the recovery of waste under ordinary conditions may lay down criteria for the "**cessation of waste status**"

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

specific to the single plant (**End of waste case by case**), with the only limit of **compliance with any applicable European or national regulations of general scope**.

This applies both to the "unique" authorisations issued under art. 208, D. LGs. 152/2006 (so-called "Environment Code"), both for authorisations for the recovery of replaced waste-that is, in fact, "absorbed"-by the Integrated Environmental Authorisation (AIA).

In the following section, an example of the bureaucracy confusion and complexity in the Italian legal system in the field of waste management is reported, by highlighting the **difficulties for stakeholders to deal with issues related to EoW materials**.

8.1.5.1 "Veneto" case study – Problems in regional application of EoW

The Veneto Region case study is the perfect example of the difficulties of National and European legislation to be applied at local level.

Is important to underline the hierarchy of modalities to define the EoW criteria, in case of conflict on the same waste categories:

- The **European Regulation** prevails over;
- The Criteria defined by the **Ministry**, that prevail over;
- The **Regional Legislation** (or the delegates entities) in the phase of ordinary authorisation of waste recovery plants.

This "**responsibility hierarchy**" is crucial for stakeholders involved in the EoW themes to manage the manage relations with the legislative organs, to understand who the referent for these issues is.

On 7th February 2018, the Resolution of the Veneto Regional Executive n° 120 (Deliberazione della Giunta Regionale), defines the **Criteria for the cessation of waste definition** "case by case" basis, in accordance with the article 184-ter, comma 2, of the Legislative Decree n° 152/2006.

These measures provide specific indications of technical and operative character to the Provincial Administration of the Metropolitan City of Venezia, which release **authorisation to waste recovery facilities** according to the article 208 of the Legislative Decree n°152/2006.

The goal is to guarantee a uniform application of the EoW Criteria from the competent administrations (provincial administration and metropolitan City of Venezia according with the Regional Law n° 3/2000 which can release authorisation to waste recovery plants) to **guarantee the right and impartial evolution of the public decisions**, by providing a summary picture of the legislation in force.

The Resolution n° 120 of the Veneto Regional Executive highlights how the Ministry acknowledges the authority on the Regions to adopt EoW criteria, but it does not provide indications for the right elaboration of them.

Some doubts remain about the real applicability of the EoW Criteria adopted (most of the time by delegates entities) in the non-regional territories, and if they **legitimise the free carriage of the EoW material through the regions**.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

In the annex A of the Resolution n°120, the main points of IPTS Technical Report on EoW Criteria are reported. It is specified that all the instances with the aim to produce **EoW Criteria will be evaluated "case by case", with an evaluation of the specific case.**

The resolution states that waste used in the treatment process for cessation of the waste status **must be non-hazardous and comply with regulation 850/2004** on persistent organic pollutants and that the procedure for issuing EoW criteria should analyse the **5 types of impacts (environmental and health; economic; on the market; normative; socio/economic)** provided by the JRC guide EUR 23990 EN – 2009.

In addition, the "Documentation requirements" that the proponent is obliged to provide for verifying compliance with the conditions laid down fixed by the art. 184-ter of D. LGs. No 152/06 and S.M.I.

The effectiveness of the **DGRV 120/2018 was "suspended"** by the **judgment of the Council of State No 1129/2018 of 28th February 2018** by which the "judges of the IV chamber" ruled that **it is for the State and not the Regions to identify**, on the basis of analysis Case by case and in addition to what is already foreseen in the Community directives, **the additional types of material that are no longer regarded as waste but as "secondary raw material"**.

The measure came at the end of a party proceeding in 2016, with an action presented by the **Consorzio Contarina** (more deeply analysed in the chapter 8.1.7.1) against the Veneto region, which in August of that year had denied the authorisation to recycle to the **experimental recovery plant Material from absorbent products in the province of Treviso.**

In other words, the regions will no longer be able to establish with ordinary authorisation when recycling can be said to have been completed, since **the power to determine the cessation of the qualification of waste (EoW) competes at first to Europe and in second to the State, but Not even to the regions** or delegated bodies like the provinces. The state uses the decrees of the environment Ministry as a legislative instrument.

The ruling denies that this power may be subordinate to the regions, by **constitutional contrast with article 117 of the Constitution** (State exclusive legislative authority in the field of the environment) **in contrast to what is foreseen by the MATTM note of 2016.**

8.1.6 Interactions between the actors and legislation in the plastic packaging waste management

The title II of the articles from the n° 217 to the n° 226 of the Legislative Decree 152/2006, for the packaging management, lays down the general principle **"the polluter pays"** and of **"shared responsibility"** for which:

- **the producers** and the **users** are responsible for the right environmental management of the packaging waste.
- **The Public Administration** should organise an efficient and economic proper system of separate collection, covering the whole national territory.
- **The citizen** should collect the waste in respect of the rules specified by the public administration.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.1.6.1 Obligations on enterprises (D.lgs 152/06, art. 221)

The term “enterprises” is meant to include the **producers** (raw material suppliers, manufacturers, importers of empty packaging and of packaging material) and the **users** (traders and distributors, packaging users and importers of filled packaging).

The enterprises should:

- achieve the **objectives of recycling and collection**;
- **pay** a “environmental contribution”
- provide independently to the **collection of their packaging waste** (art. 223);
- or **join a consortium** of CONAi system (COREPLA for plastic);

It is important to remember that the **CONAi consortium consists in equal measure of producers and users**.

8.1.6.2 The obligation on the CONAi (D.lgs 152/06, art. 225)

The CONAi should every year to present the “**General Prevention Program**”, which will contain the results based on the “Specific Prevention Plan” of each material consortium, which will focus on the following topics:

- **Prevention**;
- Recycling and collection **targets**;
- **Communication**;
- **Management**, economic and **financial situation**.

A great tool for CONAi System, to improve waste prevention, is the annual “**Prevention Dossier**”. The Dossier collects the best practice and the different experiences of prevention of the enterprises and it is also an analysis tool at national and European level.

8.1.6.3 The CONAi Environmental Contribution

The CONAi Environmental Contribution established for each type of packaging material, represents the form of financing through which CONAi distributes the cost for higher charges for separate waste collection, recycling and recovery of packaging waste among manufacturers and users. These costs, based on the provisions set forth in Legislative Decree 152/06, are distributed “**in proportion to the total quantity, weight and the type of packaging material issued on the national market**”.

Environmental Contribution amount per Plastic **from 1st January 2018**

- Level A: 179,00 €/t
- Level B: 208,00 €/t
- Level C: 228,00 €/t

Consortium Regulations state that the sums owed by all Consortium Members, Producers and Users are always collected based on the specific invoiced amount due according to the weight and type of packaging material covered by the first supply. The first supply shall mean the transfer, including temporarily or under any capacity, within Italy of:

- the finished packaging from the “**final producer**” to the “**first user**”;

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- the packaging material from a “**raw material (or semi-finished product) producer**” to a serving or proclaimed “**self-producer**”.

Moreover, the same Regulations state that any **packaging materials and packaging imported from abroad** shall be subject to the Environmental Contribution given that their use will produce waste in Italy. Otherwise **exported packaging materials are exempted from the Environmental Contribution**.

8.1.6.4 Management of primary packaging waste (Urban Waste)

The **municipality is always responsible for the collection of the primary waste** from packaging, by deciding the collection modality and communicating them to the citizens.

The management of the primary packaging from urban waste is carried out in accordance with the **agreements between ANCI (National Association of Italian Municipalities) and the CONAI**.

8.1.6.5 Management of the secondary and tertiary waste

The management of the secondary and tertiary waste from packaging is a **combination of different platforms**:

- The public **waste collection service**.
- The **Independent Systems**: the plastic packaging waste are **collected by private entities**, from big enterprises (for example supermarket). The data about the quantities and the typologies of the packaging waste shall be communicated to the CONAI.
- **CONAI system**: a network of platforms throughout the national territory capable of receiving packaging waste free of charge coming from industrial, commercial, artisanal and service that will **pay only the carriage costs**.

The CONAI system will ensure the recycling and sorting phases.

The CONAI **trademark makes it easier to recognise** the packaging manufacturing or user companies that are part of the system and actively involved in the management of packaging and packaging waste, but **CONAI does not have a contract for use of the trademark “Green Dot”** in the territory of Italy with DSD or PRO EUROPE.

8.1.6.6 Conclusion

It is possible to summarize the most important issues through some **key concepts**, which should guide the planning of the Italian legislative framework in the coming years towards the **development and consolidation of a circular economy for PPW**.

Waste management conforms to the principles of accountability and cooperation of all stakeholders involved in the **production, distribution, use and consumption** of goods from which the waste originates. The **concept of shared responsibility expressed by the legislation** provides that all-companies, public administration and consumers contribute to achieving the general objectives of the decree:

Reuse - From design process of packaging conception in order to perform, during its life cycle, a **minimum number of displacements or rotations and for an identical use**.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Saving of raw material - Containment of the consumption of raw materials used in the realization of the packaging and consequent **reduction of the weight**, with the **same product packaged and of performances**.

Use of recycled materials - Recovered material replacement of a part or all virgin raw material with **recycled/recovered material** (pre-consumption and/or post-consumption) to contribute to a reduction in the use of resources.

Facilitation of recycling activities - **Simplifying the recovery and recycling phases** of the packaging, such as the **separability of the different components** (e.g. labels, closures and regulators, etc.).

Optimization of logistics - Improvement of storage operations, optimization of loads on pallets and transport. **Optimisation of usage of primary, secondary and tertiary packaging**.

Simplification of the packaging - **System integration of multiple functions** into a single component of the packaging, eliminating an element and simplifying the system.

Optimization of production processes - Implementation of innovative packaging processes able to **reduce energy consume per unit produced** or to reduce production waste or, in general, the use of productive inputs.

The legislative framework, with clear procedures, incentives, taxes, and all the regulatory available instruments, can help to obtain these objectives and to guide the stakeholders towards a Circular Economy perspective.

8.1.7 Policy experiences from case studies

As a preliminary step towards a survey to be implemented at EU level, a first set of interviews were developed as case studies aimed to gather information from the direct experience of the actors who are involved in first-hand in the phases analysed above. In this way, **desk-based knowledge verified and enriched through actual experiences faced with respect to Packaging Plastics Waste legislation framework**.

8.1.7.1 First interview – Fater Group

The first interview (Annex 5 – Interview to Fater Group) was performed on November 22th 2017 with Guido Poliseno, Business Development Manager of Fater Group.

Fater Group was contacted with the specific perspective of understanding their experience in the field of the EoW Criteria for plastic.

Fater is the manufacturer and marketer of leading absorbent hygiene product (AHP) brands – such as Pampers nappies, Lines sanitary towels and pantyliners, Tampax tampons, Linidor, Dignity and Lines Specialist adult incontinence products, etc. – in Italy.

In 2013 Fater acquired the ACE brand, thus adding leading bleach and home cleaning products to its product line-up.

Today, Fater is an international company, which markets ACE and Neoblanc brands in Western Europe, Eastern Europe and CEEMEA, and personal hygiene absorbent products in Italy.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Fater has chosen sustainable innovation and circular economy as a total commitment challenge, which involves the entire organization and becomes the core of the business model in order to create new competitive advantages and keep growing responsibly. Fater has a strong track record in this domain, which – amongst others – led specialist environmental magazines (Italian and International) to recently dedicate to Fater a Sustainability Case Study analysis. Fater has a strong expertise as coordinator in co-funded project (5 project as coordinator so far). In addition to CIRC-PACK, two of them are:

1. RECALL (REcycling of Complex AHP waste through a first time application of patented treatment process and demonstration of sustainable business model) project co-funded by EASME. The project, completed in 2015, offers economic and environmental friendly solution to the AHP consumers, municipalities, SME operators in the field of waste and recycling, AHP producers and last but not least to the all citizens;
2. Embraced (Establishing a Multi-purpose Biorefinery for the Recycling of the organic content of AHP waste in a Circular Economy Domain) project co-funded by BBI named. This project, started in 2017, will demonstrate a sustainable model of integrated biorefinery based on the valorisation of the AHP towards the production of biobased building blocks, polymers, and fertilizers.]

Fater developed a technologic process capable to recycle used absorbent products (baby diapers, famine pads and products for incontinence), with the aim to obtain secondary raw materials.

8.1.7.2 Recap of FATER opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

- The process of writing EoW Criteria for the whole plastic waste streams is found to be too complex.
- FATER confirms the team's understanding of the tendency, at EC level, not addressed to find a "definitive" EoW Criteria for plastics (regulation), but instead to provide guidelines for MS in the management of the "no longer waste" materials.
- Other than EoW Criteria, the European Commission is promoting bilateral agreements between MS.
- The drafting of specific EoW Criteria between two or more MS can be used as precedent to write other agreements, also with not-European countries.
- The drafting of EoW Criteria by private entities is possible but with the support of the public entities, who have the duty to assist and legitimise them.

8.1.7.3 Second interview – FCA (Fiat Chrysler Automobiles)

The second interview (Annex 6 - Interview to Fiat Research Centre) was performed on June 29th 2017 with CRF, the Research Centre of Fiat Chrysler Automobiles.

The Fiat Research Centre, often abbreviated as CRF, is an applied research centre of the automobile Industry, founded in 1978 as a reference pole for innovation in Fiat Group companies. It is located in Orbassano, a few kilometers from Turin, and has branches in Trento, Valenzano (BA) and Foggia. It also controls the CRP (Research Centre Plastoptica) at Amaro in the province of Udine.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The center has participated in 542 European projects and registered more than 2800 patents, including those of the Unijet and MultiJet direct injection systems for diesel engines, which in 2002 were worth the Economist Innovation Award. The employees are 865, with a predominance of graduates in technical-scientific disciplines (data updated to October 2009). Together with the Polytechnic, the university, the Telecom Italia Lab and the National Institute of Metrology Research, it represents one of the most important research centres of the Turin area.

8.1.7.4 Recap of CFR opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

- The regional/national and European stakeholders have to define future strategies, and work more with institutions to solve criticisms related to the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislations
- Technical obstacles related to performances, quality, reliability and proper separation methods.
- Obstacles in public authorization to define EoW criteria for plastic waste and ASR.

8.1.7.5 Third interview – NOVAMONT

The third interview (Annex 7 - Interview to Novamont) was performed on Monday 16th July 2018 with Novamont S.p.A.

NOVAMONT is an Italian industrial company worldwide leader in the sector of bioplastics and involved in the development of biochemicals obtained through the integration of chemistry, environment and agriculture.

NOVAMONT promotes a bioeconomy model based not only on the efficient and sustainable use of renewable resources but also as a factor for regeneration of local areas. Research is the driving force of its industrial development and constantly improve the performance and environmental profile of its products.

NOVAMONT products are the result of innovative proprietary technologies and provide environmentally sustainable solutions to minimise the risks of these products being dispersed in the ecosystem.

8.1.7.6 Recap of NOVAMONT opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

Novamont produces biodegradable and compostable bioplastics, which are designed with the goal to be a solution for specific environmental problems associated with the end-of-life of a few traditional plastics applications. For this reason, Novamont interest in End-of-Waste Criteria for plastic is oriented to understand those specific targeted applications that could be replaced with compostable bioplastics to improve the quality of recycling (e.g.: plastic applications in which the packaging is prone to be mixed with organic content after use). The importance of communicating the difference between plastics and compostable bioplastics is crucial since the latter are designed to be collected in the organic waste stream. Therefore, the contamination of organic waste with traditional plastics would result in a decrease in the quality of compost.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

All grades of Novamont “MATER-BI,” our innovative family of biodegradable and compostable bioplastics are certified by certification bodies in accordance with the main European and international standards (EN 13432, eLabel! Certification, “OK Biodegradable Soil” standard issued by TUV AUSTRIA). Moreover, MATER-BI is the first Italian technology to have been verified with the European “Environmental Technology Verification” (ETV) programme, developed by Certiquality, which certified MATER-BI’s behaviour in biodegradation in the marine environment.

As Novamont does not produce traditional plastics it is not involved in the treatment processes of plastics waste stream, but its bioplastics are designed to be treated in the organic waste streams to obtain high quality compost and biogas. The plant dedicated to the recycling of organic waste is a qualified and efficient supply chain in the management of biodegradable and compostable plastic packaging (as reported by the Italian Composting and Biogas Association - CIC). The most serious problem is actually represented by the accidental flow of conventional plastics in the organic waste stream: their almost complete removal, which is necessary to ensure compliance with the quality standards of compost, requires refining interventions, that are highly demanding from both the effort invested and the costs related to the disposal of the huge quantities of waste produced.

At the European level, despite the positive legislative framework (Bioeconomy Strategy, Carrier Bag Directive, Waste Package, Plastic Strategy), the European Commission reconsiders the contribution of biodegradable & compostable plastics. Within the proposal for Directive, “on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment,” the European Commission has come up with measures banning or restricting the use of single-use plastic application (such as plates, cutlery, cups, plastic bags, etc.) including biodegradable & compostable plastics. Six years after the adoption of the Directive, the European Commission proposes to eventually set up standard on marine biodegradation to exclude biodegradable & compostable plastics from the scope of the directive. But biodegradable & compostable plastics are designed to be organically recycled and banning products such as plates, cutlery, or cups, which are used efficiently especially in collective catering, would only block further research & development in this sector.

From a legislative perspective a lot of effort must be put to make a strong qualitative leap. The existence of a clear and stable policy framework is crucial to promote investments. This framework should include: the creation of clear quality standards and demand support measures, as well as incentives for research, innovation, and training. Legislative actions aimed at fostering the emergence and limiting the costs of environmental externalities should be designed, as well as for the promotion of the economy circularity through the application of specific fiscal measures and the simplification of the rules governing waste recover. Other important points are the promotion of law enforcement of already existing legislation, the concrete adoption of green public procurement, the creation of flagship project for specific supply chain case studies and the diffusion of private-public partnerships. Finally, it is essential to raise citizens awareness on the topic of sustainability, through specific education schemes aimed at conveying the importance and the necessity of virtuous practices, and through public campaigns, that should also involve credible and influential players of civil society.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.		Versio 1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.2 National Legislation – Spain

For a better understanding of the Spanish regulation in packaging and packaging waste management, an analysis of the social and economic context in which it will be applied was carried out.

The packaging industry represents around 2% of the Gross Domestic Product of each country, placing the sector in fourth or fifth place in the classification of industrial sectors, in industrialized countries. In the case of Spain, the share in GDP is 1.9%.

In other sense, in 2015 the amount of municipal waste collected in Spain was 21.2 million of tons, according to the Ministry of Environment, and 7.15 million of tons of these were packaging waste.

The composition of urban solid waste in Spain is:

Figure 25 Urban solid waste composition

In separate collection, the different waste streams are deposited according to their type and nature to allow a specific treatment. Thus, the separate collection can be done through: differentiated containers, collection points, door-to-door collection, etc.

Collection method	Material		tons/ year	%
Mixed waste	Municipal waste	mixed	17,106,176	84%
Waste selectively collected	Paper and cardboard	and	1,008,959	16%
	Glass		9,129	

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

	kitchens and restaurants biodegradable	560,619	
	Parks and gardens biodegradable	229,300	
	Mixed packaging	592,353	
	Glass packaging	746,479	
Total		20,253,015	100%

Table 3 Amount of municipal waste collected in Spain 2015

The generation and composition of packaging waste in 2015 is summarized in the following table:

Material	Packaging waste generated (tons)	%
Glass	1,425,669	19.9%
Plastic	1,474,731	20.6%
Paper and cardboard	3,550,000	49.6%
Metals	393,620	5.5%
Wood	298,047	4.2%
Others	11,947	0.2%
Total	7,154,014	100.0%

Table 4 Amount and composition of packaging waste collected in Spain 2015

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.2.1 National overview

The transposition of Directive 2008/98 / EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, 9th November, about waste is carried out through Law 22/2011, 28th July, of waste and contaminated soil that replaces the previously existing Law 10/1998, 21th April, of Waste.

The necessary modification of the Spanish legislative framework about waste to adapt to changes in community law, is also an opportunity to update and improve the regime envisaged in the previously existing Law 10/1998, 21th April.

In addition, Law 10/1998, guides the waste policy according to the hierarchy principle in its production and management, maximizing the use of resources and minimizing the impacts of production and waste management. This law promotes the implementation of prevention measures, the reuse and recycling of waste, aims to increase transparency and environmental and economic efficiency of waste management activities. Finally, it promotes innovation in the prevention and management of waste, to ease the development of solutions with greater value for society. This one, was repealed by the inforce Law 22/2011, 28th July, on waste and contaminated soils, which transpose the Directive 2008/98/EC.

Law 22/2011, keeps "prevention" in the highest position of the waste hierarchy, however, eliminates "waste reduction" to be replaced by "preparation for reuse". "Recycling" and "other types of valorisations, including energy recovery" are also maintained in third and fourth places, respectively, and "elimination of waste" is added as lower step in the hierarchy.

Regarding packaging, Law 11/1997, 24th April, about Packaging and Packaging Waste incorporates the substantive rules of Directive 94/62 / EC, of the European Parliament and of the Council, 20th December, concerning Packaging and Packaging Waste.

Packaging is defined by this law as any manufactured product with materials of any nature and used to contain, protect, handle, distribute and present goods, from raw materials to finished goods, at any stage of the manufacturing, distribution, and consumption chain. All disposable articles used for this purpose are also considered packaging. This concept includes only primary or retail packaging, collective or secondary packaging and transport or tertiary packaging.

Items designed and intended to be filled at the sale point and disposable items sold fulfilled by a product or designed and intended to be filled at the sale point shall be considered packaging if they fulfil the function of packaging. The elements of the container and auxiliary elements integrated in it will be considered part of the packaging; the auxiliary elements directly hung from the product or tied to it and that perform the function of container will be considered packaging, unless they are an integral part of the product and all its elements are destined to be consumed or disposed of jointly.

The Law is structured in seven chapters, dedicated the first three, respectively, to the provisions of general application, to set certain principles of action of public administrations to promote the prevention and reuse of packaging and to establish the objectives of recycling and recovery foreseen in the mentioned Directive, while establishing intermediate recycling targets that must be met within a period of thirty-six months.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Directive (EU) 2015/720 of the European Parliament and of the Council, 29th April 2015, amending Directive 94/62 / EC as regards reducing the consumption of light plastic bags, establishes that the Member States have to adopt measures in order to reduce in a sustained way, in their territory, the consumption of light plastic bags, that is, plastic bags with a thickness of less than 50 microns.

The Royal Decree 293/2018, 18th May, about reducing the consumption of plastic bags and creating the Register of Producers, incorporated the EU Directive 2015/720 into the Spanish legislative framework

Related to materials intended to be into contact with food, since 2008, in Spain the use of recycled plastic in contact with food is regulated by the Commission Regulation (EC) 282/2008. This Regulation has been modified several times in Regulations 846/2011, 517/2013 and 1025/2015. Of course, both EC rules 1935/2004 on food contact materials and 2023/2006 on good manufacturing practice must be accomplished too.

Thus, recycled plastic can be used in food contact in the following cases:

1. Plastic waste from production of food contact materials. These pre-consumption plastics can be treated as raw materials and follow the basic regulation.
2. Recycled plastic used in an inner layer behind a functional barrier, which is defined in the Directive 2002/72/EC, 6th August, related to plastic materials and articles intended to foodstuffs contact.
3. EFSA approves the recycling process for food contact.

In this latter case, to approve the recycling process for food contact, plastic waste must come from other food contact materials, should be analysed according to regulated tests and have to come from a close loop or go through a cleaning process checked by the Challenge test, which is described by EFSA.

Finally, it should be noted another current legislation:

Order AAA / 1783/2013, 1st October, by which the annex 1 of the Regulation is changed for the development and execution of the Law 11/1997, 24th April, of Packaging and Packaging Waste, approved by Royal Decree 782/1998, 30th April.

Law 9/2006, 28th April, on evaluation of the effects of certain plans and programs in the environment.

Royal decree 252/2006, which reviews the recycling and recovery objectives established in Law 11/1997 and its development regulations, and its correction of errors.

Order MAM / 304/2002 on the recovery and disposal of waste and the European waste list and its correction of errors.

ROYAL DECREE 782/1998, 30th April, for the approval of the Regulation for the development and execution of Law 11/1997, 24th April, of Containers and container residues.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.2.2 Legislation history

Article 148.1.^a of the 1978 Spanish Constitution establishes that the Autonomous Communities have the powers of "environmental management" and, in accordance with article 149.1.23^a, the State has exclusive competence to dictate the "basic legislation on protection of the environment and the Autonomous Communities has the power to establish additional protection standards", as well as basic legislation on forests, forestry and livestock trails.

The State only has the competence to approve the basic legislation, in other words, the minimums that must be respected in any case. The Autonomous Communities can develop and implement plans to reach the targets fixed by the State law.

The actions in terms of packaging and packaging waste will be exercised by the Ministry of Environment and within it, by the General Directorate of Quality and Environmental Assessment of the General Secretariat of the Environment.

All the Autonomous Communities have the same environmental competences that consist, on the one hand, in the legislative development and execution of the basic state legislation and, on the other, in the faculty of issuing additional protection norms.

Prior to Law 11/1997, 24th April, the regulation was poor on packaging and packaging waste. The repealed Law 42/ 1975, on waste and urban solid waste partially deal with that issue. This law was repealed by Law 10/1998, 21st April, which was repealed by the inforce Law 22/2011.

The Directive 85/339/EEC, 27th June, concerning for the liquid foods containers was transpose by Royal Decree 319/1991, 8th March, that stablish actions on production, marketing, employment, recycling and filling of containers intended to contain liquids. Similarly, the Royal Decree was repealed by the Law 11/1997.

8.2.3 National Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages

Since 1997, the Packaging and Packaging Waste Law force all companies that put household packaging on the market to take charge of its recycling once they become waste. This law also allows to economic agents (packers and merchants) to participate in an integrated waste management system for used packaging from commercialize products. The system has to guarantee the periodic house collection or its proximities.

To this legislation fulfilment, economic agents (more than 12,400 companies) constituted Ecoembes, the non- profit organization that develop the packaging and packaging waste collection, treatment and recovery in Spain.

Ecoembes deals with all those who are involved in the recycling process: companies, administrations and citizens. On the one hand, companies that place packed products in the market, and on the other hand, citizens that buy these products and, after consuming them, place the packaging waste in the container. In addition, municipalities are also

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

responsible for their separate collection and, finally, recyclers are responsible for processing the waste and convert it into new raw material.

Adhered companies to de system, make an annual packaging declaration where they reflect the quantity and the type of material of the packaging that they place on the market and, depending on these variables, they pay an amount in concept of Green Dot of plus 3,800 million euros for separate collection. These contributions are used to pay the extra cost of light household packaging separate collection to public administrations (town halls, associations, deputies, etc) which are the ones with competencies in waste management in Spain.

In addition, Ecoembes works in collaboration with companies in the reduction of the environmental impact of the packaging that they place on the market. Business Plans for Prevention are implemented by the companies to undertake actions intended to achieve a weight reduction in packaging, to reuse them, the incorporation of recycled material, etc.

The administration in cooperation with Ecoembes performs the awareness and commitment of citizens. In 2017, in Spain, more than 360 communication and awareness campaigns were developed. Overall, more than 590,000 yellow and blue containers are distributed in Spain.

On one hand, paper and cardboard packaging are sent directly to collectors and recyclers. Once there, the packaging is classified based on its qualities and is then recycled into new paper and cardboard products.

On the other hand, the yellow container has three very different types of packaging: plastic packaging, metal packaging and tetrabrick, so before being sent to the respective recyclers, these must be separated in packaging sorting plants. There are 95 sorting plants throughout Spain where light packaging is separated into at least seven streams: tetrabrick, steel, aluminium, polyethylene terephthalate (PET), high density polyethylene (HDPE), film and mixed plastic. Each category is sent to its associated recycler, which will transform it into new raw material.

In 2017, 77.1% of the household packaging waste was already recycled, that means, 1.8 million tons. These results have exceeded the established objectives by the 1997 Law and by the European Directive 2004/12 / CE. Thus, Spain has confirmed its ability to respond with solvency to the demands of the European Union in recycling and place Spain among the leading countries of the European Union.

Ecoembes is part of EXPRA (Extended Producer Responsible Alliance), an organization that promotes and protects together the Extended Responsibility model of the Producer (ERP).

Related to recycling of plastic, "Asociación Nacional de Recicladores de plástico" (ANARPLA) is the only association that encompasses the main plastic recyclers in Spain. These companies mean more than 70% of the total plastic recycling capacity of Spain.

ANARPLA works since 1994 to advice companies and public administration, develops its own technical and commercial studies about plastic recycling, and organizes sectorial conferences and working groups.

ANARPLA is also associated to European Plastics Recyclers (EuPR).

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Another important waste sector association is ANAIP, the Spanish association of companies which work in plastic transformation. It was created in 1957 and it currently has more than 500 associated companies and represents more than 33.000 workers.

ANAIP is committed to the defence of plastic transformers and it is a member of some prestige organizations, such as European Plastic Converters (EuPC), AENOR, the Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE), the Spanish Building Products Manufacturers Confederation (CEPCO) and the European Plastic Pipes and Fittings Association (TEPPFA).

ANAIP has a specific division for packaging, which represents more than 40% of the total amount of ANAIP associates. ANAIP manages the secretary of the Standardization Technical Committee CTN 53/SC 4 about packaging.

8.2.3.1 Traceability and waste control

Traceability, waste control and tracking of the chain from citizen to the final recycling destination, is a very important aspect since allows to guarantee the system efficiency, correct recycling of the packaging waste and to avoid fraud.

The traceability process of packaging waste is a systematic process developed by external control companies, according to Ecoembes procedures, duly audited under ISO 9001 and 14001. The approved waste collectors/ Recyclers that have signed contracts with Ecoembes must have available, for the traceability control companies, the information related to the amount of processed materials, destination, stocks and any other necessary information to prepare the material balance or traceability chain.

Once the controls have been carried out and the necessary information has been requested, the traceability control company issues the corresponding report to both Ecoembes and the waste collector / Recycler. It shows the conclusions obtained after studying the documentation.

Depending on the material, the following are considered final destinations for recycling:

1. Steel and Aluminium: entrance to foundry.
2. Cardboard and cardboard paper drinks / food: entrance to paper mill.
3. PET: entry to recycling facility that produces clean scale and justification of product sale in this degree of completion or higher.
4. HDPE: entry to a recycling facility that produces pellets and justification for the sale of the product in this degree of completion or higher.
5. Film: entrance to a recycling facility that produces pellets and justification for the sale of products in this degree of completion or higher.
6. Plastic Mixing: entry to installation

8.2.4 Conclusions

The packaging fulfils essential functions for the conservation, products traceability, and food safety. Consumers do not "buy packaging", but packaged products. It is very important to

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

approach in this matter from a concept of life cycle. The important thing is that the package that constitutes the packaged product has the least environmental impacts throughout its life cycle, and not only the aspects related to packaging are considered. Likewise, the analysis of the results of the prevention and recycling of packaging waste should not be considered as an activity isolated from its environment. It would be very difficult for the environmental results in the packaging to be very different from the general environmental results in society.

Similarly, the waste management is completely assimilated by the society in which it is inserted. Environmental excellence must be correctly implemented with the different public services management in society and must be harmonized and proportional to them.

Prior to the environmental analysis, it will be necessary to identify the starting data in relation to the requirements that the company poses at each moment. Spanish society has evolved in several ways in recent years. On the one hand, the ratio of inhabitants per household decreases constantly and there is an increase in dwellings with one or two inhabitants. At the same time, the presence of women in the workplace is continuously increasing. All these issues, in addition to others, determine the consumption habits of Spaniards. But this analysis has become very complicated in recent years. The economic crisis and the corresponding impact on consumption, has broken all trends and has even managed to change the habits of citizens. In short, one of the current challenges in the field of sustainability is how to make environmental excellence compatible with a scenario of recovery from the economic crisis.

This innovative approach with the criteria of proportionality and eco-efficiency are the basis of the "road map" to achieve it. One of the pillars of this new approach is the "continuous improvement" criterion. This is the commitment to which all the sectors involved in the sustainable packaging waste management are necessarily involved. Aspects such as innovation, minimum costs for the best results, the use of the best available technologies and the optimization of the different management methods must necessarily be taken by hand.

8.2.5 Policy experiences from case studies

8.2.5.1 First interview - TECNOPACKAGING

The interview (Annex 8 - Interview to Tecnopackaging) was conducted on July 16th with Cristina Muñoz, Technical R&D from Tecnopackaging. Tecnopackaging is a Spanish SME that conducts R&D&i on advanced polymeric materials and their transformation processes for packaging and industrial plastic applications. its role in CIRC-PACK project is a - plastic packaging manufacturer, involved in the design and production of new packaging formats that improve the circular economy as well as satisfy commercialisation requirements. Specifically, they will produce different packaging solutions using the adequate processing techniques; namely extrusion blow moulding, injection moulding, thermoforming and blown film extrusion. With this role in mind, we contacted Tecnopackaging to better understand their experience in the field of EoW criteria for plastic.

8.2.5.2 Recap of TECNOPACKAGING opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Since the market for plastics secondary raw materials is growing, standardisation is needed for the traceability of recycled material.
- Some EU initiatives e.g. EUCERTPLAST project have developed a European wide certification scheme for post-consumer plastics recycling.
- Since recycled plastics may not have the same quality and performance compared to virgin plastics, this can be a technical barrier becoming a challenge for future technological developments e.g. monitoring systems.

8.2.5.3 Second interview - GRUPO SADA P.A.

The interview (Annex 9 - Interview to Grupo Sada P.A.) was conducted on July 18th with Manuel Ángel Gómez Gallego, Production Director from Grupo SADA P.A. He is specialist in sustainable, active and intelligent packaging for poultry.

We contacted Grupo SADA with the perspective of understanding their experience in the field of the EoW Criteria for plastic. Grupo SADA is the division of poultry processing company Nutreco in Spain, Nutreco holding company. Nutreco is one of the largest multinational companies in the food industry. Their business focuses on the overall management of the chicken production cycle, from breeders, hatcheries, farms and processing plants bait to distribution of the final product.

8.2.5.4 Recap of GRUPO SADA P.A. opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

- Producer have to use recycled plastic materials only if there are not difference in comparison with the non-recycled materials.
- It is needed a special consideration of environmental and energy aspects in the PPW application (especially in food contact uses).

8.2.5.5 Third interview - CALAF INDUSTRIAL

The interview (Annex 10 - Interview to Calaf Industrial) was conducted on July 2nd, 2018 with Carles Mussol, Technology Developer from Calaf Industrial. He is specialist in microwave electronics and machine-vision technologies.

We contacted Calaf Industrial with the perspective of understanding their experience in the field of the EoW Criteria for plastic. CALAF is a European company having a strong focus on high-value added manufacturing. The main products of the company are equipment and machinery for a wide range of sectors such as waste treatment, water treatment, agriculture, and manufacturing industry. In this sense, Calaf provides innovative solutions for automated sorting and industrial controlling by means of machine vision and other mechanical equipment.

8.2.5.6 Recap of CALAF INDUSTRIAL opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

- EoW Criteria are required to set up machinery for boosting sorting processes
- Recovery industry in Spain follows Ecoembes recommendations to develop/validate machinery for sorting packaging

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.3 Municipal and Regional Legislation – Croatia

With less than 400 kg of household waste per year, Croatia is one of the EU Member States with lowest waste production per capita. The amount of plastic waste generated per capita in Croatia is only 12kg per year. On the other hand, Croatia is below the European standard for waste recycling; only about 20% of municipal waste is recycled. The recycling rate of four fractions of municipal waste - paper, plastic, metal and glass in 2015 was 25% (Calculation according to method 2, Commission Decision 2011/753/EU establishing rules and calculation methods for verifying compliance with the targets set in Article 11 (2) of Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Waste Framework Directive.). During 2015, a total of 215,534 tonnes of packaging was put on the market, of which mostly paper, cardboard and multi-layer packaging with mostly paper components (76,663 tonnes), then glass packaging (53,335 tonnes), plastic packaging (51,959 tonnes), wood packaging (22,563 tonnes), metal packaging (10,866 tonnes) and other materials (148 tonnes).

The quantities of collected packaging waste from 2009 to 2014 have significantly decreased (around 50%, the largest decrease is noted in paper and cardboard quantities), partly due to the decreased quantities of packaging on the market, and partly due to the more efficient control of management system for this type of waste. Over 55% of collected packaging waste in 2015 was packaging waste made from paper, cardboard, and multi-layer packaging with mostly paper components, after that 25% glass packaging, 18% plastic packaging, and the rest of collected waste was packaging waste made from metal and wood. In 2015, a total of 60% of packaging waste was recovered. All the quantities within the Environmental Protection and Energy Efficiency Fund's system were recovered via recycling, so the part of recycled quantities in 2015 is also 60%, which is within the defined goal for packaging waste recycling. In comparison to defined individual goals in recycling, the goals for glass (65%), plastic (46%) and paper (89%) were also achieved, while the recycling rate for metals was 14% from the defined 50%, and for wood only 3% from the defined 15%.

8.3.1 Regional and municipal Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages

In order to comply with the objectives of the Directive 2008/98/EZ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste, and move towards a European recycling society with a high level of resource efficiency, Croatia assumed the obligation to prepare for re-use and the recycling of waste materials such as paper, metal, plastic and glass from households and possibly from other origins as far as these waste streams are similar to waste from households, that needs to be increased to a minimum of overall 50 % by weight. Following, the Waste Management Plan of the Republic of Croatia for the period 2017-2022 has been adopted.

By 1st January 2015 Republic of Croatia must take measures via its competent authorities to ensure separate collection of the following types of waste: waste paper, waste metals, waste plastics and glass, electric and electronic waste, waste batteries and accumulators, end-of-life vehicles, end-of-life tires, waste oils, textile and footwear waste and medical waste.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The local self-government unit is obliged to fulfil separate collection of difficult wastes: waste paper, waste metals, waste glass, waste plastics, waste textiles and bulky municipal waste by ensuring:

1. the operation of at least one recycling yard or a mobile unit in its area
2. the installation of an adequate number and type of containers on public surfaces for the separate collection of difficult wastes, waste paper, metal, glass, plastic, and textile, which are not covered by the special waste management system,
3. that households are notified of the location and changes in the location of recycling yards, mobile units, or containers for separate collection of difficult wastes, waste paper, metal, glass, plastic, and textile, and
4. the transportation of bulky municipal waste on user request.

Users of the public service for the collection of mixed municipal waste and biodegradable municipal waste must submit difficult waste separately from mixed municipal waste and biodegradable municipal waste. Users bear the costs of municipal waste management in proportion to the quantity of waste submitted to the service provider.

The City of Rijeka and surrounding municipalities are the first, and for the time the only in the Croatia, which have systematically resolved waste management in accordance with legal regulations. Rijeka has adopted the Waste Management Plan of the city of Rijeka for the period 2017-2022 in February 2018. The Waste Management Plan is the key document that will bring Rijeka one step closer to reducing and preventing waste generation, which are common goals set by European Union.

Recycling rates of the municipal waste for the City of Rijeka was 21% in 2014. In the composition of municipal waste, plastics occupy 22.9 %.

There are no precise data for packaging waste.

8.3.2 Municipal and Regional overview

Legislative framework in force for Environmental issues in Croatia and therefore Rijeka:

Law on Sustainable Waste Management (OG No. 94/13, 73/17), in parallel with waste management legislation, proscribes the waste packaging as a special category of municipal waste and says the purpose of waste collecting and recycling. Law on Sustainable Waste Management refers to legislative rules in Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging⁵³ (OG 88/15, 78/16, 116/17) (hereinafter: Ordinance) and in Regulation on the management of waste packaging (OG 97/15).

⁵³ Ordinance on packaging and packaging waste (OG 97/05,115/05,81/08,31/09,156/09,38/10,10/11, 81/11,126/11,38/13, 86/13) ceased to be valid as of entry into force of the Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15, 78/16, 116/17) except for the provisions of Articles 12, 13, 14, 19a, 20, para. 3, 20a and Article 25, paragraphs 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 of the Ordinance which remain valid until the entry into force of the Regulation referred to in Article 53, paragraph 4 of the Act and conclusion of the contract on performing the service of collecting waste packaging in the system managed by the Fund, and Article 16, paragraphs 3, 8, 9, 12,

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging is most comprehensive regulation on packaging and managing of packaging waste. It stipulates what is consider packaging, waste packaging, plastic carrier bags, lightweight plastic carrier bags, very lightweight plastic carrier bags, oxo-degradable plastic carrier bags.

Main goals of the Ordinance are: to separately collect and recover at least 60% of the total weight of packaging waste arising on the Croatian territory, to recycle at least 55% and at most 80% of the total weight of waste packaging material, and to achieve a minimum recycling rate of packaging materials contained in waste packaging (60% for glass, 60% for paper and cardboard, 50% for metal, 22.5% for plastic, 15% for wood).

The Ordinance is accordant with following acts:

- European Parliament and Council Directive 94/62/EC of 20 December 1994 on packaging and packaging waste that was amended last time with Directive (EU) 2015/720 of the European Parliament and Council of 29 April 2015 amending Directive 94/62/EC about reducing the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags
- Directive 1999/45/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 1999 concerning the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the classification, packaging, and labelling of dangerous preparations

The Ordinance establishes the legal framework for the implementation of the following regulations of the European Union:

- Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2006 on shipments of waste
- Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006

The Ordinance is carried out according to the following Decisions of the European Commission (hereinafter: Commission Decision) issued in connection with the implementation of Directive 94/62 / EC:

- Commission Decision 2005/270/EC of 22 March 2005 establishing the formats relating to the database system pursuant to Directive 94/62/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on packaging and packaging waste.

13 and 14 of the Ordinance which remain valid until the establishment of the Register referred to in Article 29 of the Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15,78/16,116/17).

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Commission Decision 97/129/EC of 28 January 1997 establishing the identification system for packaging materials pursuant to European Parliament and Council Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste.
- Commission Decision 2001/524/EC of 28 June 2001 relating to the publication of references for standards EN 13428:2000, EN 13429:2000, EN 13430:2000, EN 13431:2000 and EN 13432:2000 in the Official Journal of the European Communities in connection with Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste.
- Commission Decision 2001/171/EC of 19 February 2001 establishing the conditions for a derogation for glass packaging in relation to the heavy metal concentration levels established in Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste.
- Commission Decision 2009/202/EC of 24 March 2009 establishing the conditions for a derogation for plastic crates and plastic pallets in relation to the heavy metal concentration levels established in Directive 94/62/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on packaging and packaging waste.
- Commission Decision 97/662/EC of 27 May 1997 concerning questionnaires for Member States reports on the implementation of certain Directives in the waste sector (implementation of Council Directive 91/692/EEC).

Regulation on the management of waste packaging (OG 97/15) (hereinafter: Regulation) is a regulation about packaging return and packaging deposit system.

In January 2017, **Waste Management Plan of the Republic of Croatia for the period 2017-2022** was adopted as a key document for waste disposal and waste recycling, and it states, among others, details about packaging waste, plastic packaging waste and approved ways of recycling.

Following the national Waste Management Plan, and in accordance with Act on Sustainable Waste Management, Rijeka has adapted **Waste Management Plan of the City of Rijeka for the period 2017-2022**.

As waste disposal management is in the hands of local government unit, there is no obligation for Primorsko-goranska County to adapt Waste Management Plan on regional level.

8.3.3 Legislation history

Main legislation on packaging waste:

- **Law on waste** adopted on the 9th of May 1995 – the first regulation about waste and waste management in Croatia; expired on January 1st, 2004 when the new Law on waste has entered into force (Act on waste OG 178/04, 111/06, 60/08, 87/09)
- **Regulation on the waste types**, April 10th1995; gave specifics about the categories, types, and classification of waste

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **Regulation on packaging waste management**, June 20th, 1996; first specific regulation about packaging waste; expired on August 4th, 2005
- **Regulation on waste disposal conditions**, November 11th, 1997
- **Decision on communal order**, adopted on July 10th, 2003 by the Rijeka City Council; provides communal order and measures for its implementation in the area of the City of Rijeka
- **Law on waste**, December 10th, 2004, with amendments in 2006, 2008, 2009
- **Regulation on Categories, Types and Classification with Waste Catalogue and Hazardous Waste**, April 7th, 2005
- **Waste Management Strategy of the Republic of Croatia**, adopted on October 15th, 2005, with the aim to set up a framework within which Croatia will be obliged to reduce the quantity of waste it currently generates, and to manage its waste in a sustainable manor
- **Ordinance on packaging and packaging waste**, adopted on April 4th 2005, taking the place of the Regulation on waste disposal conditions (OG 53/99): *ceased to be valid as of entry into force of the Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15, 78/16, 116/17) except for the provisions of Articles 12, 13, 14, 19a, 20, para. 3, 20a and Article 25, paragraphs 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 of the Ordinance which remain valid until the entry into force of the Regulation referred to in Article 53, paragraph 4 of the Act and conclusion of the contract on performing the service of collecting waste packaging in the system managed by the Fund, and Article 16, paragraphs 3, 8, 9, 12, 13 and 14 of the Ordinance which remain valid until the establishment of the Register referred to in Article 29 of the Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15,78/16,116/17).*
- **Regulation on the criteria, procedure, and manner of determining compensation to real estate owners and local self-government units**, May 25th, 2006
- **Waste Management Plan of the Republic of Croatia for 2007-2015**, adopted on July 19th, 2007; central document on waste management in the Republic of Croatia for the period from 2007 to 2015
- **Ordinance on the methods and conditions for the landfill of waste, categories and operational requirements for waste landfills**, November 8th, 2007; on categories of landfills, procedures and other requirements for waste disposal; cease to be valid on September 29th 2015 as of entry into force of the Ordinance on the methods and conditions for the landfill of waste, categories and operational requirements for waste landfills (OG 114/15)
- **Law on Sustainable Waste Management**, entered into force on July 23th 2013; amendments in 2017; general regulation in force about waste and waste management in Croatia; defines the goals and obligations of all system stakeholders and deadlines. By the end of 2018, Croatia needs to introduce a comprehensive waste management system, which means introducing waste sorting, landfill

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

rehabilitation and construction of 13 waste management centres in the Republic of Croatia. The goal is to provide a minimum of 50% of separately collected paper, glass, plastic, and metal by 2020. The obligation of cities and municipalities was to start classifying waste from 24 July 2014. Construction of recyclable yards, green island design and procurement of separate waste collection and other communal equipment and vehicles have been launched.

- **Ordinance on Waste management**, February 12th, 2014; ceased to be valid as of entry into force Ordinance on Waste management (OG 117/2017)
- **Declaration on Waste management**; adopted on November 27th, 2014 by Primorsko – goranska County; it states that municipal waste management in the area of Primorsko – goranska County should be carried out on ecological principles based on five principles: Redesign (product), Reduce the use, Re-use, Recycle and Biodegrade. The Declaration also states that ecologically justified waste management should respect the principles of environmental sustainability and protection of resources, taking into account the overall effects on human health, environment, and economy. It implies the rejection of all the options and methods of waste incineration within the County Waste Management Centre Marišćina and technologies that result in irreversible loss of usable raw materials and generate extra pollution health hazardous toxic compounds. Waste management system therefore needs to be based on the full application of the principles of ecological waste collection and the orientation of the re-use of secondary raw materials using suitable methods of treating and recycling. The Declaration emphasizes the duty of local governments to secure conditions for separate waste collection in their area.
- **Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging**, August 4th, 2015, amendments 2016 and 2017; main regulation about packaging, waste packaging and recycling
- **Ordinance on the waste catalogue**, August 3rd, 2015; includes comprehensive waste catalogue
- **Regulation on the management of waste packaging**, September 18th, 2015
- **Waste Management Plan of the Republic of Croatia for the period 2017-2022**; January 5th, 2017; encompasses the complete picture of waste management in Croatia and give guidelines for the 6-year period
- **Ordinance on waste management**, November 13th, 2017; lists the conditions for waste management, persons responsible for waste management, and the operation of the recycling yard
- **Waste Management Plan of the City of Rijeka for the period 2017-2022**, adopted on February 27th, 2018; the main objective of the Plan is to determine a framework for the establishment of an integrated management system, primarily of municipal waste. This document estimates the annual increase in the amount of municipal waste produced by 2022, the proposed reduction plan for annual mixed communal waste, a plan to increase annual amounts of separately collected waste such as

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

paper, plastics, metals and glass, a plan to achieve a separate collection rate for recyclable municipal waste at 60% of the mass of communal waste produced, including a plan to increase annual quantities of separately collected bio-waste, to achieve a collection rate of 40% of the produced volume, if the collection is shown to be justified, feasible and sustainable. Also, the Plan estimates the mass of biodegradable waste as well as the total mass of communal waste, which would be allowed to dispose in landfills in 2020 and the impact of mechanical and biological treatment on the quantities of decommissioned waste.

8.3.4 Key Policy Measures in Force

8.3.4.1 Definition of Packaging - Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15, 78/16, 116/17)

Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging defines, in accordance with European Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste, all packaging placed on the market and all packaging waste to be used or developed in industry, commerce, service industry, household or any other source irrespective of the material. Article 4, paragraph 1 states the following:

- a) packaging - any product, regardless of the nature of the material from which it is made, which is used to hold, protection, handling, delivery, and presentation of goods, from raw materials to finished products, from producers to consumers. Packaging includes non-returnable items used for the same purpose.

Packaging can be:

- b) single use packaging - packaging made for one use only
- c) reusable packaging - the packaging which, when empty, is reused for the same purpose and whose reuse system is provided by the manufacturer
- d) multilayer (composite) packaging - packaging made of different materials which cannot be separated manually
- e) sales packaging or primary packaging – packaging conceived so as to constitute a sales unit to the final user or consumer at the point of purchase
- f) grouped packaging or secondary packaging - packaging conceived so as to constitute at the point of purchase a grouping of a certain number of sales units whether the latter is sold as such to the final user or consumer or whether it serves only as a means to replenish the shelves at the point of sale; it can be removed from the product without affecting its characteristics;
- g) transport packaging or tertiary packaging - packaging conceived so as to facilitate handling and transport of a number of sales units or grouped packaging in order to prevent physical handling and transport damage. Transport packaging does not include road, rail, ship and air containers;

Moreover, the definition of “packaging” shall be based on the following criteria:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- h) Items shall be considered to be packaging if they fulfil the definition of the packaging without prejudice to other functions which the packaging might also perform, unless the item is an integral part of a product and it is necessary to contain, support or preserve that product throughout its lifetime and all elements are intended to be used, consumed or disposed of together.
- i) Items designed and intended to be filled at the point of sale and 'disposable' items sold, filled or designed and intended to be filled at the point of sale shall be considered to be packaging provided they fulfil a packaging function.
- j) Packaging components and ancillary elements integrated into packaging shall be considered to be part of the packaging into which they are integrated. Ancillary elements hung directly on, or attached to, a product and which perform a packaging function shall be considered to be packaging unless they are an integral part of this product and all elements are intended to be consumed or disposed of together.

The Ordinance states that the packaging material is any material from which packaging is produced, such as: glass, plastic, paper, cardboard, wood, metal, a multilayer (composite) materials are mixed, and other materials.

8.3.4.2 Definition of plastic and plastic carrier bags - Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (OG 88/15, 78/16, 116/17)

With amendments to Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging in November 2017, the Ordinance states the following definition about plastic and plastic carrier bags:

- k) Plastic is a polymer as defined in Article 3, paragraph 5 of Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and establishing a European Chemicals Agency and amending Directive 1999/45 / EC and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No. 793/93 and Commission Regulation (EC) No. 1488/94 as well as Council Directive 76/769 / EEC and Directive 91/155 / EEC, 93/67 / EEC, 93/105 / EC and 2000/21 / EC (OJ L 396, 30. 12. 2006), which may be added other additives or substances, and can be used as the main structural component of the carrier bag
- l) Plastic bags are carrier bags, with or without handles, made of plastic, which are supplied to consumers at the point of sale of goods or products
- m) Lightweight plastic bags are plastic bags with a wall thickness below 50 microns
- n) Very lightweight plastic bags are plastic carrier bags with a wall thickness of less than 15 microns which are needed for hygienic reasons or provided as a primary packaging for loose food when this helps to prevent food waste
- o) Oxo-degradable plastic bags are plastic bags made of plastic materials with include additives which catalyse the fragmentation of the plastic material into micro-fragments

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The Article 14. a of the Ordinance implements the commitment to reduce the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags (Directive 2015/720 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2015 amending Directive 94/62/EC about reducing the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bag). The said Article states the following:

- Seller must charge the consumer, at the point of sale of goods or products, all lightweight plastic carrier bags
- Seller is obliged, in places where very light plastic bags are free given, to emphasize a prominent notice to consumers about energy-saving and rational use of these bags by labelling content "USE ECO-FRIENDLY BAGS"

8.3.4.3 Main local regulation in the City of Rijeka - Waste Management Plan of the City of Rijeka for the period 2017 - 2022

According to the national Waste Management Plan, and in compliance with its provisions, each local public authority had the obligation to adapt their own Plan for waste management for a certain period.

Waste Management Plan of the City of Rijeka for the period 2017-2022 is the basic document which aims to establish a comprehensive system of sustainable waste management in the City of Rijeka that, based on the analysis of current situation and legal goals for waste management, lays down the specific measures and actions needed to improve the organization of the waste management system, financing system and system of public awareness and public participation.

Area of application of the Waste Management Plan is the City of Rijeka with its administrative boundaries. Waste Management Plan of the City of Rijeka has a key role in the establishment of a sustainable waste management system at the level of the city, all following the obligations arising from existing legislation and from national and local planning documents.

8.3.5 Regional and municipal Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages

8.3.5.1 Regional/municipal Packaging recovery system

The management of waste packaging is in the competence of the communal company **Čistoća d.o.o. Rijeka**. By packaging, we consider materials such as paper, glass, plastic, textile, and metals which must be collected separately, according to the law. Čistoća collects paper, cardboard, metal, and plastic packaging according to the provisions of the Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging (NN 88/15, 78/16, 116/17) which proscribes that companies can collect packaging and packaging waste under a contract with the Fund for environmental protection, and provide warehousing, and technical and technological conditions for collecting packaging material.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The national Plan for waste management proscribes that paper, plastic, glass, metal, and cardboard that are collected separately shall be delivered to sorting plants. After sorting, the waste shall be given for processing to a company with a corresponding license.

According to the national Plan, the **Fund for environmental protection** estimates that in the period between 2016 – 2022, the total amount of waste packaging will be between 193 and 200 thousand tonnes. According to older information (2008), 55-80% of packaging waste was recycled, depending on material. The minimal recycling rate for plastic packaging recovery that is still to be achieved is 22.5%. Although the abilities for managing plastic packaging recovery and plastic were improved, it is still not enough to reach the EU standards.

The City of Rijeka planned to establish 12 recycling yards in total, and currently there are two permanent recycling yards in the administrative borders of the city. There is also an independent mobile recycling yards which covers 19 locations in Rijeka, and changes location every 2 weeks. Besides plastic materials, these recycling yards collect various kinds of waste materials, but only those that can be recovered, and exclusively from the citizens.

More on the packaging recovery system regarding national rules is described under 8.4.4.4 section.

8.3.5.2 Regional/municipal Consortium for plastic recycling

The Association of the plastic and rubber industry is a professional interest association within the Croatian Chamber of Commerce. Although this industry is not yet recognized as a perspective and significant branch in Croatia, it has continuously shown growth. In 2016, the amount of plastic and rubber processed totalled 197.000 tonnes, which is 9% more than in 2015. The key activity of this branch is the management of its waste. Plastic products at the end of their life span represent a valuable resource. All the indicators of this branch are rising in Croatia: manufacturing, income, number of companies, employees, and export. The growth accelerator of the branch is manufacturing ready and semi-ready plastic products (pipes and connectors – 103.898 t), packaging (52.417 t), construction material (19.985 t) and other plastic products (19.158 t).

The Association advocates for an independent strategy for the industry of plastic and rubber to provide the improvement of technology and to produce added value in the activities of the Circular economy. The introduction of Circular economy in the Croatian economy concerns the entire legislature on waste management, and the emphasis is on materials that can be re-used. This implies the use of secondary resources and improving economic competitiveness, while at the same time enabling more benefits for the environment.

The plastic and rubber industry in Croatia, therefore, advocates for the total ban on dumping re-usable waste in waste depots.

There is also the Society of plastics and rubber engineers, which is a member of the Association of plastics societies that issues the publication “Polimeri.” The society is a civil organization.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.3.5.3 Regional/municipal Plastic Packaging Consortium

The Fund for environmental protection and energy efficiency is the central institution for collecting and investing non-budgetary resources into programs and projects that centre on environment protection, energy efficiency and renewable energy use.

The Fund has the role of 2nd level control for using structural instruments of the EU, about the specific goals such as, environment protection, sustainable use of resources, climate changes and energy efficiency and renewable energy use.

As companies that deal with waste management, recovery and recycling need to be licenced by the Fund, the Fund gathers 9 recovery companies or recyclers:

- 2 for polymer waste
- 2 for metal
- 2 for glass
- 1 for wood
- 1 for paper and
- 1 for cardboard

It is not a consortium in the means of joint body. The collected packaging waste by these subjects is recovered materially, which enables the re-use of the packaging resources.

Along with these companies, there are 21 Centres for packaging waste management that collect packaging waste.

One of these recovery companies collects packaging material in the Primorje – Gorski kotar County in their 2 branches near Rijeka.

All the companies included in the process of packaging recovery, along with sellers, recycling yard managers, and recyclers must follow the Direction on dealing with packaging waste in the system of returnable packaging from August 22nd, 2017, that was issued by the Fund.

There is also an independent Institute for Packaging and Graphic Arts Tectus, as part of the company Tectus with 22 company members which gather notable Croatian companies. The Institute is member of the World Packaging Organization – WPO, and the European Packaging Institutes Consortium – EPIC. The Institute issues its own publications and Journal on packaging topics.

The Croatian Chamber of Commerce gathers the Packaging Community with mostly manufacturers as members.

8.3.5.4 Packaging Waste management system

The management of waste packaging is proscribed in the national Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging, mentioned above. The Ordinance differs packaging as: single-use packaging, multiple-use packaging that is returnable, and waste packaging. The system on returnable packaging includes glass, plastic (PET), metal (Al/Fe) single-use

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

packaging for beverages (except milk and dairy), with the volume of at least 0,2 l and with the returnable marking on the packaging. The packaging materials include:

- Paper/cardboard
- Plastic
- Wood
- Metal
- Multi-layer (composite)
- Glass
- Textile

The consumers in Croatia can get reimbursement in money for returning such packaging to shops that collect multiple-use packaging or to recycling yards. The packaging must be cleaned of its content, not crushed or damaged, with a visible bar-code and return sign. The Rules proscribe the shops and recycling yards that are obliged to take customers returnable packaging and reimburse them for it.

In regard to packaging that is not included in the categories described above, physical, and legal persons using such packaging are obliged to separate the packaging after use from the mixed waste, and to discard it separately to the corresponding container according to its material, or to the recycling yards.

When it comes to hazardous waste, the shop keepers that sell products that require such packaging that can contain residue from dangerous materials (paint packaging, varnishes, thinners, cleansers etc.)

This model achieved the return of 93,6% bottles and metal cans that were released on the market in 2014.

8.3.5.5 Material and object in contact with food

The matter is regulated by: the **Law on materials and objects in direct contact with food (NN 25/13, 41/14)**, the **Law on items for general use (NN 39/13, 47/14)** and several regulations:

- a) Regulation on the content and form for the application for the activity of import, manufacturing, and distribution of materials in direct contact with food (NN 3/14, 47/2017),
- b) Regulation on the safety of materials and ceramic objects in direct contact with food (NN 62/13),
- c) Regulation on the safety of materials and objects manufactured from regenerated cellulose in direct contact with food (NN 62/13)
- d) Regulation on special conditions for manufacturing and marketing items for general use (82/10) and
- e) Regulation on the safety of materials and objects in direct contact with food (NN 125/09, 31/11, 39/13)

The Law on items for general use is a framework for implementing EC and EU regulations, for this description the relevant are:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Commission Regulation (EC) 2023/2006 on good manufacturing practice for materials and articles intended to come into contact with food,
- Commission Regulation (EC) No 1895/2005 of 18 November 2005 on the restriction of use of certain epoxy derivatives in materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
- Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC
- Commission Regulation (EC) No 450/2009 of 29 May 2009 on active and intelligent materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
- Commission Regulation (EC) No 282/2008 of 27 March 2008 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods and amending Regulation (EC) No 2023/2006
- Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food.

Materials that can come into direct contact with food are materials and objects according to the Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 and products intended for infants and children under 3 years of age for special use. The materials that are included in the category of materials that can come into contact with food are:

- Glass
- Varnish
- Metal/alloy
- Paper/cardboard
- Plastic
- Paint dye, glue
- Rubber seals
- Silicone
- Top coats
- Wood, cork, textile
- Active and intelligent packaging
- Multi-layer packaging
- Industrial equipment

The Croatian Ministry of Health, and its Management for sanitary inspection conduct monitoring of the legislature according to the *Law on sanitary inspection (NN 113/08, 88/10)*. The system of control provides monitoring of the manufacturing process and of the internal Croatian market by collecting samples. All manufactures are expected to follow the good manufacturing practices described for materials and products in Annex I. of Regulation 1935/2004 and that are determined in Regulation 2023/2006 on good manufacturing practice that can come into direct contact with food.

8.3.5.6 Waste regulation authority

According to the *Law on sustainable waste management (NN 94/13, 73/17)* the institutions and organizations involved in the process of waste management are the following:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- a) The Ministry for environment protection and energetics
- b) Local and regional public authorities
- c) Legal persons with public authority

The minister of the competent ministry is free, under Article 5. of the said Law, to establish committees for drafting regulations, which are adopted by the Croatian government. Those regulations include national plans, programs and reports as well as for the evaluation of the exception from the determined priority in waste management.

The Croatian government adopts the National plan for waste management (2017-2022), and according to this plan, and in compliance with its provisions, each local public authority adopts their own Plan for waste management for a certain period. The local public authorities must issue a report for the past year demonstrating the execution of the plan, while the Agency for environment protection drafts the joint report with all the local reports.

The competencies for drafting regulation and implementation activities are proscribed in Article 23. of the Law.

The Government of the Republic of Croatia and its relevant Ministry is responsible for the waste management system and its effectiveness.

The implementation bodies on country level are the Agency for environmental protection and the Fund for environmental protection and energy efficiency. The local and regional public authorities are responsible for ensuring the conditions and implementation of proscribed measures on waste management. More than one local or regional public authority can join together to organize the joint implementation of the measures for waste management.

This is the situation in the Primorje – Gorski kotar county. 13 cities and municipalities directly deliver their waste to the County centre for waste management Marišćina (where only 5% of waste is recycled for now), and the waste for other county locations is delivered from trans-shipment stations.

8.3.5.7 Packaging waste paperwork

In Rijeka, and the surrounding cities and municipalities that have established a joint waste management system (Kraljevica, Bakar, Viškovo, Čavle, Jelenje, Klana, Kostrena), have on their streets blue containers for sorting paper and cardboard. Citizens can therefore sort such paper and cardboard waste that have been cleaned from impurities separately from communal waste.

The municipal company Čistoća that is in charge of waste management on the territories of the above-mentioned municipalities and cities, also collects paper and cardboard waste from office buildings free of charge, especially from offices of the City of Rijeka and its companies.

8.3.5.8 Traceably and Control of Waste

The Croatian Agency for environment and nature is responsible for managing the e-ONTO system, according to Article. 45 of the Law on sustainable waste management (NN 94/13,

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

73/17), which proscribes that a person who produces waste while conducting business and the person responsible for waste management are obligated to conduct a register on the production and waste flow for every category of waste. The Agency is obligated to collect, summarize, and process environment information.

The Register on the production and waste flow is composed of the Register form (ONTO, ONTO - P) and following forms (PL - O) for every category of waste. The Register is regulated by the Regulation on waste management (NN 117/17).

E – ONTO is a network application for conducting the Register which enables maintenance and input of information by a web application as a report form for monitoring waste flow from manufacturer to end destination in a single system.

The persons required to use the e – ONTO system are according to Article 45., sub-article 4. of the Law on waste management are:

- Persons with licence for waste management
- Waste salesmen
- Person inscribed in the Register of recycling yards
- Providers of the service of collecting mixed communal waste
- Providers of the service of collecting bio-degradable communal waste

If one is not obligated to use the e-ONTO system, voluntary use is also an option.

The Agency also provides a GIS system for monitoring various environmental features, one of which is waste and waste management. One of the basic tasks of the Agency is to conduct, develop, coordinate, and manage the Information system of environment and nature (ISOP). The Information system is a series of interlinked information and sources of information on the state and pressure of parts of the environment, spatial features and other inputs and information important for monitoring the environment and nature on a national level.

The ENVI portal provides the Atlas of environment, available here: <http://envi-portal.azo.hr/atlas>. The atlas provides links to several environmental features, and the feature on waste is available here: <http://envi.azo.hr/?topic=8>.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 26 ENVI portal – section on waste with the menu seen on the left

8.3.1 Legislation ongoing

The Ministry of environmental protection issued the plan for e-Counselling for the year 2018, on March 28th. The e-Counselling will start in the 2nd quarter of 2018 and is expected to end in the 3rd quarter. The counselling will include the following legislation:

- Amendments to the Law on sustainable waste management
- Regulation on special categories of waste
- Amendments on the Regulation on terms and conditions for waste disposal, the categories and working conditions for landfills
- Regulation on the Amendments of the regulation on packaging and waste packaging.

8.3.2 Impact of the legislation on the packaging plastics waste actors

1. Import:

The Law on sustainable waste management proscribes that cross-border waste commerce through, by and from the Republic of Croatia is managed under Regulation (EC) 1013/2006 of June 14th, 2006 on shipments of waste.

The Law prohibits:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Import of hazardous waste, mixed communal waste and burn residue of waste (Article 11/1013/2006)
- Import of mixed communal waste for energy use

If there are sufficient capacities in the Republic of Croatia for material recovery of certain waste materials, the principle is to give the primacy to the recovery process, rather than the export. If an enterprise or person dealing with import/export that isn't obligated under Article 3/1013/2006, they are required to inscribe into the Registers for import or export of waste, depending on their activity. If waste must be returned to Croatia, according to Articles 22-24/1013/2006, the competent Ministry must issue an approval.

The persons who are not obligated to special requirements under Article 3/1013/2006, must report the specifics on the waste imported/exported to the Agency on environment protection and nature by March 1st every year.

2. Collection:

The actors included in this process are:

- The Ministry of environment protection and energetics
- Legal persons/institutions with public authorities
- Local/regional public authorities (communal/municipal companies/private specialized companies)
- Citizens

According to the Law on environment protection, the competent Ministry/Government, adopts the National plan for waste management for a certain period (2017-2022), and the Local public authorities are required to adopt their own Plans for waste management, which will be in accordance with the National plan. The competent minister must draft Regulations for the implementation of process phases of waste management according to the Law.

The Local public authorities must then, with the regional ones, ensure conditions for implementing the measures proscribed, to ensure the efficiency of the waste management system. Specifically, this means, in the case of Croatia, to set up green islands with containers for waste separations (on a specific number of citizens), to have 12 centres for waste separation within EU standards, and to ensure services for waste collection and separation.

By February 2018., all local public authorities were required to set up containers for sorting waste, and by 2020., Croatia is required to recycle 50% of total waste collected.

3. Sorting:

The centres for waste management, are a set of buildings and machinery for processing, recovery of disposal, and are usually have a plant for mechanical-biological waste processing, management facilities, waste water facilities, internal infrastructure, disposal yards and transport stations.

The 12 centres for waste management (2 built, 1 in operation in Primorje – Gorski kotar county), are centres with large capacities for collecting waste, and should cover the territories and needs of 20 counties and the capital Zagreb.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The Republic of Croatia has taken upon the requirements set by the EU, to sort waste separately, by minimum of 50% at citizens' doorstep by 2020.

The cities and municipalities need to adopt decisions on their waste management system, regulating sorting and collection of waste, as well as penalties for persons who don't comply with the local decisions. The decisions haven't been adopted by most of the local authorities, and it is uncertain for most citizens, how will the system for waste management look like in the future. The local authorities must adopt new price lists for the service of waste management, and the price should be more favourable for citizens who sort waste. However, these activities have been severely delayed, from constructing the capacities for waste management, managing old landfills, to creating a system for waste management, which will very likely, be different for citizens depending on their residence.

The delays in adopting legislation are certainly a barrier in the development of waste management by EU standards.

4. Selling of sorted PPW:

The system of returnable packaging that includes plastic packaging is described above, in 8.3.4.4 Section.

In May 2018., the Association for plastic and rubber participated on a Round table for strengthening capacities of the recycling market in Zagreb, on the yearly green week. The round table discussed about the possibilities of establishing a waste exchange market with the inclusion of stakeholders in the discussion and the process of choosing the model for the exchange suitable for the economy. It is important to create the minimal technical requirements that a certain category of waste must have to be suitable for recycling.

It is also necessary, be their claims, to separate waste from secondary resources with bylaws, and to reach the status of secondary resource.

The waste exchange market as a register of resources is a desirable option, but not in terms of auction or resource price rise. Considering the opinions of the Association, one can conclude that there is a lack of relevant legislation which would proscribe order in the waste management system or, in other words, there currently isn't adequate regulations in force to enhance and accelerate the circular economy of waste and recycling in Croatia.

5. Crashing:

In 2005., the first Strategy for waste management was adopted, and in 2007. the first National plan for waste management 2007-2015 was adopted with the aim, and respecting EU standards, to set a realistic period for reducing the total amount of waste produced in Croatia, and to sustainably manage the waste. In 2013, the Law on sustainable waste management was adopted, and the new National plan for waste management 2017-2022.

It is considered that the legislation provides a good basis for the development and improvement of the system. However, the models chosen, begun in development and not yet operational, are not necessarily a good solution in today's standards.

The model for constructing a dozen centres for waste management to cover 20 counties in 2007, may have been ideal, but it is now starting to raise questions. The issues are: only 1 centre is operational so far, and it is foreseen that such centres will increase the cost of the

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

service of waste transportation to the centres significantly. The profession now discusses it, whether it was a better option to produce microcenters for waste management.

6. *The preparatory operation for reuse:*

The Fund for environmental protection and energy efficiency has issued Guidelines for reuse developed by the “Ente di Studio per la Pianificazione Ecosostenibile dei Rifiuti” in 2016. The Chapter 11. Is devoted to the activities for system establishment – to the construction of the centres for reuse and to the activities for establishing a system of collection and distribution. However, these guidelines were focused on reuse of usable finished objects.

Reuse is described in the Plan for waste management 2017-2022 which describes the goals and measures for the prevention of waste production. Reuse of products complies with the measures of preventing waste so the measures for waste management do not cover reuse not is reuse separately described for plastic packaging.

7. *Export:*

According to the provisions of Regulation 1013/2006, implemented in the Law on sustainable waste management, waste in cross border traffic is divided onto the Green list and Yellow list, which are both listed in the Regulation on the waste catalogue (NN 90/15). As in the EU, the waste from the Yellow list undergoes the notification procedure, whether or not it was exported for recovery or disposal.

All waste shipped to another country for disposal has to undergo the notification procedure.

There are also special requirements for the waste from the Green list, when not implementing the OECD Decision on cross border waste transport, the transport must comply with Regulation (EC) 1418/2007., or 1013/2006.

8. *Transformation:*

The legislation foresees two methods for waste management: burning waste and mechanical-biological processing of waste. The latter is considered a more desirable method. It includes different processes to achieve specific goals, one of which is maximizing reusable resources.

MB centres are planned across Croatia, as described above, but for now, only 1 is in function, as a centre for waste management in Primorje – Gorski kotar County.

From every 100 tonnes collected, 30 tonnes are drained in the biological process. Then 5 tonnes are extracted from the waste in terms of metal, cardboard, and plastic, and 35 tonnes is transformed into solid recovered fuel.

9. *Re-use:*

Within the last plan for waste management, the establishment of a fully operational system for waste management has been delayed. We have just in 2017. Adopted a plan that is based on the principles of circular economy, and the goal is set at 95% of waste to be adequately managed by 2030. Croatia has 1 operational centre for waste management, it hasn't started constructing sorting stations yet and has barely started to encourage citizens to sort their household waste. And it must do so in the very near future.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

To ensure the fulfilment of measures taken upon to the EU, Croatia must drastically start improving its performance in waste management.

The system for re-use relies of private companies that collect and buy waste to recover, or recycle materials for new use, and for new companies using innovative technologies in producing bio-degradable plastics and are turned to the future.

Feedstock recycling: we will not consider this opportunity because, how written in the previous paragraphs, the feedstock recycling is the worst option possible in the “re-use perspective.”

8.3.2.1 Conclusion

This section regarding the legislation on waste management, with special attention to packaging and plastic packaging, shows that the Republic of Croatia has shown considerable progress in the organization of the management of waste and has taken steps forward to organizing the circular economy of packaging.

These sections have shown, however, that the country is in severe delay with the implementation of the measures proscribed in the national plans for waste management, even the first one that came out of force in 2015.

The country is in delay with the construction of county centres for waste management, and the local and regional public authorities are in delay with providing conditions and services for waste separation.

When it comes to Rijeka, and the local surrounding municipalities which gravitate around the Centre for waste management Marišćina, it is noticeable that this is the only such centre operational in Croatia so far, and Rijeka and the local municipalities have at their disposal, containers for sorting waste separately. The waste is separated by plastic, tin, beverage cartons, paper, cardboard, and glass. The waste is then collected separately by the municipal company Čistoća d.o.o. and transported to Marišćina. Citizens can also bring other waste, bulk waste, and recyclable materials to 2 recycling yards, or 1 mobile, or to the private company METIS, which buys various kinds of materials from citizens and other companies.

It is difficult to evaluate the impact on the legislation on the recycling processes in Croatia, because, the recycling process has just begun. Most of the country is early stages of modifying the citizens` behaviour towards waste separation and improving their attitude towards our environment. It is a long process, but we will have to accelerate our endeavours to catch up with the commitments taken upon to reach EU standards.

So far, the system relies on private companies that are developing their own business in waste management and that recognize the future in the sustainability of the circular economy of waste.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.3.3 Policy experiences from case studies

8.3.3.1 interview - MI-PLAST

The interview (Annex 11 - Interview to MI-PLAST) was done with to MI-PLAST. MI-PLAST started working in late 1970s in Banja Luka (Bosnia and Herzegovina) but due to war incidents in 1991, it was moved to Rijeka where it has been officially operating since 1993. Its core business is production, distribution and recycling of polyethylene packaging used in household, construction, agriculture, tourism etc.

In 2010 MI-PLAST directed its work towards research and development of biodegradable materials based on biopolymers and has participated in several research projects within the EU programs for research and development and innovations – FP7, Horizon2020, Life+ and ESIF.

8.3.3.2 Recap of MI-PLAST opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

- Possibility to share experience with other companies and partners in Europe, also in the field of EoW criteria;
- It is very hard to obtain the permissions required for recycling waste;
- The excess of bureaucracy can create several adverse effects;
- With nice sorting and collection system is possible to produce excellent recycled plastic;
- Croatia mostly buy plastic waste from other countries where collection is better.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.4 Municipal and Regional Legislation – Turkey

Rapid urbanization and population increase due to advances in technology and industrialisation lead to enhance the adverse effect of human activities on the environment in Turkey such as in the world. Changing consumption behaviours and habits lead to rapidly increasing amount of generated solid waste causing solid waste management (collection, transport, handling, disposal, recycling) become difficult year by year. Thus, decreasing the generated solid waste amount became a must using integrated solid waste management. The separated collection at the sources and recycling of packaging wastes are a crucial factor at the decreasing of the amounts of solid waste.

Waste generation and management have been recognized as a priority for Turkey and policies are being developed to overcome existing obstacles. Furthermore, MSW management has been a pressure point for Turkey while being a candidate country for EU accession.

Waste Sources and Management Methods:

Municipal solid waste (MSW) in Turkey:

Municipal waste management is improving in Turkey day by day.

In **1991**, **22.3 million tonnes of MSW** was generated, or 590 kg per capita, **1.62 kg/capita-day**. In the major cities, winter waste is composed of 45%-50% food wastes, 5%-10% recyclables and 40%-50% ash, slag, and other non-recyclable waste. In summer, it is 80%-85% food wastes, 15%-18% recyclables and 1%-3% non-recyclables. In 1991, 81% of municipal solid waste was disposed in open dumps, 15% in seas, lakes and rivers, 2% was composted, and 2% was burned in the open, buried or dumped in agricultural land. In **1992**, household recycled 27% of paper and cardboard waste and 40% of glass. This increased to 36% for paper and cardboard in **1995** but fell to 24% for glass.

The State Institute of Statistics (TurkSat) has been collecting data on the status of waste services and waste disposal sites of all municipalities in Turkey within the scope of Environmental Statistics since 1994. Municipalities not being constituted in 2003 were not covered. According to the results of municipal solid waste statistics, waste of 3018 municipalities out of 3215 was collected in **2003**. The amount of solid waste collected from municipalities receiving waste collection services was realized as 12.86 million tonnes in summer, 13.26 million tonnes in winter and an annual average of **26.12 million tonnes**. From these results daily amount of solid waste per capita was calculated as 1.37 kg in summer, 1.38 kg in winter and **1.38 kg for yearly average**. In **2003**, **26.12 million tonnes of solid municipal waste** were collected, 45.3% was disposed of in municipality's dump, 28.5% was disposed of in controlled landfill, 15.2% was disposed of in metropolitan municipality's dump, 2.9% was disposed of in another municipality's dump, 2.3% was disposed of by burial, 1.2% was disposed of in composting plant, 1.0% was disposed of by burning in an open area, 0.9% was disposed of into lake and river.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Figure 27: Municipalities collecting and transporting solid waste, 2003 (TurkSat)

Solid waste															
Provinces	Population		Municipalities collecting and transporting solid waste					Total		Summer			Winter		
	Total	Municipal	Num ber of municipalities	Number	Population	Ratio in total population (%)	Ratio in total municipal population (%)	Amount (tonnes/year)	Per capita (kg/capita-day)	Amount of solid waste in summer	Amount (tonnes/day)	Per capita (kg/capita-day)	Amount of solid waste in winter	Amount (tonnes/day)	Per capita (kg/capita-day)
TURKEY	67 803 927	53 430 733	3 215	3 011	51 862 924	76,5	97,1	26 117 543	1,38	12 858 963	70 800	1,37	13 258 580	71 312	1,38
Istanbul	10 018 735	9 838 860	74	74	9 830 245	98,1	99,9	5 374 854	1,50	2 693 520	14 639	1,49	2 681 334	14 814	1,51

The amount of collected MSW in **2014** was **28 million tonnes**, equivalent to 90 % of the total generated MSW. The share of MSW going to landfill was increased by 114% in the years between 2001 and 2014. The number of sanitary landfill sites increased from 15 in 2003 to 82 in 2016. According to **2016** National Waste Management Plan and Action Plan (NWMP&AP) data, 61.07 % of the municipal waste is sent to sanitary landfills and 28.25 % is dumped into municipal dumpsites. 11 % of the MSW (packaging waste included) was reported as recycled, composted, or disposed of by other methods.

In **2016**, a total number of 1698 waste disposal and recovery facilities having a licence or a temporary licence or, regardless of licence, operated by or on behalf of municipalities were in operation. 140 of these facilities were waste disposal facilities and 1558 were waste recovery facilities. It is determined that 44 million tonnes of waste were landfilled, and 310 thousand tonnes of waste was incinerated, whereas 33 million tonnes of waste were recovered in recovery facilities.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Total environmental expenditure was realized as 31.8 billion TL in **2016**. Out of the total environmental expenditure, public sector accounted for 76.1% and business sector accounted for 23.9%. The share of total environmental expenditure in gross domestic product was 1.2%.

Total of environmental taxes accrued as 88.7 billion TL in 2016. In total environmental taxes, energy taxes accounted for 65.3%, followed by transport taxes as 33.5%, and resource and pollution taxes as 1.2% in **2016**.

Industrial Solid Waste (ISW):

According to the NEAP report of the State Planning Organization published in 1999;

- In **1992**, 25.0 million tons of industrial solid waste was produced, or 116 kg. per \$1,000 of GDP. Of this, 47% was sold, 36% was disposed of, 15% was recycled or reused, and 2% was unaccounted. Power plants generated another 12.3 million tons of solid waste, or 3,861 tons per Mtoe.
- Outside of cities, mining and rural power plants were important sources of industrial waste. Recycling rates in the non-household sectors are relatively low. 22% of firms in the service and commercial sectors have limited recycling, as do 21% of industries, 25% of hotels, and 18% of restaurants. Of those commercial establishments that recycled in 1992, 75% dealt with newspapers and magazines, 46% with packing paper, 14% with metals, and 9% with paper and glass. Just over half the firms used some of the collected materials in their own establishments, 43% sold or gave them away, 18% burned the materials, and 6% gave some recyclables to garbage collectors.

Figure 28: Waste types (%) (Turkey, 2014)

Characterisation of MSW in Kartal:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

To determine the actual waste characterisation of municipal solid waste, an in-situ research was carried out in Kartal in **2015** as academic thesis.

According to the research results, the composition of MSW has been as follows: organic 57.6%, packaging 26.5%, other flammable (diapers, bags, shoes, textiles, pillows, etc.) 8%, yard 2.9%, other flammable bulky waste (furniture parts, etc.) 1.5%, waste electrical and electronic equipment 1.2%, other non-flammable 0.98%, ash 0.87% and hazardous wastes 0.19%.

In economic analysis studies, cost for collection-sorting of packing wastes was defined as 186 TL/tonne (≈ 58.38 €/tonne). Moreover, the costs were calculated for the collection-sorting of packing wastes as 0.057 TL/km-day (≈ 0.0179 €/km-day), spent 46% for personal, 31% for the vehicle and 23 % as facility operation cost. As a result, the calculated total revenue from the sale of packaging waste was 210 TL/tonne (6.913 €/tonne) and revenue from paper/cardboard 83.73%, plastic 12.53%, metal 3.53% and glass 0.21%.

Recycling and recovery:

The number of licensed recycling and recovery facilities has skyrocketed in the last decade.

Table 5: Number of licensed sorting and recycling facilities for packaging waste⁵⁴

Year	Sorting Facilities	Recycling Facilities
2003	15	13
2006	47	38
2008	81	91

Distribution of the recycling facilities is as 18 for paper, 6 for glass, 55 for plastic, 3 for metal, 2 for composite in the related data.

Table 6: Amount of collected municipal waste (Thousand tonnes) by disposal and recovery methods, 2008 - 2016⁵⁵

	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016
Total	24 361	25 277	25 845	28 011	31 584

⁵⁴ Ministry of Environment

⁵⁵ TurkStat, Statistics on Environment, 2016

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Municipality's dumping site	12 677	11 001	9 771	9 936	9 095
Controlled landfill site	10 947	13 747	15 484	17 807	19 338
Other disposal methods ⁵⁶	461	334	435	141	58
Recovery facilities ⁵⁷	276	194	155	126	3 092

Table 7: Waste disposal and recovery facilities statistics, 2014, 2016⁵⁸

	2014		2016	
	Number of facilities	Amount of waste treated (Tonnes)	Number of facilities	Amount of waste treated (Tonnes)
Waste disposal facilities	117	41 324 637	140	44 125 262
Controlled landfill sites	113	41 281 755	134	43 815 135
Incineration plants	4	42 882	6	310 127
Waste recovery facilities	868	19 724 241	1 558	33 083 400
Composting plants	4	94 019	7	140 467
Co-incineration plants	39	532 343	35	738 908

⁵⁶ Includes disposals by filling of land with waste, dumping onto land, burning in an open area, dumping onto river and lake, burying, etc.

⁵⁷ Until 2016, data refers only to wastes that are sent to composting facilities whereas, since 2016 data refers to wastes collected separately by municipalities and sent to licensed recovery facilities that recovers glass, metal, paper, plastic, etc. as well as biogas and composting facilities.

⁵⁸ TurkStat, Statistics on Environment, 2016

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Other recovery facilities⁵⁹	825	19 097 879	1 516	32 204 025
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Policies on Waste Recovery (from the report of Turkish Court of Accounts, 2007):

In 2007, the Turkish Court of Accounts published its report on policies on waste recovery in Turkey in the framework of national regulations and evaluated the implementation results. Recovery of wastes through the methods of reuse, recycling, composting, generating energy ensures a great deal of saving both in the costs of production through transforming the materials which have economic value to an input to economy and in the costs of waste disposal through decreasing the amount of waste.

Thus, in the environmental legislation the recycling activities are encouraged and framed with specific standards. To safeguard recycling of packages, quota application has been introduced to producers. With this practice, the manufacturers, and sellers of plastic, metallic, glass and carton paper packages are liable to collect and recycle a certain percent of these materials. The practice of quota is applied to some special kinds of wastes such as batteries, accumulators, mineral oil, etc. The sectors producing wastes subject to quota application are encouraged to establish associations and organizations for the fight against waste and recycling. In this way, these activities are tried to be safeguarded and kept under record.

Within this framework, production, and distribution firms especially in the field of packaging wastes (paper, glass etc) established foundations and associations. Recycling of wastes such as used batteries and accumulators, waste oils in the "Special Wastes" category is done either by the organizations established by the facilities operating in the related sector or the companies with special recycling license. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of such organizations and special-licensed companies. 2.16. In fact, the legislation in effect introduces liability of separation at source to production, distribution and sale units including the households and the final consumers and provides for criminal sanction to the contradictory actions. Besides, it makes recycling obligatory by prohibiting disposal of wastes excluding organic wastes.

In Turkey, since 1950s waste recycling, especially glass and paper, has become a major commercial activity. However, the individual collectors generally separate recyclable matters. These persons buy used package from sellers or collect them in the streets or from garbage containers. This method is the most common one in Turkey and 25-30% of all recyclable waste is estimated to be collected in this way (excluding inorganic materials) according to researches made by the Ministry.

Apart from this, municipalities recycle at a very limited level. A limited number of municipalities are ensuring the separation of recyclable waste at source at the selected

⁵⁹ Includes the facilities which recover waste metal, plastic, paper, mineral, etc.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

pilot area by cooperating with the institutions that are authorized in the field of waste recycling.

Although a significant progress in the separation of wastes resulted from industrial and commercial activities has been achieved in the implementation; most of the household waste has been directly transferred to landfills without any process of separation by the municipalities for years. The main reason that the wastes are not separated at the source in houses although it is a legal obligation is that the infrastructure for the collection and shipment of separated wastes has not been formed. There is no temporary landfill space such as containers to separate and store the recyclable wastes and the municipalities have no instruments to collect recyclable wastes separately and transfer them to the recycling facilities.

Another problem stemming from implementation is that the associations and foundations established by the production and distribution firms pay certain amount of money to street collectors for wastes that they collect and sell to facilities in the relevant sector in order to fulfil their liability of recycling instead of establishing a system that is to enable separation at source, transfer to proper facilities and transforming them to an economic asset by processing at these facilities. These establishments are regarded to have fulfilled their recycling liability solely by presenting their documents with regard to their payments to street-collectors to the Ministry. In other words, such type of organizations established for recycling serve for production and distribution firms to release from their recycling liability with the documents they obtained through financing unhealthy and primitive street-collecting system rather than ensuring recycling.

One of the main problems with regard to recovery is that recycling sector is not under register. Hence, there are no established standards. The sector cannot even fill the quota of 12% in the mineral oils. And the sector's complaints about illegal and unhealthy recycling show us how big the problem is. To prevent illegal, unhealthy, and unsafe activities, necessary auto-control mechanisms should be established, and the audit and monitoring activities should become widespread.

In order to meet the requirements of EC directives on waste minimization; both prevention at source and recovery mechanisms should be activated. Fulfilling the requirements of EU Acquis requires first the establishment of the necessary infrastructure. Moreover, this requires an important amount of investment such as the construction of modern landfills, rehabilitation, or closure of existing ones, separating wastes at source and shipping separately, establishment of recycling facilities, etc. Secondly, apart from the Ministry and other relevant institutions of the central administration, the local administrations, households, the waste industry, voluntary organizations, the manufacturers, and the marketers should assume responsibility within a very close cooperation. Strengthening the audit and monitoring capacity will play an important role in adapting the recycling system with the modern norms.

Achieving the objectives in the waste recovery also depends on the creation of a market for recycled products. Thus, with an Article inserted to the Regulation on Solid Waste Management in 1998, the Ministry, the highest civilian authority and the municipalities are

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

given the responsibility to encourage the usage of the materials that can be recycled or disposed without giving harm to nature as well as the recycled materials and products. However, this policy has no instruments for implementation. As it can be seen in the examples from developed countries, the selection of such kind of products should be encouraged by amending the procurement legislation and the public interest should be increased through campaigns.⁶⁰

As this could not be managed within the previous existing system in 2007, the Ministry of Environment started the implementation of compatible legislation with EU to supply legislative and administrative infrastructure.

Legislation on Environment:

Currently, most of the EU waste management directives concerning MSW have been transposed into Turkey's national legislation.

There are a number of arrangements for the protection and improvement of environment in the **Constitution** and in many laws in Turkey. The number of such arrangements is increasing as the importance attached to environment is increasing. The arrangements on waste management constitute one of the most comprehensive parts of Turkey's environmental legislation. At present various regulations in the field of waste management are in force and all of them were improved and updated or rearranged within the scope of various projects and with the aim of harmonizing with EU Acquis.

As encountered at global level, rapid urbanization, and population growth in parallel with technological developments and industrialization is increasing the pressure of human activities on environment in Turkey. While the growth in production and marketing during this process makes excessive use of natural resources inevitable, wastes produced due to increasing trend of consumption have reached to threatening levels due to their quantity and hazardous contents. On this account, in parallel with the environment consciousness rising all over the world, the protection of environment has become one of the major priority policies of countries and waste management has taken a major field among the environmental protection policies of all countries. Aiming to prevent rapid consumption of natural resources and to settle the problem of wastes resulting from production, marketing, and consumption activities through converting them to economic asset, the waste management strategies form the basis of "sustainable development" approach that has been gradually adopted all over the world as a prioritized policy objective.

In Turkey, waste management has been the subject of a number of legal arrangements starting from 1930s. Since then, the number of institutions assuming role in the environmental field has increased.

⁶⁰ (https://www.sayistay.gov.tr/En/Upload/files/4-TCA_Waste_Management_Report.pdf, 2007)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Turkey has made great progress over the last decades in creating mechanisms to address its environmental problems. The foundations of the Turkish system for environmental management were laid with the Third Five Year Development Plan (1973-1977), and the main features of this system were cast in the **1982 Constitution** which recognizes the right of citizens to live in a healthy and balanced environment, the **Environment Law** was passed in **1983**, and the **Ministry of Environment was established in 1991**. Thus, Turkey's environmental management system and institutional base were both in place **before the 1992 Rio Declaration and Agenda 21** which set forth important changes in environmental protection policies, and management systems. Turkey recognizes the necessity to harmonize national environmental policies with approaches adopted by such international documents. Public awareness and demand for a clean environment are growing; and active non-governmental environmental organizations are emerging. Despite these positive developments, environmental issues have not been incorporated into economic and social decisions.

NEAP and NWMSAP:

The national and international fundamental documents such as the Five-Year Development Plans, National Environmental Action Plan, and National Program for the Adoption of the EU Acquis covers the objectives and policies concerning waste management as well.

Towards the attainment of sustainable development, besides appropriate economic and social policies, a set of essential steps including the development of an environment strategy; for identification of priorities in relation to the environmental investments, creation of the basis of collaboration between relevant organizations; and collection of information on environmental investment programs to mobilize the support of the international organizations are required.

The Development Plan is the main instrument for coordinating government policies, including those for environmental management. Although the environmental topics have been given more place in the **Fifth Five-year National Development Plan** covering 1985-1989; the issue was not handled under a separate title. In the **Sixth Five-Year Development Plan** (1990-1994); the waste management issue was handled under a separate title. Some objectives and policies were determined such as supporting the municipalities in the establishment of joint solid waste disposal facilities, the principles concerning the selection of location for regular landfilling, and operational principles, the separate disposal of medical wastes, production of landfilling tanks for the liquid wastes of the nuclear waste units.

In the **Seventh Five Year Development Plan** (1996-2000), several policies are determined such as the preparation of national environmental strategy, harmonization of the environmental legislation with EU and other international standards, giving support to the local administrations, support of waste minimization and recycling operations, prevention of all types of waste import. Moreover, it is underlined that capacity building in the field of waste management shall be attached higher importance.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

In the **Eighth Plan** (2001-2005), some objectives, principles and policies have been determined such as source separation, raising awareness in the households, revisions in legislation, increasing the amount of environmental clear up tax to the level sufficient for covering the costs, planning and implementation of waste management by one single authority in the Metropolitan Municipalities. Preparation and implementation of a “**National Solid Waste Disposal Master Plan**,” increasing the quantity of the materials recovered to the industry via recycling, advertising campaigns to ensure the consumption of recovered productions, maintaining the separation of solid wastes at the source were put forward.

The **National Environmental Action Plan (NEAP)** responds to the need for a strategy and can supplement the existing Development Plan with concrete actions for integrating environment and development.

The first **NEAP** was prepared with wide participation of all parties and stakeholders in 1995 under the coordination of the State Planning Organization and with the technical assistance of the Ministry of Environment and the financial support of the World Bank and put into effect in 1998 by Ministry of Environment.

There have been a number of National Waste Management Plans covering the period 2009-2013. The main aim of the Plan is to determine national policies and the decision-making structure for the preparation of detailed waste management plans for separate waste streams. The latest Plans were made with the aim of fulfilling criteria according to the EU harmonization process. In 2008, the “**Regulation on General Principles of Waste Management**” (OJ 5 July 2008, #2697) set the framework of waste management in Turkey, from waste generation to disposal so that the procedures are followed in an environmentally sound way (ETC/SCP).

The last **National Waste Management Strategy and Action Plan (NWMSAP)** was prepared in the framework of Turkey’s **10th Five Year Development Plan** of 2014-2018. The **NWMSAP** covers years from 2014 to 2023 and has the objective to regain the waste and put it in economy by means of recycling and recovery and to define sustainable waste management strategies in country wide, to prevent rapid decrease of natural resources. The target is to recover 35% of waste and send the rest only to controlled disposal. In this scope, in September 2017 the objective of “**Zero Waste**” was published and all governmental and municipal organisations were asked to prepare zero waste plan. Municipal wastes, packaging wastes, sanitary wastes, hazardous wastes, special wastes such as vegetable waste oil, mineral waste oil, waste batteries and accumulators, electric and electronic wastes, end-of-life tires, end-of-life vehicles are in the framework of the plan to be collected and recycled more efficiently. The “**Zero Waste**” strategy has been started in September 2017.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Method	Beginning	Target in 2023
	2014	
Packaging waste collected in source separated from other wastes	5.3%	12%
Recovery of MSW by biological treatment	0.2%	4%
Recovery of MSW by mechanical-biological treatment	5.4%	11%
Recovery of MSW by thermal treatment	0.3%	8%
Disposal of MSW in landfill	88.7%	65%

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Ministry of Environment:

Given the magnitude of environmental problems, national institutions were created to identify, improve, coordinate, monitor and supervise activities, as well as procure resources. The first was a Permanent Board of Consultants for Environmental Problems, in the early 1970s. Then, in 1978, an Environment Organization was attached to the Prime Minister's office, as was a General Directorate of Environment in 1984, which was transformed into the Under secretariat of Environment in 1989. The Ministry of Environment was established by government Decree no. 443 in 1991, which empowers it to conduct activities to protect and improve the environment.

Waste generation and management have been recognized as a priority for Turkey and policies are being developed to overcome existing obstacles. Furthermore, MSW management has been a pressure point for Turkey while being a candidate country for EU accession.

The **Waste Framework Directive** (2008/98/EC) of the EU establishes certain conditions that must be complied by the end-of-waste requirements. Like the efforts in the EU, Turkey is interested in introducing such criteria into its waste legislation to promote material valorisation and waste re-use in the country. During the accession period, Turkey has adopted all relevant waste directives into its legislation. All requirements in the **Waste Framework Directive** (2008/98/EC) were harmonised in the "**Regulation on Waste Management**" (OJ 2 April 2015, #29314) except the end-of-waste ("EoW") criteria defined in the Article 6 of the Directive.

The "**Regulation on Waste Management**" (OJ 2 April 2015, #29314) is a crucial step towards successful waste management in Turkey. Although it is shown to have some shortcomings in its implementation, the MSW management system has been improved by novel studies and new regulations. The main reasons of shortcomings can be identified as:

- Waste management systems development was not a priority policy area;
- Duties and powers are distributed among many institutions and organizations, with inadequate coordination and cooperation among them;
- The fees and taxes collected in return for services were inadequate;
- The infrastructure (facilities and the existing technical capacity) was limited and most of facilities needed modernization.

Besides of shortcoming, the regulation brought also progress in environmental management, stating that wastes should be collected by and delivered to licenced companies, imposing controls for the re-using waste derived from secondary materials in order to protect the human health and the environment from risks associated to the collection, transport, treatment, storage and disposal of waste. These administrative burdens in some cases might not be necessary where minor risk is involved, and the certainty of re-use is guaranteed. Removing the administrative burdens, by changing the waste status of the material when it is not necessary, may be an economic incentive to encourage the re-use and upcycle of wastes.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The Turkish Ministry of Environment and Urbanization (MoEU) gives licenses to collection, separation, and recycling facilities.

The National strategy on the reduction of biodegradable waste to be disposed of in landfill facilities has also been developed. This strategy shall include the measures to be taken with the methods such as recycling, composting, biogas production or energy/material recovery. According to the strategy for the reduction of biodegradable waste amounts, the implementation of the EU Landfill Directive (99/31/EC) will be carried out by 2025 (MoEU, 2012).

Environmental Law:

The “**Environmental Law**” describes all the pollution and waste type definitions, authority and responsibilities of the citizen and manufacturers as waste producers, restrictions, penal sanctions, authority, and responsibilities of the ministry of environment, metropolitan municipalities, and local municipalities.

There are regulations according to waste types: “**Regulation on Waste Control**”, “**Regulation on Controlled Landfill of Wastes**”, “**Regulation on Packaging Waste Control**”, “**Regulation of Hazardous Waste**”, “**Regulation on Control of Medical Wastes**”, “**Regulation on the Control of Waste Electrical and Electronic Goods**”, “**Regulation on the Control of the End-of-life Tires**”, “**Regulation on the Control of the End-of-life Vehicles**”, “**Regulation on the Control of Waste Batteries and Accumulators**”, “**Waste Oil Control Regulation**”, “**Waste Vegetable Oil Control Regulation**”, “**Regulation on the Control of Waste Electrical and Electronic Goods**”, “**Regulation on Environmental Inspection**”, “**Regulation on Environmental Permit and License**”, “**Regulation on Control of Excavation Soil, Construction and Demolition Wastes**”, “**Regulation on Control of Polychlorinated Biphenyls and Polychlorinated Terphenyls**”, “**Regulation on Mine Wastes**”, “**Regulation on Waste Incineration**”, “**Regulation on Restoration of Land Damaged by Mining Activities**”, “**Regulation on Receiving Waste from Ships and Control of Wastes**” .

The **Environmental Law** (no 2872) of 1983 embodies the ‘polluter pays’ principle adopted by other countries and sets forth the concept of absolute liability to operationalize it. It also defines activities to prevent and solve environmental problems. These involve banning certain polluting operations, requiring environmental impact assessments (EIAs) for specific activities (effective in 1993), identifying sensitive locales to be defined as special environmental protection areas, providing sanctions to prevent the discharge of hazardous chemical substances and wastes, banning noise, promoting incentives to pollute less, creating an environmental fund, and securing participation in decision making bodies such as the Environment Council (ENC), Higher Council for the Environment (HCE), and Local Environment Committees (LECs).

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging			
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1	
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18	

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA):

The **EIA Regulation**, drafted by the Ministry of Environment and enacted in 1993, was based on US and EU procedures.

Local governments:

Municipalities produce infrastructure and services for protecting and managing the environment. They are legally responsible for managing solid waste, installing, and operating water, gas, and urban transport services, and constructing and repairing streets. Although sewerage and bus services are not specified among municipal duties, they have been assumed in practice. Further, municipalities have an important planning role, as they are responsible for approving structure and implementation plans that affect all forms of development within their boundaries. Municipal revenues, especially of metropolitan governments, are obtained from diverse sources: local taxes, fees from citizens; required grants and credit with technical assistance and implementation plans are given by The Bank of Provinces (İller Bank). Aside from İller Bank, municipalities can borrow with central government guarantees from external sources for their larger projects. On average, 40% of a municipality's budget is spent on "cleansing" activities which is primarily solid waste collection and disposal.

The authority and responsibilities of municipalities are mentioned in "**Municipal Law**" and "**Metropolitan Municipality Law.**"

According to the **Metropolitan Municipality Law** (OJ 10 July 2004, #5216) and the **Municipal Law** (OJ 3 July 2005, #5393), sole responsibility for the management of municipal waste falls on the municipalities. They are responsible for providing all services regarding collection, transportation, separation, recycling, disposal, and storage of solid wastes, or to appoint others to provide these services. Nevertheless, while fulfilling their duties in collecting and transporting the solid waste, they do not show the required level of activity and attention in solid municipal waste management. This situation has been improving by newly adopted management perspectives.

Current Situation in Packaging Waste Management in Turkey:

According to Ministry of Environment and Urbanization, the statistical data about quantity of waste and packaging waste in İstanbul province in 2016 is as follows (Waste Information System, 2017):

Waste type	Quantity of waste produced(kg)	Quantity of waste released to market (kg)	Recovery rate (%)	Quantity to be recovered (kg)	Quantity recovered (kg)	Actual recovery rate (%)
Plastic	5.712.346.598	502.101.453	48	241.008.697	1.707.813	0,34

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Metal	155.600.148	39.004.968	48	18.722.385	0	0,00
Composite	50.160.749	48.049.730	48	23.063.870	0	0,00
Paper, cardboard	1.135.538.242	762.880.106	48	366.182.451	31.120.374	4,08
Glass	189.409.412	204.212.308	48	136.421.908	2.950.990	1,04
Wood	23.869.669	177.698.556	5	884.927,8	169.081	0,09
Total	7.266.924.818	1.813.947.121	45,49	794.284.239	35.948.258	1,98

In İstanbul, the number of facilities having environmental permit and license to packaging waste recovery and/or packaging waste collection and separation is 163. Besides this, according to the registration of İstanbul Tax Office, there are 720 packaging waste producers, 6.414.893 market launchers and 453 supplier facilities. The Packaging Waste Management Plan of 23 district municipalities were approved. Number of registered business firms is 7.849. According to the Waste Management Application, total registered quantity of hazardous waste derived from facilities operating in İstanbul was 143.829,55 tonnes in 2016, 31.169,01 tonnes of this quantity was disposed, 111.168,02 tonnes recovered, 4.129,84 tonnes exported, and 730,64 tonnes is stocked.

Control of Packing Wastes in Turkey and the General Framework of Legislation:

To be able to compare the progress in recycling, former data may be evaluated.

Solid waste recovery and recycling has been a longstanding commercial activity in Turkey. Glass and paper recycling have been conducted at industrial scales since the 1950s. With the recent investments in the recycling industry, all types plastic materials, glass, paper, and metals can be recycled at industrial levels in Turkey.

Turkey, as one of the biggest steel scrap importers of the world, recycles more than 2 million tons of steel scrap annually. Recycling of nonferrous metals is also widespread and conducted at industrial scale, including aluminium, copper, lead and silver. The scrap metal recycling industry is built on small and medium scale scrap dealers spread around the country. This type of operation is also valid for most of collection and recovery of recyclable MSW. Recovery of plastics, paper, glass, and metal from municipal solid waste is mostly conducted, as indicated above, by the scrap dealers and individual collectors (scavengers etc.). These individual collectors and scrap dealers purchase the used packaging (mostly paper and cardboard) from commercial units, markets and business centres and

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

reprocess (sort and bale) these materials to sell directly to the industrial recycling facilities. In addition, scavenging and collection from the waste bins is a widespread activity. Since this type of collection and recovery process is a part of “unregistered” economic activity, it is difficult to specify figures reflecting actual collection and recovery. This is a widespread collection and recovery method utilized in Turkey. However, estimates made by experienced individuals working in this field indicates that total amount of MSW recovered in Turkey is over 1.0 million tons/year. This estimation, together with the data showing the amount of packaging and recyclable materials placed into market, shown in following table, packaging waste recycling in Turkey is well above 30%.

Table 8: Amounts of packaging waste (tons/year) placed in to market, and estimated recovery and recycling figures for Turkey in 2000

	Placed into market (tons/year)	Amount recovered (tons)	% Recycling
Paper and board	1.850.000	700.000	36
Glass	350.000	80.000	25
Plastics	550.000	170.000	30
Metal	150.000	50.000	30
Total	2.900.000	1.000.000	35

However, most of these activities operate within the hands of private entrepreneurs and waste collectors working on streets and in waste yards. This obviously is driven by the fact that a strong used material market operates in Turkey as well as by the limited economic conditions in the country that provide an employment opportunity for this sector. Paper and cardboard are collected through the scrap/ waste dealers and delivered to recycling facilities nationwide. There exist approximately 30 mediums to large-scale paper recyclers operating with capacities exceeding 50 tons/day. The output of these facilities is mostly the packaging cardboard made out of recycled paper. Glass recycling also works on the free market principles, which is mostly operated by the Glassworks Co. of Turkey, consuming more than 90% of the collected used glass bottles. The collection and recovery scheme are the same as paper and cardboard recovery. In addition to glass bottle banks well spread in large cities, private entrepreneurs and scrap dealers collect, sort, and prepare used glass bottles for recycling. There exist five major buys back centres and glass cullet preparation units nationwide. Significant efforts have been made, in recent years, to increase the number of glass bottle banks and separate collection systems.

The plastics and metal packaging collection system are essentially the same. PET recycling has been an industrial activity since the establishment of a major PET recycling plant in 1992. HDPE, LDPE, and PVC post-consumer bottle recycling have also been a long-standing

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

operation and have been evolving since the oil crises in the 1970s. Several small-scale plastics recyclers (like PVC recycling operations) exist, since these facilities can be established with fairly low initial investments. In summary a strong market demand exists for almost all types of packaging waste, regardless of its nature.

Current scrap material prices are indicative of the world market influences. However, glass, paper and PET recycling are being conducted at fairly high industrial capacities, which is another important recyclable item in household solid waste. Used beverage and tin cans are being recycled together with steel scrap by the steel smelters. Several small-scale aluminium recyclers are spread around the country; and a major aluminium can recycler recently started operation in the western part of Turkey with a capacity of 12,000 tons/year. Due to the high intrinsic economic value of aluminium cans, the aluminium collection and recycling rate is fairly high, exceeding 60% recovery rate.

Developments in waste industry offer new opportunities to Turkey. Number of institutions authorized in accordance with the environment legislation is 12, including 4 that are for packing wastes. It is observed that a new and extended market is rapidly forming in the area of waste managing.

According to data given by ÇEVKO, waste composition in 5 different megalopolis cities in Turkey was as follows in 2000 (%):

	Bursa	İstanbul	İzmir	Adana	Mersin
Population (1997)	1,958,529	9,198,809	3,114,859	1,682,483	1,508,232
Organic matter	53.1	43	46	64.4	63
Recyclable	36.4	33.9	31.0	25.2	29.4
Paper and cardboard	18.4	7.8	12	14.8	18.42
Plastics	11.6	14.2	12	5.92	6.69
Glass	3.4	6.2	3	1.4	1.25
Metals	3	5.8	4	3.08	3.08
Other	10.5	23	23	11	8

Average per capita municipal waste generation in Turkey may be assumed as 0.95 kg/person-day. If overall figures are required to reflect the compositional characteristics of

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

MSW in Turkey, organic components can be assumed to be 50–55%, whereas recyclable and others (ash and slag, dust etc.) can be assumed to be 20–25%. However, some correction is always required to accommodate the statistical variations arising from the specific nature of waste sources, seasonal changes, and demographic facts. For example, significant alterations may be presented in tourist sites due to the condensed population and the type of consumption during the tourist season.

As a result of the necessity of harmonization of EU's *acquis* with legal *acquis* within the context of Turkey's member state status, **Directive on the Control of Packing Wastes** was adapted as **Regulation on Packing and Control of Packing Waste** on 2004 and published on the National Journal on 30 July 2004. The regulation entered into force on January 1, 2005. Parallel to the amendments made to the UN Directive, the Directive has taken its current form by undergoing changes first on 2007 and then on 2011, taking the necessities of the sector into account.

The regulation is based on the **United Nations Directive on Packing Wastes** ("Directive") dated 20 December 1994 numbered 94/62/EC, as a result of European Union membership process and endeavour of harmonization of our national legislation with the legal *acquis* of European Union.

"**Regulation on Control of Solid Wastes**" (OJ 14 March 1991, #20814,) was changed by "**Regulation on Change on Regulation of Control of Solid Wastes**" (OJ 25 April 2002, #24736), definition and processing framework was declared about recycling, organic recycling, collecting-sorting facility, licencing, returnable packaging waste, quota. Later, the basis of the legal regulation of control of packing wastes was specifically given under the name of "**Regulation of Control of Packaging and Packaging Waste**" (OJ 30 July 2004, #25538, entered in force on 1 January 2005), aligning Turkey's legislation with the EU Directive 94/62/EC. Its aim is to minimise the generation of packaging waste and to also increase the rate of recycled packaging waste which cannot be avoided within the method of production. The regulation also includes principles and standards for packaging waste to be collected separately at its source, then sorted and transported within a certain system. Institutions and suppliers who are not members of authorized organisations are obliged to recover packaging waste. Recycling targets are given to authorized institutions and suppliers with this regulation.

It was then amended under the version "**Regulation of Control of Packaging Waste**" (published on OJ 25777, 05 April 2007) has the main changes for marketers and producers such as: the definition of packaging explained by giving examples, wastes occurring during production were excluded of the definition, the marking of packaging during production was defined on voluntariness basis, access and submission to ministry through web system was started, heavy metal concentration to be controlled by marketers, marketers had the right to be represented by authorized bodies.

The Regulations were later amended in 2011. The primary aim is to reduce the amount of packaging waste going to landfill and includes all materials such as, plastics, metals, glass, paper/cardboard, and composites. The law also introduced specific recovery targets for all packaging regardless of whether it is domestic or industrial.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Considering the exigencies in the sector and the changes that have been made in the **EU Acquis Communautaire the Draft Study on Regulation on Packing Wastes** ("Draft Regulation") has been prepared and it is been submitted to the public opinion on 23rd March 2016.

Since the regulation involves many parties from industrial organizations to municipalities, consumers, and waste management companies, and since each party has its own priorities, hundreds of different opinions on the draft are sent to the Ministry. Issues where no consensus exists even in the industry itself add a further twist of the knife to this chaos. In an environment of such diverse opinions, ÇEVKO Foundation, which has been driven by the goal of establishing a healthy system of separate collection since its foundation, has reviewed the draft in meetings held with many stakeholders of the industry, compiled items that have been agreed should or should not be included in the new draft, and shared this document with all parties and our Ministry.

In the Draft Regulation, the scope of regulation has been indicated as "all packing that have been released to the market and these packing's' wastes". Therefore, as in the current regulation, regardless of their domestic, industrial, or commercial nature, all packing and packing wastes that are made of plastic, metal, glass, paper-carton, composite, and the like materials are in the scope of the Draft Regulation.

Distinctly from the Regulation, in the Draft Regulation, it has been explicitly given place to the concept of "extended producer responsibility". Whereas the Article 4 of the Draft Regulation refers to "extended producer responsibility", Article 9, which stipulates the packing producers' liabilities, indicates that the first liability of the packing producer is "as part of the extended producer liability, to produce, as from the packing design phase, with the minimum waste production after the manufacture and usage, with the easiest recycling and recovery, with the most economical and the least environmentally harmful manner.

Within the context of the current Directive, "Extended producer liability" means the usage of repair, reutilization, fragmentation and recycling processes and application of one of the methods that design, production and sale that favours and enables the efficient usage, in order to reach the aim of efficient use of resources in the free movement of the products in the market.

The remarkable matter in the Draft Regulation is that different objectives have been defined for the recycling and recovery of packing wastes. Alongside the Authorized Institutions' and the market launchers', which apply the deposit system, "supply oriented" packing waste recycling objective, it is been designated non-supply-oriented recycling and recovery objective throughout the country.

The requirement for obtaining environmental license for the persons and institutions that desire to be in service for the purpose of packing waste parsing, recycling, and recovery, has been regulated under the Draft Regulation as well. If these facilities do not comply with the designated conditions in the Draft Regulation, the execution of administrative sanctions have been foreseen within the scope of the Environmental Law numbered 2872.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

After evaluation of the Draft Regulation, the latest **Regulation on Packaging Waste Control** ("Regulation") was published in Official Journal number 30283 on 27 December 2017, entering into effect on 1 January 2018.

Turkey has updated the regulatory regime for packaging and waste, including significant new rules regarding waste collection and recycling. Most notably, **free plastic bags will be banned from the beginning of 2019 and packaging used in the Turkish market must be at least partially made from recycled materials.**

All producers, marketers and suppliers of packaging are obligated under the Turkish regulations, these include: Packaged product suppliers, Fillers and packers, Brand owners, Importers. Obligated parties are required to achieve recovery targets mentioned in the legislation as well as carrying out activities for raising public awareness of recycling. Producers can fulfil their obligations individually or by joining an approved compliance scheme such as ÇEVKO (Foundation for Protection of Environment and Valorisation of Packaging Wastes). Membership of a scheme transfers much of the company's obligations to the scheme, with the scheme taking on the majority of administrative burdens in addition to organising the collection and recovery of the packaging waste.

Labelling become mandatory in Turkey with the Regulation published in 2005 ordering to terminate the labelling until 1st January of 2007. ÇEVKO is the contact point for the Green Dot membership.

"Circular Economy," quite a novel concept not only locally but also globally, was the topic of comprehensive discussions between 5-6 October 2017 with the participation of a wide range of stakeholders including those from the public and private sector, to representatives of finance institutions and NGOs. Operating for 26 years for the establishment and development of a sustainable recycling system for the economic and continuous recovery of packaging waste in Turkey, the ÇEVKO Foundation presented the "Circular Economy Package" in its international congress. 263 attendees participated in the Circular Economy Congress ranging from the public and private sector, to NGOs, universities, and media outlets. The package came into force in 2018 in the European Union (EU), bringing along new legal regulations.

Legislation on Food Safety and Health:

- **"Law on Public Health"** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593) is the pioneer in public health protection issues and regulates the administrative and technical basement for following legislation in Turkey.
- **"Law on Veterinary Services, Plant Health, Food and Feed"** (OJ 11 June 2010, #5996)
- **"Regulation on Turkish Food Codex"** (OJ 29 December 2011, 28157.3)
- **"Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food"** (OJ 29 December 2011, #28157.3)
- **"Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food"** (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **“Regulation on Food Safety and Food Quality Inspection and Control”** (OJ 26 September 2008, #27009)
- **“Regulation on Water Intended for Human Consumption”** (OJ 17 February 2005, #25730, amended by OJ 31 July 2009, #2730, OJ 7 March 2013, #28580 and OJ 11 April 2014, #28969, OJ 20 October 2016, #29863)
- **“Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food”** (Com. #2013/34, published on OJ 17 July 2013, #28710)
- **“Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on the List of Food Simulants Used in Migration Test of the Components of the Plastic Materials and Articles in Contact with Food”** (Com. #2013/35, published on OJ 17 July 2013, #28710)
- **“Communiqué on the Principles and Procedures Related to Standard Practices That Must Be Complied within the Wholesale and Retail Trade of Vegetables and Fruits”** (OJ 3 October 2017, #30199)
- **“Communiqué on Food-Contact Active and Smart Materials and Articles of Turkish Food Codex”** (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382)

Food contact materials (FCMs) are all materials which are or are intended or likely to be in contact with food such as food packaging, kitchenware, and tableware, as well as materials for food manufacturing, preparation, storage, and distribution. They can thus influence food safety and quality throughout the whole of the food supply chain. FCMs cover a wide range of different materials such as plastic, paper, glass, and metal, but also adhesives, printing inks and coatings used in the finishing of the final articles. Actors in the chain include manufacturers of raw materials, intermediate and final FCMs and food products, as well as importers and distributors.

“Regulation on Turkish Food Codex” (OJ 16 November 1997, #23172) was amended in 2009. **“Regulation on Materials in Contact with Food in Turkish Food Codex”** (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382), **“Communiqué On Food-Contact Active and Smart Materials and Articles of Turkish Food Codex”** (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382) and **“Regulation on Food Safety and Food Quality Inspection and Control”** (OJ 26 September 2008, #27009) define the requirements in packaging in contact with food to be used only once or multiple times. The regulations are based on **Law on Veterinary Services, Plant Health, Food and Feed**, numbered 5996 published in 2010.

“Regulation on Water Intended for Human Consumption” (OJ 17 February 2005, #25730, amended by OJ 31 July 2009, #2730, OJ 7 March 2013, #28580 and OJ 11 April 2014, #28969, OJ 20 October 2016, #29863) prepared correspondingly to Conseil Directive 98/83/EC, Conseil Directive on 16 May 2003 numbered 2003/40/EC and EU Commission Regulation 115/2010, implemented by Public Health Agency under Ministry of Health defines technical and administrative issues on serving healthy potable water.

“Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food” (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382) is the newest regulation on FCMs. The new regulation aligns the rules on food contact materials with Regulation (EC) no 1935/2004. In addition, it sets the procedure for the authorization of the substances that are used in the food contact materials and articles.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

This legislation was prepared and adopted according to the Commission Regulation numbered 10/2011/EU "Commission Regulation on Plastic Materials and Articles" and Conseil Directive numbered 85/572/EEC on the "List of food simulants used in migration test of components of the plastic materials and articles in contact with food", in the framework of harmonization with EU legislation.

"Communiqué on the Principles and Procedures Related to Standard Practices That Must Be Complied within the Wholesale and Retail Trade of Vegetables and Fruits" (OJ 3 October 2017, #30199) regulates the packaging, transporting, storing and offer for retail sale of goods by the Ministry of Customs and Trade. 'Packaging' is defined. The Communiqué is published in context of **"Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food"** (OJ 29 December 2011, #28157.3).

"Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food" (Com. #2013/34-, published on OJ 17 July 2013, #28710) regulates the list of substances allowed to be used in the production of plastic layers in plastic materials and articles (monomers and other starting materials, additives other than colorants, non-solvent polymer production assistants and macromolecules obtained from microbial fermentation), it allows the use of colorants and solvents if they comply with the provisions of the **"Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food"**.

The specifications of food simulants used in migration test to determine the components of plastic materials and articles in contact with a single foodstuff or with a specific foodstuff group are given in **"Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on the List of Food Simulants Used in Migration Test of the Components of the Plastic Materials and Articles in Contact with Food"**.

Legislation on Chemical Substances and Hygiene:

Adoption of international legislation related to chemicals has been implemented considering the following legislation:

- **Commission regulation (EU) No 487/2013** of 8 May 2013 amending, for the purposes of its adaptation to technical and scientific progress, **Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures,**
- **Directive 2012/18/EU** of The European Parliament and of The Council of 4 July 2012 **on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances,** amending and subsequently repealing **Council Directive 96/82/EC (Seveso III),**
- **"The Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS)"** declared by United Nations,
- **REACH Regulation 1907/2006/EC** on "Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals"

Related national legislation:

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **Law on Preparation and Implementation of Technical Legislation on Products”** (OJ 29 June 2001, #4703)
- **“Regulation on Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Dangerous Substances and Preparations”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures” (SEA)** (OJ 11 December 2013, #28848 Bis)
- **“Regulation on Restrictions on the Manufacture, placing on the Market and Use of Certain Dangerous Substances, Preparations and Articles”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed)
- **“Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Compilation and Distribution of Safety Data Sheets Related to Dangerous Substances and Preparations “**(OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures “**(OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Restriction and Prohibition of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 21 November 2014, #29182) (name has changed, and some articles have been added)
- **“Regulation on the Attachment and Use of the ‘CE’ Conformity Mark to the Product,”** (Council of Ministers Decision, 15 November 2001, #2001/3530) (repealed) replaced by **“Regulation on ‘CE’ Mark”** (OJ 23 February 2012, #28213, Council of Ministries Decision 2011/2588)
- **“Regulation on Market Surveillance and Inspection of Products”** (decree of the Council of Ministers (13 November 2001, #2001/3529) (repealed)
- **“Regulation on Market Surveillance and Inspection of Ministry of Customs and Trade”** (OJ 12 June 2014, #29028)
- **“Communiqué on the Manufacture, Import, Market Supervision and Inspection of Tampons, Hygienic Pads, Nursing Pads, Diapers and Similar Products and Notification Essentials”** on Official Journal on 31 March 2013 #28807, repealed on OJ on 21 December 2017 #30277).
- **“Communiqué on Import Control of Certain User Products Controlled by Ministry of Customs and Trade (Product safety and Control: 2018/12)”** (OJ 30 December 2017, #30286.2)
- **“Communiqué on Amount and Detection of N-nitrosamines and N-nitro sable Substances in Elastomer or Rubber Feeding Bottle Teats and Soothers “**(OJ 31 October 2013, #28807)
- **“Communiqué on Conformity Assessment in Certain Consumer Products”** (OJ 3 May 2016, #29701)
- **“Law on cosmetics”** (OJ 24 March 2005, #5324)
- **“Regulation on Cosmetics”** (OJ 23 May 2005, #25823, in conformity with EU Cosmetic Legislation Conseil Directive 76/768/EEC and Conseil Decision 96/335/EC, amended by OJ 15 July 2015, # 29417 including nanomaterials)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

In order to adopt REACH regulation in Turkey, the Market Surveillance and Inspection Coordination Board (PGD) decided on 17 June 2014 that the legislative studies for the **REACH Regulation 1907/2006 / EC on "Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals"** will be carried out, that the restrictions in this area should be regulated by the relevant PGD institutions and that an audit should be started as soon as possible until the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization starts the regulations. In this context, with the purpose of protecting consumers' health and safety by eliminating the chemical risks to consumers and detecting dangerous chemicals in some textile and shoe products exported to and from abroad, **"Draft Communiqué for Surveillance and Supervision of Market for Dangerous Chemical Substance Content of Some Consumer Products"** was prepared and presented to the information of the public. Azo-dyes, phthalates (DEFP, DBP, BBP, DINP, DIDP, DNOP), flame retardants (TEPA, PBBs, TRIS), DMF (limited to 0.1 mg/kg), Chrome IV (limited to 3 mg/kg), lead (limited to 100 mg/kg in plastic and metal coatings), Cadmium (limited to 0.01% of the plastic material in mass in packaging materials), Organostannic compounds (DOT) (limited to 0.01% in mass in products in contact with skin like hygienic pads, diapers), cancerogenic and allergen dyes (in textile, leather products, toys, furniture), Polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (limited to 1 mg/kg BaP or limited to 10 mg/kg of all listed PAHs in plastic and rubber parts of children toys) were listed. The Communiqué was published on OJ on 14 January 2015 #29236. Then Turkish implementation of European Union's REACH has been published on 23 June 2017, the **"Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals"** (abbreviation KKDIK in Turkish) Nr 30105 by Ministry of Environment and Urbanization. The **"Communiqué for Surveillance and Supervision of Market for Dangerous Chemical Substance Content of Some Consumer Products"** was in force from 14 January 2015 (OJ #29236) to 21 December 2017 (OJ #30277).

"Communiqué on Conformity Assessment in Certain Consumer Products" (OJ 3 May 2016, #29701) is based on **"Law on Preparation and Implementation of Technical Legislation on Products"** (OJ 29 June 2001, #4703), **"Regulation on Market Surveillance and Inspection of Products"** entered in force by decree of the Council of Ministers (13 November 2001, #2001/3529) named **"Regulation on Market Surveillance and Inspection of Ministry of Customs and Trade"** (OJ 12 June 2014, #29028). It regulates standards for soother, feeding bottle, feeding bottle teat, sippy cup or baby training cup, sippy cup or baby training cup teat and similar products as well as manual tooth brushes, brush head and interface of electrically or battery-operated toothbrushes in oral hygiene given in TS EN and TS EN ISO, repealing the previous related communiqués.

"Regulation on Cosmetics" (OJ 23 May 2005, #25823), in conformity with EU Cosmetic Legislation Conseil Directive 76/768/EEC and Conseil Decision 96/335/EC, has been amended by OJ 15 July 2015, # 29417 including nanomaterials, Declaration Sheet for Cosmetic with Nanomaterial, prohibition of use of several chemicals such as DEGE, addition of potassium hydroxide as peeler and titanium oxide and zinc oxide as UV filtration agent in order to comply with updated EU Directives, all prohibited, limited, allowed substances are given by chemical identification name, CAS no and EC No in the related lists in Annexes.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

There is not yet any regulation on cotton buds in Turkey.

There is not yet any regulation on limiting microplastics in Turkey.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

General Overview:

Turkey is on the way to develop more effective waste management strategies. It is aimed to set up a waste management system in Turkey acting in accordance with the related national legislation and EU legislation, covering the establishment of necessary waste treatment facilities (pre-treatment facilities and landfills) and transfer stations, reduction of the amount of waste, ensuring recycling and reuse, and reducing the waste transportation costs (MoEU, 2012). As a first step to achieve these objectives, studies are being carried out across Turkey. Waste management plans involving details on the collection process have been prepared by municipalities since 2008. By the end of 2011, 283 packaging waste management plants are approved by the MoEU.

Most of the EU waste management directives have also been transposed into Turkey's national legislation.

The fields of authority and responsibility of the existing institutions still result in overlapping powers. Effective coordination and cooperation among relevant institutions need to be set stronger to enable the operability of the system. Governmental financing support and adequate knowledge and equipment are necessary to set up a sound waste management system country wide. Although it is a legal obligation and there are international commitments in this regard, the first "National Waste Management Strategy" paper of Turkey has been prepared for 2008-2012 and then related regional and local waste management plans have been prepared in further years.

One of the most problematic areas in Turkey in terms of harmonization with EU is the environment, which is one of the most comprehensive fields of EU Acquis. Waste management, which is necessary for harmonization with environmental Acquis, is among the costly fields. With a view to harmonizing with the EU Acquis in this field, several projects have been conducted with the technical and financial support of EU. Major steps have been taken within the framework of these projects in terms of harmonization of Turkey's legislation both with EU Acquis and international standards and in terms of the establishment and planning of the necessary actions to be taken within mentioned process. The work in this regard is progressing steadily.

The main problem in İstanbul during waste collection from source is the street collectors which take the MSW from municipal containers and sell the recyclable wastes to unregistered waste traders, this fact disables the follow-up of some part of the MSW, rising informal economy and causing lack of actual recycling data. These informal street collectors damage also municipal collecting containers for solid waste and recyclable waste.

Waste Management Plan is prepared and used in all institutions; planning, method and results are reported to related administrations.

The web application "Integrated Waste Information System" of the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization is used for entering, checking, approving, and monitoring waste management data by municipalities, licensed companies, authorized institutions, and ministry. In 2018 the application has been updated to integrate all administrative

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

procedure in the same application, so that paper-based national waste transport forms are no more required due to digital processing.

As the main source of MSW is the citizen, municipalities work with authorised institutions and licensed companies to raise public environmental awareness organizing campaigns, contests, formation classes and visits to dwellings, schools, and workplaces, promoting environment-friendly shopping bags, accessories, and printed materials. As a result, quantity of collected recyclable waste is augmenting.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.4.1 Municipal and Regional overview

The authority and responsibilities of municipalities are mentioned in “**Municipal Law**” and “**Metropolitan Municipality Law.**”

According to the **Metropolitan Municipality Law** (OJ 10 July 2004, #5216) and the **Municipality Law** (OJ 3 July 2005, #5393), sole responsibility for the management of municipal waste falls on the municipalities. They are responsible for providing all services regarding collection, transportation, separation, recycling, disposal, and storage of solid wastes, or to appoint others to provide these services. Nevertheless, while fulfilling their duties in collecting and transporting the solid waste, they do not show the required level of activity and attention in solid municipal waste management. This situation has been improving by newly adopted management perspectives.

“**Regulation on Controlled Landfill of Wastes**” (published on OJ 26 March 2010, #27533, amended on OJ 11 March 2015, #29292) has defined the target amount of biodegradable wastes to be landfilled taking as reference the total biodegradable waste amount in weight of year 2005, so that it shall be diminished to 75% in 2020, to 50% in 2023, and to 75% in 2030. The Ministry of Environment prepared the national strategy in no more than two years after that the regulation entered in force, to define the required measures by recycling, composting, biogas production or energy/material recovery methods.

Waste management, which is necessary for harmonization with environmental Acquis, is among the costly fields. In Istanbul, district municipalities provide collecting and transport of MSW and the Metropolitan Municipality is dealing with the municipal solid waste in controlled landfill areas and biogas plants, special wastes (medical, hazardous etc) are treated in waste removal plants of the metropolitan municipality or in other licensed plants. In general, licensed companies are serving in district municipalities for MSW and packaging waste for collecting, transportation and separation. Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality has its own company.

The legislation gives opportunity to municipalities to organize under the framework of union of municipalities and share the responsibility with members dealing with solid waste management and packaging waste management.

“**Regulation of Control of Packaging Waste**” regulates the essentials and principles of reducing the amount of packaging waste going to landfill and includes all materials such as, plastics, metals, glass, paper/cardboard, and composites. It introduced specific recovery targets for all packaging regardless of whether it is domestic or industrial. Municipalities are responsible for providing all services regarding increasing public environmental awareness and engagement, collection, transportation, separation, recycling, disposal, and storage of solid wastes, or to appoint others to provide these services.

Municipalities work with authorized authorities such as ÇEVKO, PAGÇEV, TAP that supply necessary waste specific collecting material, booklets, education classes, take technical and administrative support to prepare and carry out waste management plan.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Municipalities prepare “Packaging Waste Management Plan” with authorized institution and representative of the licensed companies, defining and describing the methodology, tools, licensed company, program about collection of packaging waste separately at source, pick up, transportation, separation, recycling, storage of packaging waste. The plan is presented to MoEU for approval by the municipality. The plan consists of 5 parts: Contact information, Present situation of the region, implementation plan, monitoring and evaluation, annexes.

8.4.2 Legislation history

Figure 29: Legislation history of main Turkish laws regarding PPW

- “**Law on Public Health**” (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593)
- Permanent Board of Consultants for Environmental Problems, in the early 1970s
- Environment Organization attached to the Prime Minister’s office in 1978
- General Directorate of Environment attached to the Prime Minister’s office in 1984
- Under secretariat of Environment in 1989
- “**Environment Law**” was passed in **1983** (no 2872)
- **Ministry of Environment** was established in **1991** by government Decree no. 443
- “**National Environmental Action Plan (NEAP)**” prepared in 1995, put into effect in 1998
- “**National Solid Waste Disposal Master Plan**” in 8th Five Year Development Plan (2001-2005)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **“Regulation on General Principles of Waste Management”** (OJ 5 July 2008, #2697)
- **“National Waste Management Strategy and Action Plan (NWMSAP)”** prepared in the framework of Turkey’s **10th Five Year Development Plan** of 2014-2018
- **“Zero Waste”** strategy has been started in September 2017 in **NWMSAP** covering years from 2014 to 2023
- **“Regulation on Waste Management”** (OJ 2 April 2015, #29314)
- **Metropolitan Municipality Law** (OJ 10 July 2004, #5216)
- **Municipality Law** (OJ 3 July 2005, #5393)
- **“Regulation of Control of Packaging Waste”** (published on OJ 25777, 05 April 2007), the marking of packaging during production was defined on voluntariness basis, access, and submission to ministry through web system was started, heavy metal concentration to be controlled by marketers, marketers had the right to be represented by authorized bodies
- the latest **Regulation on Packaging Waste Control** (“Regulation”) was published in Official Journal number 30283 on 27 December 2017, entering effect on 1 January 2018. Free plastic bags will be banned from the beginning of 2019 and packaging used in the Turkish market must be at least partially made from recycled materials.
- **“Law on Veterinary Services, Plant Health, Food and Feed”** (OJ 11 June 2010, #5996)
- **“Regulation on Turkish Food Codex”** (OJ 16 November 1997, #23172)
- **Law on Preparation and Implementation of Technical Legislation on Products”** (OJ 29 June 2001, #4703)
- **“Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017, it will still be in force until 31.12.2023) helping to distinct the waste category and determine the prevention and intervention method
- **“Communiqué on Amount and Detection of N-nitrosamines and N-nitrosable Substances in Elastomer or Rubber Feeding Bottle Teats and Soothers”** (OJ 31 October 2013, #28807) prohibited N-nitrosamines in baby teat and soothers
- **“Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals”** (abbreviation KKDİK in Turkish) Nr 30105, 23 June 2017) to implement REACH in Turkey. It repealed several regulations
- **“Communiqué on Plastic Materials and Articles in Contact with Food in Turkish Food Codex”** by Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs (OJ 10 June 2011, #27960, Com. #2011/29), changed the former communiqué banning the use of 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl) propane (**BPA**) (ref #13480) in producing polycarbonate materials and articles used by baby consumers such as **baby feeding bottle**.

8.4.3 Key Policy Measures in Force

8.4.3.1 Environmental Law

The **Environmental Law** numbered 2872 (OJ 11 August 1983, #18132) describes all the pollution and waste type definitions, authority and responsibilities of the citizen and

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

manufacturers as waste producers, restrictions, penal sanctions, authority, and responsibilities of the ministry of environment, metropolitan municipalities, and local municipalities.

It forbids to give any kind of waste and residual to receiving environment directly or indirectly, storing, moving, removing or by other similar actions realized in a manner harmful to the environment contrary to the standards and methods determined in the related regulations in article 8. The article 11 states the principle as the production and recovery of wastes and the prevention or reduction of wastes, as well as the collection of waste at the source of the recoverable wastes. Principles for the preparation of waste management plans shall be regulated by a regulation to be issued by the Ministry. Wastes that are not recoverable are disposed of by appropriate methods determined by the regulations. Waste producers shall take measures to minimize their waste by means of appropriate methods and technologies. Real and / or legal persons who wish to establish and operate waste recycling, reusing and disposal facilities are obliged to obtain license from the Ministry by registering with the related institutions in accordance with the principles determined by the regulation, the product standard, the suitability of the sale of their products and the inspection on the market. Institutions or organizations engaged in waste transportation and / or collection works must obtain a license from the Ministry, except for municipal wastes. Institutions and establishments engaged in the transportation and collection of domestic wastes are registered in the Ministry. If the municipalities establish service unions for wastewater treatment, waste disposal and waste recovery facilities, technical and financial assistance shall be provided to these service unions in the fields of research, studies, and projects. Manufacturers, importers, and traders who are liable to the marketplace for their responsibilities shall gather to form associations with legal personality in order to collect, transport, recover, recycle and dispose the wastes resulting at end-of-life of their products and to absorb necessary expenses, to fulfil the training under the coordination of the Ministry.

Article 20 item b) regulates the related administrative fines for those who do not establish or operate the necessary waste collection, pre-treatment, treatment, or removal facility. Article 20 item r) regulates the administrative fine for those who collect, moves, transport, store or temporarily store, recycle, regain, reuse, or dispose the waste in a way contrary to the prohibitions or limitations.

8.4.3.2 Metropolitan Municipality Law and Municipality Law

According to the **Metropolitan Municipality Law** (OJ 10 July 2004, #5216) and the **Municipality Law** (OJ 3 July 2005, #5393), sole responsibility for the management of municipal waste falls on the municipalities. They are responsible for providing all services regarding collection, transportation, separation, recycling, disposal, and storage of solid wastes, or to appoint others to provide these services. Nevertheless, while fulfilling their duties in collecting and transporting the solid waste, they do not show the required level of activity and attention in solid municipal waste management. This situation has been improving by newly adopted management perspectives.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.4.3.3 Regulation of Control of Packaging Waste

"Regulation of Control of Packaging Waste" (OJ 05 April 2007, #25777) has the main changes for marketers and producers such as: the definition of packaging explained by giving examples, wastes occurring during production were excluded of the definition, the labelling of packaging during production was defined on voluntariness basis, access and submission to ministry through web system was started, heavy metal concentration to be controlled by marketers, marketers had the right to be represented by authorized bodies. Labelling become mandatory in Turkey with the Regulation published in 2005 ordering to terminate the marking until 1st January of 2007.

The regulation was amended in 2011. The technical and administrative standards about production of packing that have certain qualities, prevention of formation of packing wastes, reutilization of the amount of dismissible packing waste, reduction of packing wastes by recycling, objectives for the recycling and recovery of packing wastes on yearly basis, separate collection at the source, carrying and decomposition are defined. The principle of "extended producer liability" is used as the basis and thus the liability is on the businesses that put packed products on the market. Businesses are liable to inform the kind and amount of packing they put on market through Packing Information System and ensure that these packing are collected for recycle and reutilization. Moreover, it is the responsibility of the businesses to absorb the expenses of recycling and reutilization. Furthermore, technically waste administration is left to municipalities though market launchers are responsible from the financial administration of packing wastes. The packing producers' liabilities, indicates that the first liability of the packing producer is "as part of the extended producer liability, to produce, as from the packing design phase, with the minimum waste production after the manufacture and usage, with the easiest recycling and recovery, with the most economical and the least environmentally harmful manner. Alongside the Authorized Institutions' and the market launchers', which apply the deposit system, "supply oriented" packing waste recycling objective, it is been designated non-supply-oriented recycling and recovery objective throughout the country.

The latest **Regulation on Packaging Waste Control** ("Regulation") published in Official Journal number 30283 on 27 December 2017, entering into effect on 1 January 2018 bans delivery of free plastic bags in market from the beginning of 2019 and packaging used in the Turkish market must be at least partially made from recycled materials. Significant changes introduced by the Regulation include:

- From 1 January 2019, sales points (including distant sales) will be prohibited from giving out plastic bags to users or consumers, free of charge.
- Producers of plastic, paper, board, glass, and metal packages which will be supplied to the domestic market must now at least partially use:
 - Packaging waste collected within Turkey, or
 - Recycled packaging waste gathered from such waste.
- At least 80% of recycling targets must now be met from non-industrial sources.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- The due date for submitting annual notifications about packaging materials produced, imported, exported, supplied and/or packages of imported goods, has moved from February to March.
- Municipalities' responsibilities for collecting packaging waste are now outlined more clearly.
- Residential sites with 100 or more houses must now have storage equipment for packaging wastes which follows the municipality's collection system.
- A colour coding system is introduced for bins used to collect packaging waste:
 - Blue for paper.
 - Yellow for plastics.
 - Grey for metals.
- The Packaging Commission will now hold a meeting once per year.
- Each municipality's vehicle fleet for collecting domestic waste must now include at least 20% vehicles capable of collecting packaging waste.
- Manufacturers of packaging of plastic, paper, board, glass, or metal must use in packaging the materials collected inland or recycled from these collected materials to be launched inland in following ratios.

Compulsory use rates (%)				
Years	Plastic	Paper, cardboard	Glass	Metal
2018	4	25	12	10
2019	6	30	15	15
2020 and over	8	35	20	20

- The target recycling quotas are defined in 3 phases:
 - The authorized institutions/market launchers have to realize the following recycling ratios of their packaging wastes from 2005 to 2018:

Rates of the package aimed to be recovered according to materials and years (%)					
Years	Glass	Plastic	Metal	Paper, cardboard	Wood
2005	32	32	30	20	-
2006	33	33	33	30	-
2007	35	35	35	35	-

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

2008	35	35	35	35	-
2009	36	36	36	36	-
2010	37	37	37	37	-
2011	38	38	38	38	-
2012	40	40	40	40	-
2013	42	42	42	42	5
2014	44	44	44	44	5
2015	48	48	48	48	5
2016	52	52	52	52	7
2017	54	54	54	54	9

- i. The authorized institutions and market launchers who use deposit/refund system have to realize at least the following recycling ratios based on materials from 2018:

Recovery rates based on materials (%) (preparation to reuse included)					
Years	Glass	Plastic	Metal	Paper, cardboard	Wood
2018	54	54	54	54	11
2019	54	54	54	54	13
2020 onwards	60	55	55	60	15

- ii. The Ministry, together with all the parties responsible for packaging waste management, will take the necessary precautions to ensure that the total recycling and recovery targets can be achieved in 2018, regardless of the material type:

Years	Total recovery rate (%)	Total recycling rate (%)
2018	56	54
2019	58	54
2020 onwards	60	55

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

It is obligatory that at least 80% of the targets stated in the second category, except wood, will be supplied from other packaging wastes except for those originating from the industrial enterprises collected by the separate collection system. Work for separate collection of packaging waste at the source will be carried out in cooperation with the municipalities and within the scope of packaging waste management plans of them.

To ensure recycling / recovery objectives of composite packaging; the composite package will be classified as the material present in its unit composition constituting the maximum amount by weight.

8.4.3.4 Regulation on Turkish Food Codex

The “**Regulation on Turkish Food Codex,**” article 17 (1) item b) describes the properties of packaging material as: “Pressed and imprinted papers, recycled papers and plastics that are not produced as food packaging material shall not be used as food packaging material. However, production burrs and edge wastes are not treated as recycled plastics and can be used without leaving the facility, as part of production, within the framework of good production practices and in accordance with the provisions of the relevant legislation. Annex 36A about technical specifications of colorants in plastics and Annex 36B about colorants that may be used in plastics in specific conditions were repealed and article 22 is amended as:

“Use of plastic-based materials and articles in contact with food shall comply with the following principles:

- a) Plastics to be in contact with food shall be composed of high molecular weight polymers and shall not have any chemical interaction with food. The number of monomers that can be absorbed into the structure of the material and the material coming into contact with the food must conform to the criteria specified in the technical specifications of the plastics.
- b) Adding additives during production to the plastics that will be in touch with food such as plasticizer, antioxidant, stabilizer, emulgator, glazing, catalyser; the amount shall be in a level that will not lead to change quality of foodstuff and cause any toxic effect.
- c) Plastic food contact materials and packages shall not absorb foodstuff, shall not leak the food, age, shall not change taste, odour, or colour, shall have needed physical and mechanical properties for carrying and storing.
- d) Plastics used as food packaging shall be used only once. However, the procedures and principles regarding the reuse of plastic materials and articles after reconstruction of hygienic conditions without altering their structure and shape shall be regulated by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs.
- e) Plastics or other materials to contact with food shall have the quality defined in this section in case the products are used in coating by methods such as gluing, extrusion, coating, impregnation or in lamination and contain plastic and resin lamination.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- f) Colorants to be used in plastics in contact with food shall not migrate in food and not contain toxic material.
- g) Colorants shall have high purity and follow the specifications below;
- 1) In colorants, amount of metals and metalloids dissolved in 0.1 M HCl shall not exceed the limits given below:

Metal/Metalloid	Quantity (max)
Lead	0.01%
Arsenic	0.01%
Chromium	0.1%
Antimony	0.05%
Mercury	0.005%
Cadmium	0.01%
Selenium	0.01%
Barium	0.01%

- 2) Unsulfurated primer aromatic amine content dissolved in 1 M HCl, calculated in form of aniline shall not exceed 500 mg/kg. Each or total of benzidine, betanaftilamine and 4-aminobipheniline shall not exceed 10 mg/kg.
- 3) Total quantity of sulfonated aromatic amine calculated in form of aniline sulfonic acid shall not exceed 500 mg/kg.
- 4) Toluene extract of carbon black shall not exceed 0.15%.
- 5) Quantity of phenyls calculated in form of decachlorobiphenyl must not exceed 25 mg/kg.
- h) Migration of chemical materials in structure of plastics with food-like dissolvent shall not exceed 60 mg/kg or 10 mg/dm². Migration and extraction works shall be realized in the highest temperatures and the longest periods under the normal usage conditions with food in their own categories.
- i) Food-contact plastic materials shall have a structure that is not easily broken, torn, and deformed.

“**Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials in Contact with Food**” regulates the active and smart materials and articles, the colorants that can be used in paper, metal, glass, and plastic materials. In its annex 6, colorants in plastic materials and articles in touch with food are described as in the article 22 of “**Regulation on Turkish Food Codex**”. This regulation defines the packaging, filling, and labelling.

The “**Communiqué on Food-Contact Active and Smart Materials and Articles of Turkish Food Codex**” (OJ 5 April 2018, # 30382) defines additional specifications for food-contact active and smart materials and articles. It is based on “**Regulation on Materials in Contact with Food in Turkish Food Codex**.”

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The amendment made in the “**Communiqué on Plastic Materials and Articles in Contact with Food in Turkish Food Codex**” by Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs (OJ 10 June 2011, #27960, Com. #2011/29), changed the former communiqué banning the use of 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl) propane (**BPA**) (ref #13480) in producing polycarbonate materials and articles used by baby consumers such as **baby feeding bottle**, and production, importing and selling in premises was banned 1 month from the communiqué.

Migration limits were regulated in the “**Communiqué on Plastic Materials and Articles in Contact with Food in Turkish Food Codex**” (OJ 17 July 2013, #28710, Com. #2013/34) with rules about plastic materials and articles made completely of plastic and currently, ex ante or maybe in touch with food, plastic materials and articles multi-layered connected by gluing or in another way, plastic materials and articles printed or coated by previous types of plastics, plastic layers or plastic coatings in the tap, cover or layers on the cover or closure in plastic formed of two or more layers of different materials, plastic materials and layers in the multi-material multilayer structure. It defines the limitation in composition of plastic materials and articles with migration test procedure.

8.4.3.5 Regulation on Water Intended for Human Consumption

“**Regulation on Water Intended for Human Consumption**” (OJ 17 February 2005, #25730, amended by OJ 31 July 2009, #2730, OJ 7 March 2013, #28580 and OJ 11 April 2014, #28969, OJ 20 October 2016, #29863) prepared correspondingly to Conseil Directive 98/83/EC, Conseil Directive on 16 May 2003 numbered 2003/40/EC and EU Commission Regulation 115/2010, implemented by Public Health Agency under Ministry of Health defines technical and administrative issues on serving healthy potable water.

In the regulation, vessels used for filling water are evaluated in two groups as returnable and non-returnable.

‘Returnable vessel’ is defined as vessel used more than one time in filling spring water or potable water, made of glass, metal, chrome-nickel, polycarbonate etc, not interfering with water; and ‘non-returnable vessel’ is defined as vessels that shall not be used more than once filling water, made of PET, glass, metal, chrome-nickel etc. In case the packaging vessel is not made of glass, the information and documents about the use and manufacture of this vessel and that it is fit health wise shall be presented to the ministry and get authorized.

a) The returnable vessels shall be washable with hot water (not less than 55-70 °C) and suitable cleaning material, fully automatic, and shall not undergo any deformation after washing. Detector etc system shall control that the quality of the vessel has not changed. These vessels shall not be used more than 5 years or 75 times. Detection of the number of filling shall be carried out by an electronic tracking system supplied by the exploiter; the principles on this system shall be determinate by the public health agency. Returnable polycarbonate vessels shall have the name of water and production date of the vessel printed in relief on the neck or body of the vessel, and trade name, registered emblem, or logo. No other water shall be filled in these vessels. The shelf life of the waters offered for sale in these vessels cannot exceed three months.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

b) The non-returnable vessels: In case that vessels made of a material other than glass and metal are used in filling water, these vessels shall be produced automatically in related units of the manufacturing workshop from raw material and from perform. Before filling, the vessels shall be cleaned with pressurized water or air, then put into automatic filling system. Filling the water, in addition to vessels made of glass, polyethylene (PET) and polyvinylchloride (PVC), it can be used non-returnable packages made automatically of aluminium foil.

Bottle caps on water vessels shall have be authorized by the Ministry and have the following properties: Caps shall be made of plastic or metal which do not interfere with water and do not harm human health; they shall be closed in automatic cloaking machine in manufacturing facility so that they cannot be open without tearing or deforming. Filling water in vessels in form of glassware, suitable caps to completely cover the cup mouth without using glue are used. These caps shall have an opening extension for easy opening. The caps are kept under hygienic conditions in the facility. Use of used or deformed caps is prohibited.

8.4.3.6 Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food

“**Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food**” (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382) is the newest regulation on FCMs. The new regulation aligns the rules on food contact materials with Regulation (EC) no 1935/2004. In addition, it sets the procedure for the authorization of the substances that are used in the food contact materials and articles. It applies to 1) materials and articles including active and smart materials, a) that are intended to be in contact with food, b) that are produced to be in contact with food, c) that will probably get in contact with food or that its ingredients might migrate to the food in the normal or predicted use conditions, 2) materials and articles in contact with water serving to individual consumption. It does not apply to materials and articles used to coating or storing foods like cheese, prepared meat products or fruits, constituting a part of the food itself and being consumed with the food, fixed water supply units for personal or general use and materials supplied antequely.

Operators have to ensure compliance with this regulation by 31st Dec 2018 or 31st Dec 2019 for some exceptions.

This legislation was prepared and adopted according to the Commission Regulation numbered 10/2011/EU “Commission Regulation on Plastic Materials and Articles” and Conseil Directive numbered 85/572/EEC on the “List of food simulants used in migration test of components of the plastic materials and articles in contact with food”, in the framework of harmonization with EU legislation.

8.4.3.7 Communiqué on the Principles and Procedures Related to Standard Practices That Must Be Complied within the Wholesale and Retail Trade of Vegetables and Fruits

“**Communiqué on the Principles and Procedures Related to Standard Practices That Must Be Complied within the Wholesale and Retail Trade of Vegetables and Fruits**” (OJ 3 October 2017, #30199) regulates the packaging, transporting, storing and offer for retail sale of goods by the Ministry of Customs and Trade. ‘Packaging’ is defined as transport containers

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

made of paper, plastic, wood, metal, or a combination of these materials, which hold together the goods contained therein during the transfer process from manufacturer to customer, which best keep the structure and shape of the goods and which facilitate the loading and unloading, transport and storage. 'Single use packaging' is defined as the packaging made of wood or paper or paper-based material manufactured for sole use and used only once. 'Reusable packaging' is defined as packaging made of plastic material and used several times. The Communiqué orders the use of single use packaging in suitable dimensions to fit in pallets of (80x120) cm, and the use of reusable packaging in dimensions of (60x40) cm, (40x30) cm and (30x20) cm to fit in pallets of (80x120) cm. Reusable packaging shall be modular and collapsible and shall be disinfected after each use in compliance with food safety. Full packaging shall weigh 30 kg. In matters not covered by this Communiqué on the packaging of goods, the Turkish Standards Institute relevant standards/criteria apply.

8.4.3.8 Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals

"Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals" (abbreviation KKDİK in Turkish) Nr 30105 by Ministry of Environment and Urbanization. The **"Communiqué for Surveillance and Supervision of Market for Dangerous Chemical Substance Content of Some Consumer Products"** was in force from 14 January 2015 (OJ #29236) to 21 December 2017 (OJ #30277).

It repealed following regulations:

- **CICR (Chemical Inventory and Control Regulation 27092)** which was published on the date 26 December 2008, #27092. The substances which are restricted were previously covered by the **"Regulation on Restriction Regarding to Manufacture, placing on the Market and Use of Certain Hazardous Substances, Preparations and Articles"**.
- After the publication of KKDİK, this regulation will also be repealed but this took place after 6 months from the date of publication which is 23 December 2017. After 23.12.2017 Annex XIV and XVII of the KKDİK have been taking over the provisions relating to restriction, authorization of some substances.
- Annex XIV has been a blank Annex as of the date of publication. To manage the **procedural** bureaucracy of amending the regulation, the Competent Authority (CA) had preferred to publish the **"List of substances subject to authorization"** on the web site of the Competent Authority'. This will let the CA to update the Annex XIV without any delay and obligation to procedure to follow which the regulatory amendments are needed.
- Annex XVII which is related to the **"Restrictions on the Manufacture, placing on the Market and Use of Certain Dangerous Substances, Preparations and Articles"** has several entries and these have been coming into force across several dates. Further in-depth briefings will be needed.
- Another regulation that is to be repealed by the KKDİK is the **"Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous substances and Mixtures"** (29204) published on 13

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

December 2014. Indeed, this is the youngest regulation repealed by KKDİK, but enforcement of that repeal is also quite late relatively. The existing Regulation on SDS (No: 29204) will still be in force until 31.12.2023.

- Article 27 of KKDİK which sets out the provisions regarding the compilation and distribution of the SDS, has been in force as of 23.12.2017. After 23.12.2017 an SDS may be compiled in accordance with the KKDİK regulation, or with 29204. In practice, however, preparing a SDS as per KKDİK will not be possible, as the Chemical Safety Assessors who must compile the SDS in accordance with KKDİK will not be available as of that date. The SDS's that are compiled in accordance with 29204 will be deemed as compliant until 31.12.2023. Until sufficient numbers of Safety Assessors, for whom the general principles and provisions are set out in Annex XVIII of KKDİK, have been trained and are available, the SDS's will need to be compiled in accordance with 29204.
- Absorbent hygiene products are regulated by the "**Communiqué on the Manufacture, Import, Market Supervision and Inspection of Tampons, Hygienic Pads, Nursing Pads, Diapers and Similar Products and Notification Essentials**" on Official Journal on 31 March 2013 #28807, and then repealed by the communiqué on OJ on 21 December 2017 #30277.
- "**Communiqué on Import Control of Certain User Products Controlled by Ministry of Customs and Trade (Product safety and Control: 2018/12)**" (OJ 30 December 2017, #30286.2) regulates several procedures and principles for communiqués including a specific measure within the "**Communiqué on Amount and Detection of N-nitrosamines and N-nitro sable Substances in Elastomer or Rubber Feeding Bottle Teats and Soothers**" (OJ 31 October 2013, #28807) having the same limits as in the Commission Directive 93/11/EEC of 15 March 1993.

In order to comply with KKDİK, it requires pre-registration and registration respectively for the substances that are manufactured or placed on the market (in other words imported) in Turkey either on their own or in mixtures or in articles with an intended release which are equal to or above 1 mta.

Different from the EU REACH regulation, KKDİK does not set out separate pre-registration and registration deadlines depending on the classification of the substance or the annual tonnage band.

Thus:

- All pre-registrations should be submitted before 31.12.2020.
- All registrations must be completed between 31.12.2020 - 31.12.2023.
- After 31.12.2023, substances either on their own, in mixtures or in articles that are equal to or above 1 mta, cannot be manufactured or placed on the market if they are not registered in accordance with the relevant provisions of KKDİK.
- There is the need for an Only Representative (OR) in accordance with Article 9 of KKDİK for companies that do not have a Legal Entity in Turkey. One of the first actions for the

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

global chemical industry should be to find a reliable OR that has a Legal Entity in Turkey. The companies who already have an appointed Only Representative in Turkey, for example to comply with SEA and/or CICR regulations can ask their OR to manage their responsibilities under KKDIK. The other global manufacturers who have not yet appointed an OR would be advised to start seeking one.

- The initial term of KKDIK is from 23.12.2017 (the first date that most of the provisions of KKDIK get in force) to 31.12.2020. Activity during this time will likely be mostly based on finding and appointing an OR, identification of the substances to pre-register and submitting the pre-registrations via the OR.
- The more critical term will be between 1.1.2021 and 31.12.2023 where more complex tasks such as data sharing, dossier compilation and registration will take place. Also, the official fees for registration will be another subject of this critical term on the top of the LoA costs or data related costs that the registrants will be facing.

8.4.4 Regional and municipal Organs and Systems for the Collection and Recycling of Plastic packages

Institutions Authorized by the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization:

1. **LASDER** (Rubber Industries Association); has been established to fulfil the responsibilities related to the transportation, temporary storage, recovery and disposal of finished tires within the scope of the "**Regulation on the Control of the End-of-life Tires**" published in the Official Journal dated 25.11.2006 and numbered 26357 and it serves as an authorized body by the Ministry.
2. **TAP** (Portable Battery Manufacturers and Importers Association); was established to fulfil the responsibilities related to the collection and disposal of waste batteries within the scope of the "**Regulation on the Control of Waste Batteries and Accumulators**" published in the Official Journal dated 31.08.2004 and numbered 25569, and serves as an authorized body by the Ministry.
3. **AKÜDER** (Accumulator Producer and Recycling Industry Association); has been established to fulfil the responsibilities related to collection, transport, recovery and disposal of waste accumulators within the scope of the "**Regulation on the Control of Waste Batteries and Accumulators**" published in the Official Journal dated 31.08.2004 and numbered 25569, and serves as an authorized body by the Ministry.
4. **TÜMAKÜDER** (All Battery Importers and Manufacturers Association); has been established to fulfil the responsibilities related to collection, transport, recovery and disposal of waste accumulators within the scope of the "**Regulation on the Control of Waste Batteries and Accumulators**" published in the Official Journal dated 31.08.2004 and numbered 25569, and serves as an authorized body by the Ministry.
5. **PETDER** (Petroleum Industry Association); has been established to fulfil its responsibilities related to "collection, transport, recovery and disposal" of "collection of waste engine oils" within the scope of the "**Waste Oil Control Regulation**" published

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

in the Official Journal dated 30.07.2008 and numbered 26952 and is serving as an authorized body by the Ministry.

6. **ÇEVKO** (Environmental Protection and Packaging Waste Valorisation Foundation Economic Enterprise); was established in order to fulfil the responsibilities of packaging businesses in the field of packaging waste management under the "**Packaging Waste Control Regulation**" published in the Official Journal dated 24.08.2011 and numbered 28035 and is authorized by the Ministry.
7. **TÜKÇEV** (Consumer and Environmental Education Foundation Economic Business); was established in order to fulfil the responsibilities of packaging businesses in the field of packaging waste management under the "**Packaging Waste Control Regulation**" published in the Official Journal dated 24.08.2011 and numbered 28035 and is authorized by the Ministry.
8. **PAGÇEV** (Turkish Plastic Industry Research and Development Foundation, Recycling Economic Enterprise); was established in order to fulfil the responsibilities of packaging businesses in the field of packaging waste management under the "**Packaging Waste Control Regulation**" published in the Official Journal dated 24.08.2011 and numbered 28035 and is authorized by the Ministry.
9. **ELDAY** (Electrical and Electronic Recycling and Waste Management Association Economic Enterprise); was established with the aim of fulfilling its responsibilities regarding management of Refrigerators, Coolers, Air Conditioning Equipment, Large Appliances, Vending Machines and Television and Monitors groups put on the market within the scope of "**Regulation on the Control of Waste Electrical and Electronic Goods**" published in the Official Journal dated 22.05.2012 and numbered 28300 serving as an authorized organization.
10. **TÜBİSAD** (Association of Information Industrialists and Businessmen Economic Enterprise); in the scope of "**Regulation on the Control of Waste Electrical and Electronic Goods**" published in the Official Journal dated 22.05.2012 and numbered 28300, television and monitors were put on the market and authorized in the category of information and telecommunication and consumer equipment.
11. **AGİD** (Lighting Manufacturers' Association Economic Enterprise); has been commissioned as an authorized organization under the categories of lighting equipment's, small household appliances, electric and electronic appliances, toys, sports and entertainment equipment, monitoring and control appliances which are put on the market under the "**Regulation on the Control of Waste Electrical and Electronic Goods**" published in the Official Journal dated 22.05.2012 and numbered 28300.
12. **AGED** (Waste Paper and Recycling Businessmen Association); has been serving as an authorized body to fulfil the responsibilities of the market-oriented enterprises within the scope of "**Packaging Waste Control Regulation**" published in the Official Journal dated 24.08.2011 and number 28035.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Initiatives:

Important initiatives taken to improve MSW management have been found to promote better MSW management in Turkey.

ÇEVKO (Foundation for Protection of Environment and Valorisation of Packaging Wastes) is the pioneer in packaging waste management as a non-profit organisation dedicated to packaging waste recycling, has been established in 1991 with the initiative of 14 leading industrial companies in Turkey in order to contribute to establishment of a sustainable recycling system with the contribution and participation of local management and consumers for the economic and regular recycling of packaging wastes in Turkey. ÇEVKO foundation, having carried on activities about collection of packaging waste at source as a volunteer until 2005, has been authorized by the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization upon the enforcement of the regulation for the recovery of any type of packaging waste. With this authorization, ÇEVKO Foundation has been able to take over the responsibilities of industrial corporations launching packages and packaged products to the market. ÇEVKO Foundation performs the responsibility it has taken over from the marketer industrial corporations by means of acting in cooperation with local authorities and licensed collection – separation companies.

ÇEVKO Foundation carries out activities regarding communication, awareness-raising, and training for the performance of the liabilities it has assumed. The authorized organization develops activities about the separate collection of packaging waste at source in cooperation with municipal administrations and licensed companies on behalf of the packaging producers and economic operators which put packaging on to the market it is. By this, ÇEVKO Foundation fills a significant gap at the implementation stage of the regulation. ÇEVKO Foundation, having taken over the recovery responsibilities of the industry, carries out its activities on contractual basis with many economic operators. Such corporations include domestic or foreign ones active in Turkey as fillers, packaging producers, packing recyclers with private labels, big scale shopping malls and chain stores from food, consumption, medicine, chemistry, and oil, etc. sectors using glass, metal, plastic, paper, and composite packaging.

The activities of the waste management department are as follows:

- In order to reach the recovery targets, to execute contracts with collection-separation, recycling, and recovery plants with license/provisional license to which they are contracted or with the municipalities on behalf of the marketers it is and to monitor the activities carried out pursuant to such contract;
- To review the notifications and certifications made by the collection-separation, recycling, and recovery plants with license/provisional license by acting in cooperation with the municipalities for the separate collection of packaging waste at its source;
- to carry out informative activities within the scope of the present packaging waste management plan;

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- To follow up the packaging waste collected at the contracted municipalities and to give support in kind;
- To negotiate with collection-separation, recycling, and recovery plants with license/provisional license to create material capacity.

TUKCEV (Consumer and Environmental Education Foundation Economic Business) is the second authorised institution in Turkey which was authorised by the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization in 2010.

Ongoing initiatives towards improving the MSW management system in Turkey are present.

Packaging Commission: It is established as described in the Regulation on Control of Packaging Waste” to meet and evaluate the works and practices carried out in line with Regulation. Packaging Commission consists of authorized representatives of municipalities, manufacturers, packaging producers, merchants, licensed collection, sorting and recycling facilities, sales points, and other relevant sectors. The Commission covers all relevant parties of the packaging industry. This committee meets when necessary in the Presidency of the Ministry representative. The decisions taken by the Commission are of guiding status. It has the first meeting in 20 May 2009 and 10 sub-committees have been established related to problems issued during practices of the Regulation, evaluated EU directives and good practices in the world about recycling.

Türkiye Materials Marketplace

In 2015, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (the “EBRD” or the “Bank”) launched the Near Zero Waste (NØW) Programme aiming to catalyse a transformational change in Turkey’s waste management. It will carry out this by developing financing mechanisms to encourage early movers to develop waste minimisation investments in best available techniques in different waste streams and value chain links. The NØW Project gives technical assistance to support the implementation of Turkey’s integrated waste management action plan, to identify and develop waste minimisation initiatives by the private sector, and to develop awareness and knowledge initiatives supporting waste minimisation expansion throughout Turkey.

The EBRD is financing a sub-project under NØW called the Türkiye Materials Marketplace in Turkey. The Türkiye Materials Marketplace (“TMM”) is a cloud-based platform designed to facilitate cross-industry materials reuse among Turkish companies and communities. The project is based on a secure marketplace software platform through which project members will be invited to share materials data from their operations. With assistance from the project team, companies will then work collaboratively to identify, evaluate, and implement material reuse and valorisation opportunities which are crucial components of circular economy. This study has been planned within the policy dialogue activities of the TMM project under the NØW Programme.

Local Provincial Environmental Commission: Established according to Law of Environment, it consists of representatives of governmental organizations and trading and industrial chambers in the province and decides about environmental problems and practices such

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

as determining the fees for medical wastes, prohibiting or allowing certain work hours for building works or open area activities according to surrounding noise sensitive area etc. The commission meets regularly every month.

Union of Municipalities of Turkey: It was established in 1945 as a public interest association, with the Council of Ministers decision of 21 August 2002 dated and law No: 2002/4550, it has reached the status of local administrative authority which holds a public entity possess, administrative and financial autonomy. It has become a public legal entity who is the representative of all the municipalities in 2005, in compliance with the Article 20 of the Law No:5355 on Local Authorities Union as part of the Local Authorities Reform Process. It is established at country level and has the natural membership of all municipalities in Turkey carries out the following duties prescribed in Law no 5355 and Unions Statute:

- Organising training programs for mayors, council members and municipal personnel.
- Representing municipalities in presence of International and national authorities.
- Assisting municipalities in their development and provide guidance.
- To encourage the prevalence of good implementation examples and exchange of experience.
- Publishing books, bulletins and journal and such publications on the subjects within the scope of duties.
- Organizing seminars, workshop, panels, and technical visits about municipal work abroad or in country.
- Carrying out joint service projects with public institutions, universities and NGO's working in the field of municipal work.
- Giving technical support to municipalities in development technology and information.
- Cooperating and conducting joint projects with international institutions and their co-institutions in the country.
- Aiding the works of municipalities in the process of EU and assisting municipalities to benefit from EU grants and technical assistance.

The Environment and urbanization department prepared a report "Design, Selection of Place of Sanitary Landfill Sites and Rehabilitation of Wild Dumping Sites" in 2014.

Union of Municipalities of the Marmara Region: has been founded by the municipalities which are located on the shores of Marmara Sea, the Bosphorus and the Dardanelles to prevent the pollution of the sea, to protect the fishery products, to coordinate various municipal services - especially the initiatives with the tourism institutions - and to solve the current environmental problems. The scope of the Association is limited to the boundaries of the municipalities that are members of the Association.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The Association has 230-member municipalities including 11 central municipalities in Marmara. One of the most important objectives of the Union is to assist in local administrations and municipalities providing more efficient services to the public by developing the coordination and solidarity between the local administrations and municipalities. It has urban policy centre, migration policy centre, management development centre, urban technology and innovation centre, local government academy, disaster coordination and cooperation centre; it publishes reports and periodic magazines, it organizes training and ability development classes and events for municipal works.

Through educational programs, environmentally-oriented technical contacts, promotional programs and by multilateral collaborations, MMU supports the environmental efforts of the municipalities. It is important for MMU to act as a bridge between the municipalities and central government and to convey the local environment policies and environmental management strategies to the central government. On the other hand, in cooperation with the legislation directly related to the municipalities, efforts are made to achieve a common implementation; and evaluation is made by including different opinions and proposals for activating the implementation. The collected proposals are transferred to the central government and therefore, it is ensured that the municipalities actively take part in the regulations.

The Marmara Sea, which is the main issue for the foundation of MMU in 1975, is one of the top priority areas today. All stakeholders come together periodically with the Marmara Sea Symposiums to receive help from the interdisciplinary approach and the strength of acting together. Considering that the energy efficiency and efficient use of resources is also directly related to environmental management, the collaborations that are believed to increase the ability in this respect are taken part. The MMU Environment Platform brings together individuals from the member municipalities working in areas such as Environmental Protection and Control, Waste Management and Cleaning Services. The Platform aims to develop solutions to common problems with a holistic view, share experiences and the examples of good practice, raise awareness on the issue of a sustainable environment, and create a common ground of understanding between the central administration and the local administrations by sharing opinions and suggestions on legal regulations concerning the local administrations.

Environment Foundation of Turkey (EFT): is a non-governmental, non-profit, and volunteer organization which was founded on 1 February 1978, aiming to work to give everybody a cleaner, more organized, healthier, and favourable environment to live in, through doing research on environmental protection and development and organizing scientific meetings. While EFT's services keep going as research, publication and raising public awareness, published books by the foundation, which cover almost every aspect of the environment, constitute the groundwork of Turkish literature on environment.

EFT has published a total of 191 books so far. In 1978, when the term "environment" was poorly understood, EFT proposed establishment of the Prime Ministry Under secretariat of

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Environment to enable inclusion of the concept of environment within the body of the Government and showed a successful example of its efforts on “constructive influence on public and the government”.

After two years of its foundation, EFT started to establish the roots for the branch of environmental law which was little known in the country, published books on the subject and showed efforts on promoting and developing this new branch of law. EFT, then focused on involvement of the environment in the Constitution and preparing an environmental law draft. Because of its efforts from 1980 to 1982, the foundation played a vital role in the inclusion of Article 56 on the environment in the Constitution and enactment of Environment Law numbered 2872 in 1983. EFT, with an inclination toward inventorial work mentioned in the Fourth Five-Year Development Plan, in conclusion of a study which took over a year by a team of 33, by publishing the Environmental Profile of Turkey in 1981 became the first NGO in the world, which performed such a study. In the following years seven more editions were published. In 1988, with the support of the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), EFT commenced the research project on the “Comparison of EC and Turkish Environmental Legislation”; EFT compiled and published “Turkish Environmental Legislation” in a single volume. In 1989, EFT became the first NGO to emphasize new and clean energy resources by performing a comprehensive study and holding a conference in 1984. In 1989, EFT became the first NGO to render a service of comparing the environmental legislations of the European Union and Turkey in 1989 and reiterated a similar study in 2001. EFT inviting the representatives of all coastal countries of the Mediterranean to Antalya in 1989, became the first Turkish non-governmental organization to host an international Mediterranean conference. EFT took steps that led to the establishment of the expression and concept of “sustainable development” in Turkey. It organized the first conference on sustainable development on 29-30 November 1989, and introduced “Our Common Future”, which is the fundamental source of the concept of Sustainable Development, into Turkish and the printed 6500 copies of the book were depleted fast and the Foundation perpetuated its studies in this respect. EFT published books “The Wetlands of Turkey” and “Biological Diversity in Turkey” which were as beneficial as the “Environmental Profile of Turkey.” With the financial support from GTZ of the Federal German Government, EFT hosted the “Tourism and Environment Conference” on 3-5 October in Çeşme, İzmir. EFT, in 1994, by a Training Program on Environmental Impact Assessment, gave a five-day training course it organized in Ankara to 80 technicians at certain levels. FT translated and published a new book titled “Green Management.” EFT published second edition of “Environmental Education” which consists of the presentations and discussions at the Environmental Education in Turkey meeting held in 2007. In 2016, EFT published “Global Climate Change and its Impacts”.

8.4.4.1 Regional/municipal Packaging recovery system

All municipalities have contract with licensed companies to collect, transport, separate and recovery of packaging waste. ÇEVKO is the main authorized institution to coordinate and support packaging waste management. İstanbul Metropolitan Municipality has its own licensed company İSTAÇ.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Industrial facilities have their own recycling/recovery plant or have contract with licensed companies.

Ministry of Environment and Urbanization is the sole authorized organization in the country. All recovery must be reported and approved by Ministry.

8.4.4.2 Regional/municipal Consortium for plastic recycling

All municipalities have contract with licensed companies to collect, transport, separate and recovery for plastic packaging. ÇEVKO is the main authorized institution to coordinate and support packaging waste management. İstanbul Metropolitan Municipality has its own licensed company İSTAÇ.

8.4.4.3 Material and object in contact with food

Several institutions are authorized in this issue.

- Ministry of Health
- Ministry of Environment and Urbanization
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Livestock
- Ministry of Customs and Trade
- Public Health Agency
- the Market Surveillance and Inspection Coordination Board (PGD)
- Turkish Standards Institute

8.4.4.4 Waste regulation authority

Ministry of Environment and Urbanization is the waste regulation authority in Turkey.

8.4.4.5 Packaging waste paperwork

Ministry of Environment and Urbanization is the authority in Turkey.

8.4.4.6 Traceably and Control of Waste

Ministry of Environment and Urbanization is the authority in Turkey.

8.4.5 Legislation ongoing

“Draft Regulation on Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control”

“Draft Regulation on Permanent Organic Pollutants”

“Draft Regulation on Amendment of Regulation on waste Batteries and Accumulators”

“Draft Regulation on Controlled Landfill of Wastes”

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.4.6 Impact of the legislation on the packaging plastics waste actors

8.4.6.1 Import:

- **Environment Law** (1983, No 5272)
- **"Law on Public Health"** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593)
- **"Regulation on Waste Management"** (OJ 2 April 2015, #29314)
- **"Regulation on Control of Solid Wastes"** (OJ 25 April 2002, #24736)
- **"Regulation on Packaging Waste Control"** (OJ 05 April 2007, #25777, OJ 27 December 2017, #30283)
- **"Regulation on Controlled Landfill of Wastes," "Regulation of Hazardous Waste," "Regulation on Environmental Inspection," "Regulation on Environmental Permit and License," "Regulation on Control of Polychlorinated Biphenyls and Polychlorinated Terphenyls," "Regulation on Receiving Waste from Ships and Control of Wastes"**
- **Law on Preparation and Implementation of Technical Legislation on Products"** (OJ 29 June 2001, #4703)
- **"Regulation on Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Dangerous Substances and Preparations"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **"Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures" (SEA)** (OJ 11 December 2013, #28848 Bis)
- **"Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **"Regulation on Compilation and Distribution of Safety Data Sheets Related to Dangerous Substances and Preparations "** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **"Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures "** (OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **"Regulation on Restriction and Prohibition of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures"** (OJ 21 November 2014, #29182)
- **"Regulation on Market Surveillance and Inspection of Ministry of Customs and Trade"** (OJ 12 June 2014, #29028)
- **"Communiqué on Import Control of Certain User Products Controlled by Ministry of Customs and Trade (Product safety and Control: 2018/12)"** (OJ 30 December 2017, #30286.2)
- **"Communiqué on Amount and Detection of N-nitrosamines and N-nitro sable Substances in Elastomer or Rubber Feeding Bottle Teats and Soothers"** (OJ 31 October 2013, #28807)
- **"Communiqué on Conformity Assessment in Certain Consumer Products"** (OJ 3 May 2016, #29701)

8.4.6.2 Collection:

- **Environment Law** (1983, No 5272)
- **"Law on Public Health"** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593)
- **Metropolitan Municipality Law** (OJ 10 July 2004, #5216)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **Municipal Law** (OJ 3 July 2005, #5393)
- **"Regulation on Waste Management"** (OJ 2 April 2015, #29314)
- **"Regulation on Control of Solid Wastes"** (OJ 25 April 2002, #24736)
- **"Regulation on Packaging Waste Control"** (OJ 05 April 2007, #25777, OJ 27 December 2017, #30283)
- **"Regulation on Environmental Permit and License"**

8.4.6.3 Sorting:

- **Environment Law** (1983, No 5272)
- **"Law on Public Health"** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593)
- **Metropolitan Municipality Law** (OJ 10 July 2004, #5216)
- **Municipal Law** (OJ 3 July 2005, #5393)
- **"Regulation on Waste Management"** (OJ 2 April 2015, #29314)
- **"Regulation on Control of Solid Wastes"** (OJ 25 April 2002, #24736)
- **"Regulation on Packaging Waste Control"** (OJ 05 April 2007, #25777, OJ 27 December 2017, #30283)
- **"Regulation on Environmental Permit and License"**
- **"Regulation on Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Dangerous Substances and Preparations"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **"Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures" (SEA)** (OJ 11 December 2013, #28848 Bis)
- **"Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **"Regulation on Compilation and Distribution of Safety Data Sheets Related to Dangerous Substances and Preparations"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **"Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures"** (OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **"Regulation on Restriction and Prohibition of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures"** (OJ 21 November 2014, #29182)

8.4.6.4 Selling of sorted PPW:

- **Environment Law** (1983, No 5272)
- **"Law on Public Health"** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593)
- **"Regulation on Packaging Waste Control"** (OJ 05 April 2007, #25777, OJ 27 December 2017, #30283)
- **"Regulation on Environmental Permit and License"**
- **"Regulation on Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Dangerous Substances and Preparations"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **"Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures" (SEA)** (OJ 11 December 2013, #28848 Bis)
- **"Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **"Regulation on Compilation and Distribution of Safety Data Sheets Related to Dangerous Substances and Preparations"** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **“Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Restriction and Prohibition of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 21 November 2014, #29182)

8.4.6.5 Crashing:

- **“Regulation on Environmental Permit and License”**
- **“Regulation on Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Dangerous Substances and Preparations”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures” (SEA)** (OJ 11 December 2013, #28848 Bis)
- **“Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Compilation and Distribution of Safety Data Sheets Related to Dangerous Substances and Preparations ”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Restriction and Prohibition of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 21 November 2014, #29182)

8.4.6.6 The preparatory operation for reuse:

- **Environment Law** (1983, No 5272)
- **“Law on Public Health”** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593)
- **Metropolitan Municipality Law** (OJ 10 July 2004, #5216)
- **Municipal Law** (OJ 3 July 2005, #5393)
- **“Regulation on Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Dangerous Substances and Preparations”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures” (SEA)** (OJ 11 December 2013, #28848 Bis)
- **“Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Compilation and Distribution of Safety Data Sheets Related to Dangerous Substances and Preparations ”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017)

8.4.6.7 Export:

- **Environment Law** (1983, No 5272)

8.4.6.8 Transformation:

- **“Regulation on Market Surveillance and Inspection of Ministry of Customs and Trade”** (OJ 12 June 2014, #29028)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.4.6.9 Re-use:

- **Law on Preparation and Implementation of Technical Legislation on Products**” (OJ 29 June 2001, #4703)
- **“Law on Public Health”** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593) is the pioneer in public health protection issues and regulates the administrative and technical basement for following legislation in Turkey.
- **“Law on Veterinary Services, Plant Health, Food and Feed”** (OJ 11 June 2010, #5996)
- **“Regulation on Market Surveillance and Inspection of Ministry of Customs and Trade”** (OJ 12 June 2014, #29028)
- **“Regulation on Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Dangerous Substances and Preparations”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures” (SEA)** (OJ 11 December 2013, #28848 Bis)
- **“Regulation on ‘CE’ Mark”** (OJ 23 February 2012, #28213, Council of Ministries Decision 2011/2588)
- **“Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals”** (OJ 26 December 2008, #27092, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Compilation and Distribution of Safety Data Sheets Related to Dangerous Substances and Preparations “**(OJ 26 December 2008, #27092)
- **“Regulation on Safety Data Sheets Related to the Hazardous Substances and Mixtures “**(OJ 13 December 2014, #29204, repealed on 23 June 2017)
- **“Regulation on Restriction and Prohibition of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures”** (OJ 21 November 2014, #29182) (name has changed, and some articles have been added)
- **“Regulation on Turkish Food Codex** (OJ 29 December 2011, 28157.3)
- **“Turkish Food Codex Regulation on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food”** (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382)
- **“Regulation on Food Safety and Food Quality Inspection and Control”** (OJ 26 September 2008, #27009)
- **“Regulation on Water Intended for Human Consumption”** (OJ 17 February 2005, #25730, amended by OJ 31 July 2009, #2730, OJ 7 March 2013, #28580 and OJ 11 April 2014, #28969, OJ 20 October 2016, #29863)
- **“Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on Materials and Articles in Contact with Food”** (Com. #2013/34, published on OJ 17 July 2013, #28710)
- **“Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on the List of Food Simulants Used in Migration Test of the Components of the Plastic Materials and Articles in Contact with Food”** (Com. #2013/35, published on OJ 17 July 2013, #28710)
- **“Communiqué on the Principles and Procedures Related to Standard Practices That Must Be Complied within the Wholesale and Retail Trade of Vegetables and Fruits”** (OJ 3 October 2017, #30199)
- **“Communiqué on Food-Contact Active and Smart Materials and Articles of Turkish Food Codex”** (OJ 5 April 2018, #30382)

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **“Communiqué on Amount and Detection of N-nitrosamines and N-nitro sable Substances in Elastomer or Rubber Feeding Bottle Teats and Soothers “** (OJ 31 October 2013, #28807)
- **“Communiqué on Conformity Assessment in Certain Consumer Products”** (OJ 3 May 2016, #29701)
- **“Law on cosmetics”** (OJ 24 March 2005, #5324)

8.4.6.10 Feedstock recycling:

- **“Law on Public Health”** (OJ 24 April 1930, #1593) is the pioneer in public health protection issues and regulates the administrative and technical basement for following legislation in Turkey.
- **“Law on Veterinary Services, Plant Health, Food and Feed”** (OJ 11 June 2010, #5996)
- **“Regulation on Turkish Food Codex** (OJ 29 December 2011, 28157.3)
- **“Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on the List of Food Simulants Used in Migration Test of the Components of the Plastic Materials and Articles in Contact with Food”** (Com. #2013/35, published on OJ 17 July 2013, #28710)
- **“Communiqué on Conformity Assessment in Certain Consumer Products”** (OJ 3 May 2016, #29701)
- **“Regulation on Food Safety and Food Quality Inspection and Control”** (OJ 26 September 2008, #27009)

8.4.6.11 Conclusion

Although there is an established regulatory programme for recycling of solid wastes in developed countries, improper disposal methods are still broadly adapted in developing countries. Turkey, as an economically developing country, has a number of open dumps in operation. This creates a significant risk for the environment and for human health. However, Turkey's accession to European Union requires compliance with the European Union legislation and therefore there is currently an increasing pressure on the government authorities to develop a sustainable approach to recycling (particularly focusing on plastics) and composting activities and integrate strategies aiming at pursuing sustainable society in Turkey.

Disposal of solid wastes is a significant environmental problem in mainly developing countries as it is in Turkey. Open dumping, which creates environmental risks, is used very commonly in smaller provinces in Turkey, causing ground water and air pollution along with blockage problems in sewer system and creates health risks for the population living nearby. Explosion of accumulated methane gas also is an important risk because of these buries wastes.

One of the promising benefits of robust waste management is reuse of waste material for energy generation as it is anticipated that “waste to energy” conversion could help getting rid of problems of electricity scarcity and waste management together. In this respect, recycling has gained an importance as it could help reducing the amount of waste along with decreasing the demand in raw materials.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Plastics have become an essential part of our modern lifestyle, and the global plastic production has increased immensely during the past 50 years. Plastics have recently become commonly used materials for packaging purposes as they are light and flexible. This has contributed greatly to the generation of plastic-related waste. After a relatively short service life, most plastic products are discarded and sent to landfill sites, incinerators, recycling facilities or chemical treatment. Chemical reduction converts plastic waste into chemicals used as feedstock in industrial processes or as fuel. According to the study focused on the literature survey on the reuse of plastics and municipal waste sector in Turkey, the identified gaps and weaknesses were as follows:

-In Turkey there are a number of Materials Recycling Facilities (MRF) to recover plastics from other recyclables, however there is no plastic separation at source. This is an important gap in producing high quality recycled plastics;

-There is a lack of communication between plastic producers (from scrap plastics) and reprocessed plastic buyers. This miscommunication is an important problem in determining the quality requirement of reprocessed plastics in recycling market;

-In terms of waste hierarchy there is an urgent need for collaboration of responsible authorities to produce sustainable strategies to motivate stakeholders (public organisations, private sector, academia, non-governmental organisations) to encourage recycling activities;

-There is a lack of investment provision of recycling activities such as building civil amenity sites where bulky items could be separated at specific points found nearby the populated areas and bring facilities which could be placed at important points such as big supermarkets;

-There is not any technological improvement in terms of producing required equipment for reprocessing waste. This causes dependence on external sources to feed national recycling system.

The possible solution options to fill these gaps are concluded below:

- The Turkish Ministry of Environment and Urbanization and its affiliated organisations in the provinces are required to strengthen their investigations and controls to make sure the current waste legislation is implemented properly;
- There must be a robust waste collection system in place supplied by licensed authorities to avoid scavenging of recyclable wastes;
- Householders should be trained on how to place their wastes in correct recycling bins in order to improve recycling efficiency;
- In terms of determination the quality of reprocessed plastics, there must be a guidance manual published in the context of Turkish Standards;
- There should be more research incentives to establish an effective recycling system or especially highly populated cities in Turkey by making into account the specific requirements of these places.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The primary objective of managing waste is that the materials should be handled, treated, and disposed of safely. Managing the municipal waste is a complex issue that requires suitable technologies, allocated budget coupled with a regulatory system including comprehensive policies and guidelines. It is also an issue which in recent years has kept alive the cultural, political and science debate.

However, problems related to solid waste in Turkey appear at the beginning of waste collection stage. Due to commingle waste collection there appears to be cross-contamination between recyclables, which causes quality of recycled materials to get lower.

For this reason, more research is required to establish a database and information on Turkish waste generation and composition to develop robust recycling models which enable the impact of segregation schemes to be assessed and predict the potential for introducing new degradation schemes and technologies. This will form the basis of the future, planning, design, technology development and implementation of municipal waste management facilities.

8.4.7 Policy experiences from case studies

8.4.7.1 First interview - TARHAN PLASTIC CORPORATION

The first interview (Annex 12 - Interview to Tarhan Plastic Corporation) was done on July 6th with Cansu Canatan, Environmental Engineer in Tarhan Plastic Corporation.

We contacted Tarhan Plastic Corporation with perspective of understanding their experience in recycling of plastic and secondary raw materials production.

Tarhan Plastic Corporation has 17 plants in Turkey. However, plastic recovery is only performed in Aksaray plant. They have technologies capable to recycle of plastic bag, aluminium, and plastic foil wastes. They carry out collection and separation of packaging wastes.

8.4.7.2 Recap of TARHAN PLASTIC CORPORATION opinion

Here below the main findings of the interview are summarised:

- In Turkey, packaging wastes are not always collected separately and legally.
- Legislations are adequate, but there is room for improvement in practice.
- There are impurity problems with recycling since the waste is not separately collected.
- EoW can give great convenience in giving added value of wastes. However, this situation can be early for Turkey.

8.4.7.3 Second interview - VATAN PLASTIC

The second interview (Annex 12 - Interview to Vatan Plastic) was done on May 15th with Serap BARAN, Quality Manager in Vatan Plastic Industry and Trade Limited Company. The

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

interview was done with written answers since the reciprocal programs could not be balanced with the company.

We contacted Vatan Plastic Industry and Trade Limited Company with perspective of understanding their experience in recycling of plastic and secondary raw materials production.

They have 5 plants in Turkey. Exporting 60% of their production, they export to 100 countries in 5 continents. The first five-layer stretch film production was done by Vatan Plastic in Turkey. In addition, PE film, polymer filler, shrink film, polypropylene fibre, garbage bag, greenhouse cover, plastic packaging products, HDPE and LDPE are produced in plants.

We summarise the interview in a table to emphasise the main topics discussed.

8.4.7.4 Recap of VATAN PLASTIC opinion

- The company produces packaging products, recycles them and uses the recycled materials as secondary raw materials.
- It is stated that EoW and their trade will be very positive progressions for plastic manufacturers.
- Packaging wastes are not always collected separately and legally. Therefore, there are impurity problems with recycling since the waste is not separately collected.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

8.5 Conclusions

The purpose of the Deliverable 6.4 is to lay the foundations for identifying barriers and opportunities at EU level for the valorisation of biobased and fossil-based plastics waste as secondary raw materials in the current EU legislative framework.

The performed activities, including desk-based analysis of the European policy framework, local legislative insights, and interviews to the case studies of relevant practitioners, allowed to identify a set of relevant findings, which will be useful to establish the basis for the successive activities of Task 6.3.

During the development of the Deliverable 6.4, a number of barriers found within the desk-based investigation of EU legislative framework have been indeed confirmed through local and national insights of Italian, Spanish, Turkish, and Croatian cases.

In particular, the performed interviews to industrial case studies allowed to confirm several risks and chances already identified at general level, to identify new ones, and in general to give the right weight to the main issues analysed. Here below the main conclusions retrievable from the performed activities are summarized, with special focus on the outcomes of the local insights.

Relevant barriers, confirmed by the case studies

In the legislative framework:

- Technological gap between the MS in collection, selection, treating and processing of PPW (e.g. Croatia buy plastic waste from other countries where collection is better segregated, or buy production waste, which does not require as much energy and water as reprocessing post-consumer waste).
- No efforts to find “definitive” EoW Criteria for plastics (regulation), but instead to provide guidelines for MS in the management of the “no longer waste” materials.
- Criticisms related to the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislations.
- Within the proposal for Directive, “on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment,” the European Commission has come up with measures banning or restricting the use of single-use plastic application (such as plates, cutlery, cups, plastic bags, etc.) including biodegradable & compostable plastics.
- Biodegradable & compostable plastics are designed to be organically recycled and banning products such as plates, cutlery, or cups, which are used efficiently especially in collective catering, would only block further research & development in this sector.

From existing experiences:

- Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Needed high quality standards of compost, that requires refining interventions,
- High effort invested, and high costs related to the disposal of the huge quantities of waste produced.
- Packaging wastes are not always collected separately and legally (e.g. in Turkey).
- Since recycled plastics may do not have the same quality and performance compared to virgin plastics, this can be a technical barrier becoming a challenge for future technological developments e.g. monitoring systems.

Areas for possible solutions, confirmed by the case studies

In the legislative framework:

- Other than EoW Criteria, the European Commission is promoting bilateral agreements between MS.
- The drafting of specific EoW Criteria between two or more MS can be used as precedent to write other agreements, also with not-European countries.
- The drafting of EoW Criteria by private entities is possible but with the support of the public entities, who have the duty to assist and legitimise them.
- Since the market for plastics secondary raw materials is growing, standardisation is needed for the traceability of recycled material.
- End-of-Waste Criteria for plastic can be oriented towards specific targeted applications in order to replace fossil feedstock plastic with compostable bioplastics.
- The legislative framework (especially at National and municipal level) should help to improve the quality of recycling (e.g.: plastic applications in which the packaging is prone to be mixed with organic content after use).
- The existence of a clear and stable policy framework is crucial to promote investments. This framework should include: the creation of clear quality standards and demand support measures, as well as incentives for research, innovation, and training.
- Legislative actions aimed at fostering the emergence and limiting the costs of environmental externalities should be designed, as well as for the promotion of the economy circularity through the application of specific fiscal measures and the simplification of the rules governing waste recover.
- Promotion of law enforcement of already existing legislation, concrete adoption of green public procurement, creation of flagship project for specific supply chain case studies and diffusion of private-public partnerships.

From existing experiences:

- Technical obstacles related to performances, quality, reliability and proper separation methods can be helped by holistic legislative framework.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- Raise citizens awareness on the topic of sustainability, through specific education schemes aimed at conveying the importance and the necessity of virtuous practices, and through public campaigns.
- The importance of communicating the difference between plastics and compostable bioplastics is crucial since the latter are designed to be collected in the organic waste stream.
- It is important to promote biobased plastics packaging materials in order to let understand to the consumers the benefits that the shift from fossil feedstock to biological resources is effectively feasible.
- Cooperation between the MS of private and public entities, if improved, can be an effective opportunity to fill the technological gap between MS and the right way for all MS to reach the EU targets joined together.
- Sharing of the legislative experiences among the MS can develop national legislative frameworks with common characteristics in order to avoid regulatory barriers and to facilitate international trades.

The development of the interviews, investigating the hands-on experience of practitioners for a number of case studies, allowed to retrieve relevant opinions on how to face and overcome almost all the problems crossed on the theme of PPW reuse and recycling, in many different steps of the value chain, often embracing the possibility to transform barriers in challenges.

The developed investigation of the legislative landscape will allow to continue and improve the analysis of legislative barriers and possible solutions through the consultation to stakeholders not already involved in the project during the next phases of the project. The team will also consider the updates to the EU legislative framework, in order to complete the spectrum of the analysis with eventual the new bottlenecks and drivers from updated legislation. In Deliverable 6.3, that will be the recipient of the subsequent activities, the team will propose a set policy recommendation for EU institutions aimed at unlocking and facilitating the recycling of fossil-based and bio-based plastics waste as secondary materials for packaging.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

9 REFERENCES

Web pages:

USDA - Foreign Agricultural Service, <https://www.usda-eu.org/>

EUR-Lex, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/>

Eurostat, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

European Council and the Council of the EU, <http://www.consilium.europa.eu/>

Seafish, <http://www.seafish.org/>

Plastics Europe, <https://www.plasticseurope.org/en>

Circular Ocean INTERREG, <http://www.circularocean.eu/>

BLASTIC project, <https://www.blastic.eu/>

European Commission, <http://ec.europa.eu/>

Packaging Europe, <https://packagingeurope.com/>

ECHA - European Chemicals Agency, <https://echa.europa.eu/>

European Bioplastics, <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/>

Nova Institute, <http://www.nova-institut.de/>

Science | AAAS - American Association for the Advancement of Science, <https://www.sciencemag.org/>

Plastics Europe, <https://www.plasticseurope.org/en>

The Balance, <https://www.thebalance.com/>

UNECE - United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, <https://www.unece.org/>

Conai - Consorzio Nazionale Imballaggi, www.conai.org/

Rete Ambiente, <http://www.reteambiente.it/>

Corepla - Consorzio Nazionale per la Raccolta, il Riciclo ed il Recupero degli Imballaggi in Plastica, <http://www.corepla.it/>

Aliplast spa, <http://www.aliplastspa.com/>

NOVAMONT, <https://novamont.it/eng>

SILEASPA, <https://www.sileaspa.it/>

TurkStat, www.turkstat.gov.tr/

SAYISTAY - Turkish Court of Accounts, <https://www.sayistay.gov.tr/>

Conversion Market & Strategy GmbH, www.conversio-gmbh.com/

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

General References:

JRS IPTS, 2008, *End of Waste Criteria*, Final Report.

Alejandro Villanueva, Peter Eder (European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Institute for Prospective Technological Studies), 2014, *End-of-waste criteria for waste plastic for conversion*, Technical proposals.

Ellen MacArthur Foundation, January 2017, *The New Plastics Economy*, Catalysing action.

Walter Ganapini, 2012, *Bioplastics-A case study of Bioeconomy in Italy*.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 1- ORDINARY LEGISLATIVE PROCEDURE

In order to understand the main interactions between the EU organisms with the MS legislation, this section shows a short summary of the main EU procedures and legislative means.

The “**Procedure of Codecision**” was introduced in 1992. From the 13th December 2017 with the Lisbon Treaty the “Codecision”, becomes the ordinary legislative procedure for the UE legislation.

The **European Commission** is the main legislative organ in the EU and is the promoter of the legislative process with the **legislative initiative monopoly**.

The **Commission** can submit a proposal for UE legal acts:

- On its **own initiative**
- At the request of the **Parliament**
- At the request of the **Council**
- At the request of a million of **citizens**

There are some specific cases, defined in the treaties, with other European political bodies can launch the initiative.

In case of successful procedure outcome, the Parliament or Council can produce three types of the legislative act:

- **Regulation**: binding and applicable in all the member states;
- **Directive**: the request results are binding but the member states can choose the way to implement the Directive;
- **Decision**: binding only for whom is intended.

The **Ordinary Legislative Procedure** can be divided into three phases or readings

- **Legislative proposal and First reading**

The Commission adopts the legislative proposals by written procedure or oral procedure, by submitting the legislative proposal to the European Parliament.

The Parliament can adopt it in first reading or **introduce amendments**.

The Council can accept the Parliament amendments or decide to amend them. In the last case, the proposal returns to the Parliament for the second reading.

- **Second reading and Conciliation**

The Parliament has three months to approve or rejects the Council position.

- In the first case the **act is adopted**;
- Otherwise, the **procedure ends**.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

If the Council approves all of the Parliament's amendments, the act is adopted; otherwise, the Parliament and the **Council Presidents** convene the **Conciliation Committee**.

The Committee is composed of equal number of Parliament and Council members. If the Committee agrees with the common legislative project the text is forwarded to The Parliament and the Council for a third reading, or else if it's rejected the procedure ends.

- **Third reading**

The Parliament and the Council shall react to the Committee common project in three weeks.

Only if the Parliament and the Council accept jointly, the act will be adopted, otherwise, the procedure ends.

Table 9: Ordinary Legislative Procedure

First reading

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 2 - ARTICLE 10 AS AMENDED

Article 10 as amended

1. Member States shall take the necessary measures to ensure that waste undergoes preparing for re-use, recycling, or other recovery operations, in accordance with Articles 4 and 13.

2. Where necessary to comply with paragraph 1 and to facilitate or improve preparing for re-use, recycling and other recovery operations, waste shall be subject to separate collection and shall not be mixed with other waste or other materials with different properties.

3. Member States may allow derogations from paragraph 2 provided that at least one of the following conditions is met:

(a) collecting certain types of waste together does not affect their potential to undergo preparing for re-use, recycling or other recovery operations in accordance with Article 4 and results in output from those operations which is of comparable quality to that achieved through separate collection;

(b) separate collection does not deliver the best environmental outcome when considering the overall environmental impacts of the management of the relevant waste streams;

(c) separate collection is not technically feasible taking into consideration good practices in waste collection;

(d) separate collection would entail disproportionate economic costs taking into account the costs of adverse environmental and health impacts of mixed waste collection and treatment, the potential for efficiency improvements in waste collection and treatment, revenues from sales of secondary raw materials as well as the application of the polluter-pays principle and extended producer responsibility.

Member States shall regularly review derogations under this paragraph taking into account good practices in separate collection of waste and other developments in waste management.

4. Member States shall take measures to ensure that waste that has been separately collected for preparing for re- use and recycling pursuant to Article 11(1) and Article 22 is not incinerated, with the exception of waste resulting from subsequent treatment operations of the separately collected waste for which incineration delivers the best environmental outcome in accordance with Article 4.

5. Where necessary to comply with paragraph 1 of this Article and to facilitate or improve recovery, Member States shall take the necessary measures, before or during recovery, to remove hazardous substances, mixtures and components from hazardous waste with a view to their treatment in accordance with Articles 4 and 13.

6. By 31 December 2021, Member States shall submit a report to the Commission on the implementation of this Article as regards municipal waste and bio-waste, including on the material and territorial coverage of separate collection and any derogations under paragraph 3.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 3 - PLASTIC MATERIAL FOR PACKAGING

Below the most used plastic materials in the packaging production are reported. The vast variety can help to understand the complexity of this material stream.

Polyethylene terephthalate

(PETE or PET - recycling code: 1)

Polyethylene terephthalate or polyethylene terephthalate belongs to the family of polyesters. It is a thermoplastic resin that adapts to the family of polyesters and is particularly suitable for gas and tubs. Among the first solutions:

- **Bottles, Film, Pipes, trays and blisters, containers and packaging, Labels.**

High density polyethylene

(HDPE - recycle code: 2)

Polyethylene (PE) is the simplest of synthetic polymers and is the most common among plastics. It is a thermoplastic resin, obtained from the polymerization of ethylene. It is distinguished in high-density polyethylene (PE-HD) and low-density (PE-LD), which has been assigned the recycle code 4. The high-density polyethylene is formed by linear chains, which give greater strength and rigidity, making it therefore particularly suitable to produce cans and rigid containers. The most common applications are:

- **bottles for the containment of detergents or food**, toys, plastic caps, pipes for transporting water and natural gas.

Polyvinyl chloride

(PVC - recycle code: 3)

Polyvinyl chloride (or polyvinylchloride) is the polymer obtained from the polymerization of vinyl chloride and is a thermoplastic. The most relevant applications are:

- construction pipes (for example gutters and pipes for drinking water), doors, vinyl floors, **rigid and plasticized film for packaging**, phonograph records.

Low density polyethylene

(LDPE - recycle code: 4)

Low-density polyethylene (also a thermoplastic) belongs to the polyethylene family, which is to say polymers obtained from the polymerization of ethylene and is distinguished because polymer chains are not linear like in high-density polyethylene (PE-HD, recycle code 2), but they have ramifications, which make it a lighter, ductile and flexible material. It is used in the production of flexible products such as films (from which **bags** and envelopes are also derived), used both for **packaging** and, for example, in agriculture.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Polypropylene

(PP - recycle code: 5)

Polypropylene is a thermoplastic material that has found its most extensive applications in the isotactic form. Polypropylene is made of many objects in common plastic, starting from household items and toys, but also many rigid packaging (cans, flasks) and flexible packaging (**film for automatic packaging**).

Polystyrene or Polystyrene

(PS - recycle code: 6)

Polystyrene, or polystyrene, is the (thermoplastic) polymer of styrene. The expanded polystyrene (EPS) is obtained by immersing the polystyrene granule in water and adding pentane. With the polystyrene many artefacts are made: from **disposable tableware to packaging**.

Other plastics

(recycling code: 7)

All other polymers fall into this category, for which no a specific code has been provided, or their combinations (for example a tray consisting of an outer layer of PET and an inner layer of PE-LD). Examples of polymers used to produce packaging for which a specific recycling code has not been defined are: Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), Polycarbonate (PC), Polylactic acid (PLA).

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 4 - LEGISLATION FOR PLASTIC MATERIALS AS A PRODUCT

Restriction of Hazardous Substances

The Directive 2011/65/CE (RoHS 2) establishes norms on the restriction for the use of hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment (EEe), to defence human health and environment, including the recovery and the ecological displacement of the EEe.

This product directive does not regard the Packaging plastics waste issues, so it will not be analysed.

REACH Regulation

The Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the **Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals**, (in short REACH) has been adopted to improve the protection of human health and the environment from the risks that can be posed by chemicals, while enhancing the competitiveness of the EU chemicals industry. It also promotes alternative methods for the hazard assessment of substances to reduce the number of tests on animals.

In principle, REACH applies to all chemical substances; not only those used in industrial processes but also in our day-to-day lives, for example in cleaning products, paints as well as in articles such as clothes, furniture, and electrical appliances. Therefore, the regulation has an impact on most companies across the EU.

REACH places the burden of proof on companies. To comply with the regulation, companies must identify and manage the risks linked to the substances they manufacture and market in the EU. They must demonstrate to **European Chemicals Agency** (ECHA) how the substance can be safely used, and they must communicate the risk management measures to the users.

If the risks cannot be managed, authorities can restrict the use of substances in different ways. In the long run, the most hazardous substances should be substituted with less dangerous ones.

REACH stands for Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals. It entered into force on 1 June 2007, by establishing procedures for collecting and assessing information on the properties and hazards of substances.

Companies need to register their substances and to do this they need to work together with other companies who are registering the same substance.

ECHA receives and evaluates individual registrations for their compliance, and the EU Member States evaluate selected substances to clarify initial concerns for human health or for the environment. Authorities and ECHA's scientific committees assess whether the risks of substances can be managed.

Authorities can ban hazardous substances if their risks are unmanageable. They can also decide to restrict a use or make it subject to a prior authorisation.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

REACH impacts on a wide range of companies across many sectors, even those who may not think of themselves as being involved with chemicals.

In general, under REACH the following **roles** are envisaged for compliance:

- **Manufacturer:** producers of chemicals, either to for internal use or to supply to other people (even if it is for export);
- **Importer:** when buying anything from outside the EU/EEA, such as individual chemicals, mixtures for onwards sale or finished products, like clothes, furniture, or plastic goods;
- **Downstream users:** most companies use chemicals, sometimes even without realising it;
- **Companies established outside the EU:** companies established outside the EU are not bound by the obligations of REACH, even when exporting their products into the customs territory of the European Union. The responsibility for fulfilling the requirements of REACH, such as pre-registration or registration lies with the importers established in the European Union, or with the only representative of a non-EU manufacturer established in the European Union.⁶¹

CLP Regulation

The Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation is in force from 2008 as EU Regulation, with the aim to align the European Union system of classification, labelling and packaging of chemical substances and mixtures to the Globally Harmonised System (GHS).

It facilitates global trade, by harmonising communication of hazard information of chemicals and by promoting regulatory efficiency. It complements the 2006 Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) Regulation (EC No 1907/2006) and replaces the current system contained in the Dangerous Substances Directive (67/548/EEC) and the Dangerous Preparations Directive (1999/45/EC).

It introduces new classification criteria, European hazard symbols (pictograms) and Risk and Safety Statements for labelling, while taking into account elements which were part of the prior EU legislation.

Companies must appropriately classify, label, and package their substances and mixtures before placing them on the market. Main aims are workers protection, consumers, and the environment.

Food Contact Materials

Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 provides a harmonised legal EU framework. It sets out the general principles of safety and inertness for all Food Contact Materials (FCMs).

The principles set out in Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 require that materials do not:

- Release their constituents into food at **levels harmful to human health**

⁶¹ <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/understanding-reach>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **Change food composition, taste, and odour** in an unacceptable way

Moreover, the framework provides:

- **special rules on active and intelligent materials** (they are by their design not inert)
- powers to enact **additional EU measures for specific materials** (e.g. for plastics)
- the procedure to perform **safety assessments of substances used to manufacture FCMs** involving the European Food Safety Authority
- **rules on labelling including an indication for use** (e.g. as a coffee machine, a wine bottle, or a soup spoon) or by reproducing the appropriate symbol. For more information, please refer to the following document on Symbols for labelling food contact materials.
- compliance documentation and **traceability**

Regulation on Good Manufacturing Practices

Regulation (EC) No 2023/2006 ensures that the manufacturing process is well controlled so that the specifications for FCMs remain in conformity with the legislation:

- premises fit for purpose and staff awareness of **critical production stages**
- documented **quality assurance** and **quality control systems** maintained at the premises, and
- selection of suitable starting materials for the **manufacturing process** with a view to the safety and inertness of the final articles

Good manufacturing rules apply to **all stages in the manufacturing chain of food** contact materials, although other legislation covers the production of starting materials.

The Persistent Organic Pollutant (POP) Regulation

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs) are chemical substances that persist in the environment and pose a risk of causing adverse effects to human health and the environment. This group of priority pollutants consists of pesticides (such as DDT), industrial chemicals (such as polychlorinated biphenyls, PCBs) and unintentional by-products of industrial processes (such as dioxins and furans).

Below, the instruments establishing strict international regimes for initial lists of POPs:

- The Protocol to the regional UNECE Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP) on POPs, opened for signatures in June 1998 and entered into force on 23 October 2003
- The global Stockholm Convention on POPs, opened for signatures in May 2001 and entered into force on 17 May 2004

Both contain **provisions for including additional chemicals** into these lists. They lay down the following control measures:

- **Prohibition or severe restriction** of the production and use of intentionally produced POPs

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

- **Restrictions on export and import** of the intentionally produced POPs (Stockholm Convention)
- **Provisions on the safe handling of stockpiles** (Stockholm Convention)
- **Provisions on the environmentally sound disposal** of wastes containing POPs
- **Provisions on the reduction of emissions** of unintentionally produced POPs (e.g. dioxins and furans)

New substances added to the Stockholm Convention in May 2009 and to the POP Protocol in December 2009.

EU's common system of value added tax (VAT)

The Directive 2006/112/EC (the EU's common system of value added tax (VAT)) recasts and repeals the original sixth value added tax (VAT) directive, thus clarifying the EU's VAT legislation currently in force.

VAT is applied to all transactions carried out in the EU for consideration (payment) by a taxable person. Taxable transactions include supplies of goods or services within a single EU country, intra-EU acquisitions of goods (goods supplied and dispatched or transported by a business in one EU country to a business in another) and imports of goods into the EU from outside.

Regarding the place of transaction, different rules apply depending on the nature of the transaction, the kind of product supplied and whether transport is involved.

- supply of goods;
- intra-EU acquisition of goods;
- imports of goods;
- supply of services;
- passenger transport;
- activities relating to culture, sport, education, and entertainment;
- restaurant services.

payable on taxable transactions, e.g. domestic supplies of goods or services. There is in general no right to deduct in the case of an economic activity that is exempt from VAT, or if the taxable person qualifies for a special scheme. In certain cases, deductions may be limited or adjusted.

The directive sets out the obligations of taxable and certain non-taxable persons. Generally, VAT is payable by any taxable person making a taxable supply of goods or services. Exceptions include specific transactions where it is the customer who pays VAT, e.g. supplies of natural gas, and transactions where the EU country may choose to designate the customer to pay VAT, as with certain fraud-sensitive supplies such as emission allowances (until 31 December 2018).

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

The directive permits derogations by EU countries from standard VAT rules, e.g. to prevent certain types of tax evasion. There are also special VAT schemes designed to reduce paperwork, e.g. for small businesses and for farmers.⁶²

⁶² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=legisum:l31057>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 5 – INTERVIEW TO FATER GROUP

Question

Answer

Why is Fater interested in EoW Criteria for plastic?

Fater presented, on 25th October 2017, the first plant to recycle the 100% of used AHP. The plant is operating by a waste operator (named Contarina) who transforms the used product in three different secondary raw materials:

1. plastic,
2. cellulose and
3. superabsorbent polymer.

What is your experience in the local/regional/national legislation on waste recycling and 'end-of-waste'?

Fater started actions aimed to obtain the necessary authorizations at regional and local level. Firstly, in August 2016, the Veneto Regional Executive recognize the secondary raw materials stream from the Contarina plant.

Then, in the august 2016 the Regional Government ended the authorization, in contrast with the circular 10045, on 1st July 2015, emended by Ministry of Environment, with allowed local authorities to manage the policies related to the secondary raw materials.

In April 2017 The Ministry of the Environment opened a "Work Table" for the EoW materials and overcome the regional obstacles in the carriage of secondary raw materials.

At the time of the interview, Fater was waiting for a Decree in the next months (Afterwards, on 7th February 2018 Delivery of the Regional Government on the definition of Criteria for cessation of definition of waste "case by case").

In March 2018, the Environment Ministry accepts the Fater proposal for the

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

How can you interact with these processes (regulatory process)?

Fater followed all the steps of the legislation process, trying to set up a dialogue with the institutions.

For the "Work Table," an Open Consultation was indeed foreseen, where the stakeholders can participate actively.

What is your experience with the European legislation?

We know that the Commission supports and favour ad-hoc agreements (bilateral and multilateral) between the singular MS for each waste stream.

Did you make use of existing standards to assess the process chain and the final secondary raw material proprieties?

Yes, Fater uses existing standards to verify the characteristics of the recycling process and of the final materials. Only for the levels of remaining medical product, Fater developed a specific methodology to degrade the harmful molecules.

How can other stakeholders help you?

Fater developed a methodology to degrade the harmful molecules, where a data collection period of 24 months is foreseen, with the aim to involve the stakeholders in the verification of the first hypothesis.

What are the main obstacles experienced in the treatment processes of plastics waste stream to obtain secondary raw materials?

Lack of communication between the institutions.

Too much bureaucracy.

Lack of common platform to share the status of work to find the best way to write EoW criteria, avoiding the risk to work in parallel and not together.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 6 - INTERVIEW TO FIAT RESEARCH CENTRE

Question	Answer
Why is your Company interested in EoW Criteria for plastic?	<p>FCA (interests are related to the reduction of volumes of plastic waste produced in FCA Plastic Units plants in Europe. Today FCA plants are producing several hundreds of tons of plastic waste and we would like to convert these into a secondary raw material.</p> <p>Moreover, on the basis of the Extended Producer Responsibility, FCA is responsible of end-of-life vehicles management that ask to reach reuse/recycle/recovery of vehicles (85% recyclable, 95% recoverable); then our interest is to modify some stream of plastics materials in order to convert them into EoW (separation of tyres, bumpers, tank, glass, automotive shredder residue) with final objective to be recycled. A further interest is related to ASR that could became EoW by treatment to obtain secondary solid fuels for recovery.</p>
What is your experience in the local/regional/national legislation on waste recycling and 'end-of-waste'?	Frequent meetings with all regional/national stakeholders to define future strategies
How can you interact with these processes (regulatory process)?	Lobbying activities, technical discussions and compliance verification with other legislative constraints related to raw materials (e.g. REACH)
What is your experience with the European legislation?	Frequent meetings with all Eu stakeholders (institutional and sectorial) to define future strategies
Did you make use of existing standards to assess the process chain and the final secondary raw material proprieties?	The procedure to classify as EoW has been conducted only on some metallic production scraps from FCA plants. (regulation 333/2011 and 715/2013).
How can other stakeholders help you?	Sector associations of plastic recycling should contribute in strengthening the

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

value chain for both production (for proper volumes and quality) and interactions. Stakeholders have to work more with institutions to solve criticisms related to the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislations.

What are the main obstacles experienced in the treatment processes of plastics waste stream to obtain secondary raw materials?

Technical issues related to performances, quality, reliability and proper separation methods.

Logistics and volumes to be optimized and assured.

Public authorization to define EoW criteria for plastic waste and ASR

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 7 - INTERVIEW TO NOVAMONT

Why is your Company interested in EoW Criteria for plastic?

Novamont produces biodegradable and compostable bioplastics, which are designed with the objective to be a solution for specific environmental problems associated with the end-of-life of a number of traditional plastics applications. For this reason, Novamont interest in End-of-Waste Criteria for plastic is oriented to understand those specific targeted applications that could be replaced with compostable bioplastics in order to improve the quality of recycling. In fact, the idea behind the production of compostable bioplastics is not a mere replacement of all the existing traditional products but the design of real solutions to environmental and social challenges, like organic waste collection.

Compostable bioplastics are an effective solution especially for those plastic applications in which the packaging is prone to be mixed with organic content after use. Using this kind of bioplastics in these cases can help return organic content to soil, allowing to increase the quality of organic waste recycling. Some market applications that fulfil these criteria are carrier bags for supermarkets, (to be eventually used for organic waste separate collection), organic waste bags, foodservice and packaging used in closed-loop systems (events, canteens, fast food restaurants, etc.), specific packaging items designed to be mixed with organic matter (teabags, coffee capsules, etc.). Another bioplastic application,

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

different form packaging, are mulching films for agricultural use, which can be directly left on soil and ploughed under, avoiding the accumulation of plastic material, and simultaneously working as fertilizers.

It is crucial to separate and communicate the differences between these applications and the ones for which the use of traditional plastics is still a proper solution in terms of environmental performances, such as plastic bottles, whose clean packaging can be easily recycled after use.

The importance of communicating the difference between plastics and compostable bioplastics is crucial since the latter are designed to be collected in the organic waste stream. Therefore, the contamination of organic waste with traditional plastics would result in a decrease in the quality of compost.

Regarding the contamination of plastic waste stream with bioplastics, the Italian National Packaging Consortium CONAI in 2013 has given a specific team to work on the Biodegradable Packaging Recovery Project. As reported in "Bioplastics: A case study of Bioeconomy in Italy"⁶³ the final report produced within the project concluded that biodegradable packaging can be collected with organic waste, as the final destination for this type of waste is composting, but it can also be collected together with traditional plastic packaging, up to a maximum content of 10%. Finally, the project team recommended that clear

⁶³ Walter Ganapini: "Bioplastics-A case study of Bioeconomy in Italy", 2012

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

information be given to the public, to ensure that biodegradable packaging waste is collected and recycled properly. In October 2017, a recent study jointly released by Corepla, the Italian Consortium for Collecting, Recycling, and Recovering Plastic Packaging, the Italian Composters Consortium (CIC), and Assobioplastiche, the Italian Bioplastic and Biodegradable and Compostable material Association analysing the quality of recycled plastics from 19 waste sorting and recycling facilities around the country, found that compostable plastics only made up 0.85% of the plastic input.

What is your experience in the local/regional/national legislation on waste recycling and 'end-of-waste'?

About waste management, at the national level Legislative Decree No 152/2006 sets up the same goal of 65% of municipal wastes included by the EU as part of the Circular Economy package, while the National Program for Waste Reduction deals with the volume of public sector's green purchases, considering the target of 50%. This program holds also a specific focus on bio-waste, minimization of food waste and valorisation of agro-industry by-products. The Decree of the Ministries Council Presidency (7 March 2016), deals with the requirements that organic wastes must meet to be composted. Another measure aimed at both regulating waste management and giving support to companies is the Environmental Annex to the Stability Law 2014. It supports circular and green economy, through measures such as: incentives for the use of recycled products and materials; regulation for

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

the management of specific waste and incentives to increase the volume of collected waste; description of environmental minimum criteria for Green Public Procurement; creation of a Committee for Natural Capital, that can provide information on biomass consumption and constantly check the impact of policies on resources conservation; the establishment of a system of Payment for Environmental and Ecosystem Services. The National Action Plan (NAP) for Green Public Procurement is based on the Code of Public Contracts and has the strategy for the GPP application in Italy, such as environmental targets to be reached, commodity categories and other methodological aspects. In 2016 the Environmental Annex established for the Italian Public Administration to reach to the Code, the new Code of Public Contracts has defined more precisely the Environmental Minimum Criteria to participate in public tenders. Italy was the first country developing a specific legislation (Law 28/2012) aimed at reducing the commercialization of traditional plastic shopping bags, allowing only the commercialization of those bags which are either thick enough to be reusable or not reusable but biodegradable and compostable. Italian legislation was followed by the European Commission's proposal *Reducing the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags*, published in November 2013, approved then in April 2015. Italy formally implemented its legislation in August 2017, when the Mezzogiorno Decree implementing the European Directive

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

was approved, including measures on Fruits & Vegetables bags, allowing only biodegradable and compostable (by 2018). The 2017 Budget Law implemented two similar measures, aimed at limiting the contamination of plastic in sea: starting from 2019 cotton buds must be compostable and biodegradable, and starting from 2020 the use of microplastics in cosmetic products will be banned.

At European level, was recently approved the so called “waste package” (part of the Action Plan on Circular Economy). The measures approved provide: mandatory separate collection of bio-waste by 31/12/2023; possibility for Member States to include biodegradable & compostable plastics within the bio-waste; the contribution of biodegradable & compostable plastics towards the recycling target of plastics.

At local level the key role of the municipalities is related to the implementation of the door-to door collection scheme for organic waste. At this propose Novamont, In the logic of the simultaneous growth of industrial development and support for the world of institutions, develops experimental projects conducted with public authorities, collective catering and waste management companies and other organisations and associations to create virtuous systems and a sustainability culture. An iconic example in this respect is that of AMSA for development of the system for differentiated collection in Milan. Now Milan collects more than twice the

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

organic waste of any other European city through a door-to-door system.

How can you interact with these processes (regulatory process)?

It is possible to interact with these processes through the cooperation and communication with local stakeholders and institutions, intermediate bodies, trade associations, civil society, environmental organisations.

Over years Novamont has been setting up strategic partnerships with the different stakeholders of the value chains (R&D institutions, customers, major brands, etc.) to design applications able to give solutions to both technical and environmental concerns (e.g. contamination of natural environment, organic waste management and disposal, etc.). The cooperation with local and national institution is key to creating conditions for growth of the market for bioplastics and to spreading a circular model of development based on resource efficiency. Novamont has been also collaborating with some important non-governmental organizations to promote environmental initiatives (aimed, for example, at cleaning up the sea and its coasts, rivers and lakes) and has developed advocacy activities aim at raising awareness among citizens and helping them rediscover the value of the materials they use in their daily lives.

What is your experience with the European legislation?

We have already mentioned the EU proposal *Reducing the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags*, finally

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

approved in April 2015. Published on June 6th, 2015, the EU Directive 2015/720 gives new rules on lightweight plastic carrier bags. By November 2016 Member States must implement the directive, which provides two options for reducing consumption of plastic bags: introduction of economics measures or marketing restrictions. In both cases, by December 31st, 2018, the bags cannot be given for free and by December 31st, 2019, the consumption must be reduced to 40 bags per capita. The European Commission is also committed to:

- By May 27st, 2017, adopt measures to regulate the labelling for biodegradable and compostable bags (still to be done)
- Provide a report on the environmental impact of oxo- biodegradable bags
- Give a report on ways to reduce the use of the very lightweight plastic carrier bags, below 15 microns

At this stage the European Commission has not yet adopted the measures on the labelling for biodegradable & compostable plastics

Another important legislation related to waste management is the most recent Circular Economy Package, finally approved by the European Parliament on April 2018, introducing new waste-management targets about reuse, recycling, and landfilling, strengthening provisions on waste prevention and extended producer responsibility, and streamlining definitions, reporting

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

obligations and calculation methods for targets.

Despite the positive legislative framework (Bioeconomy Strategy, Carrier Bag Directive, Waste Package, Plastic Strategy), the European Commission reconsiders the contribution of biodegradable & compostable plastics. Within the proposal for Directive published on May 28th 2018, “on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment”, the European Commission has come up with measures banning or restricting the use of single-use plastic application (such as plates, cutlery, cups, plastic bags, etc.) including biodegradable & compostable plastics. Six years after the adoption of the Directive, the European Commission proposes to eventually set up standard on marine biodegradation to exclude biodegradable & compostable plastics from the scope of the directive. But biodegradable & compostable plastics are designed to be organically recycled and banning products such as plates, cutlery, or cups, which are used efficiently especially in collective catering, would only block further research & development in this sector.

Did you make use of existing standards to assess the process chain and the final secondary raw material proprieties?

Novamont bioplastics are certified and guaranteed during their use and in the end-of-life phase⁶⁴. All grades of Novamont “MATER-BI,” our innovative family of biodegradable and compostable bioplastics, are certified

⁶⁴ <https://novamont.it/eng/mater-bi-certifications>

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

by certification bodies by the main European and international standards.

The European standard EN 13432 is the most important technical references in the bioplastic sector. The European standard EN 13432 defines the characteristics needed for a material to be considered compostable.

MATER-BI obtained the eLabel! certification, a multi-label promoted by the Italian non-profit organization "Kyoto Club," which certifies the excellence and environmental innovation of products, providing information that is transparent from both a qualitative and quantitative perspective, helping the consumer to make an independent and immediate assessment. The eLabel! certification attests to MATER-BI's environmental performance and its level of innovation based on renewable raw materials content and sustainability, greenhouse gases emissions, end of life and biodegradability in nature if uncontrolled release.

MATER-BI mulch film obtained the "OK Biodegradable Soil" standard issued by TUV AUSTRIA. This standard follows existing international standards (UNIEN 13432:2002, UNIEN 14995:2007, and ASTM 6400:04) and with the Italian standard UNI 149:2013 and French standard NFU52-001.

MATER-BI is the first Italian technology to have been verified with the European "Environmental Technology Verification" (ETV) programme, developed by Certiquality., which certified MATER-BI's behaviour in

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

biodegradation in the marine environment.

How can other stakeholders help you?

The existence of a clear and stable policy framework is crucial to promote investments. This framework should include the creation of clear quality standards and demand support measures, as well as incentives for research, innovation, and training. Legislative acts aimed at fostering the emergence and limiting the costs of environmental externalities should be designed, as well as for the promotion of the economy circularity through the application of specific fiscal measures and the simplification of the rules governing waste recover. Other important points are the promotion of law enforcement of already existing legislation, the concrete adoption of green public procurement, the creation of flagship project for specific supply chain case studies and the diffusion of private-public partnerships. Finally, it is essential to raise citizens awareness on the topic of sustainability, through specific education schemes aimed at conveying the importance and the necessity of virtuous practices, and through public campaigns, that should also involve credible and influential players of civil society.

What are the main obstacles experienced in the treatment processes of plastics waste stream to obtain secondary raw materials?

As we do not produce traditional plastics we are not involved in the treatment processes of plastics waste stream, but our bioplastics are designed to be treated in the organic

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

waste streams to obtain high quality compost and biogas.

The Italian Composting and Biogas Association (CIC) states⁶⁵ that the plant dedicated to the recycling of organic waste represents a qualified and efficient supply chain in the management of biodegradable and compostable plastic packaging: almost all the Italian plants (with few exceptions, due to particular pre-treatment systems) accept and manage without any problem the presence of compostable plastic products in the flow of organic streams, both in the case of biological processes of composting only and in integrated processes (composting and anaerobic digestion). CIC shows that the most serious problem is actually represented by the accidental flow of conventional plastics in the organic waste stream: their almost complete removal, which is necessary to ensure compliance with the quality standards of compost, requires refining interventions, that are highly demanding from both the effort invested and the costs related to the disposal of the huge quantities of waste produced.

⁶⁵ https://www.sileaspa.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/CS-CIC_Sacchetti-biodegradabili-otto-verita%CC%80-per-una-migliore-raccolta-dellumido-domestico.pdf

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 8 - INTERVIEW TO TECNOPACKAGING

Question

Answer

Why is Tecnopackaging interested in EoW Criteria for plastic?

For Tecnopackaging is good to include criteria and improving of regulation/legislation for packaging design e.g. to improve their recyclability because it represents a business opportunity in which we would be well positioned with respect to other competitor companies. Not only with the use of biodegradable materials but also with the improvement of recyclability. It represents an opportunity for plastic recovery industry.

What is your experience in the local/regional/national legislation?

There is no reference to a regional policy on sustainable public procurement for plastic packaging.

How can you interact with these processes (regulatory process)?

Tecnopackaging, as small company, has not any experience dealing with local/regional/national legislation proposal/modification.

What is your experience with the European legislation?

There are no European standards regarding the quality that recycled materials should accomplish. There is an absence of a unique market for recycled materials. In addition, there is no economic incentive for companies who would like to use recycled materials for packaging production. European legislation should promote and support the creation of a unique market of recycled materials that includes information about the material quality and other parameters (e.g. Melt Flow Index). The aim is to facilitate the use of these materials for production of new products. This is the case, for example, of recycled polymers in the form of pellets. The absence of standardization difficult the production work because if material provider change, all material characteristics will be different. Thus, there

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

is no traceability of the material. Some European initiatives are dealing with this issue, e.g. EUCERTPLAST scheme.

Did you use existing standards to assess the process chain and the final secondary raw material properties?

For secondary raw material properties, main information comes in the material's Technical Data Sheet. In addition, Tecnopackaging does mechanical and rheological tests of these materials according ISO 527 and ISO 1133, respectively. Companies provides the material's Technical Data Sheet, including security information related to Security Data Sheet. Each test has a specific standard.

How can other stakeholders help you?

Since the main interest is to homogenize the quality of recycled materials for production, legislative and normalization support is needed. In terms of eco-design, e.g. CIRC-PACK's WP4 is working on the different layers of multilayer packaging with support of different partners.

What are the main obstacles experienced in the production of secondary raw material from plastics waste?

There is no standardization of these materials. Thus, there is no homogeneity between suppliers. Quality is not always the same.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 9 - INTERVIEW TO GRUPO SADA P.A.

Question

Answer

Why is SADA interested in EoW Criteria for plastic?

Because GRUPO SADA considers the attention of the environmental and energy aspects as a very important factor to be considered within the line of its business, production and marketing of poultry products.

What is your experience in the legislation linked to the EoW criteria?

We have not experience with this kind of legislation.

What has been your interaction with these processes?

GRUPO SADA has adopted the technical improvements available with the ultimate goal of minimizing the negative environmental impact derived from our activities. One example has been the implantation of the monolayer PET in the packaging with the improvement for the recyclability that this type of materials presents

What is your experience with the European legislation?

We have experience in legislation related with post consumer- recycled material like PET and legislation related with food contact materials.

Did you use existing standards to assess the process chain and the final secondary raw material proprieties?

No, we are end user of packaging materials develops by other companies

How can other stakeholders help you?

With the development of new packaging materials and systems that maintain the organoleptic, microbiological, and shelf-life properties of our products and be materials of low environmental impact and all with a reasonable price for the type of product that is produced in GRUPO SADA.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

What are the main obstacles experienced in the production of secondary raw material from plastics waste?

GRUPO SADA does not manufacture secondary raw materials from plastic waste. The company only uses recycled plastic materials without any problem in comparison with the non-recycled materials.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 10 - INTERVIEW TO CALAF INDUSTRIAL

Question

Answer

Why is CALAF interested in EoW Criteria for plastic?

Calaf is interested in these criteria because waste streams that are candidates for the EoW procedure must have undergone a recovery operation.

At this point is where Calaf sells its machinery to get the maximum value from waste plastic and glass.

What is your experience in the legislation linked to the EoW criteria?

We do not have experience in the legislation.

What is your experience with the European legislation?

We do not have experience with the European legislation.

Did you use existing standards to assess the process chain and the final secondary raw material proprieties?

We are using standards implemented by Ecoembes to assess our machines and processes in the recovery stage.

How can other stakeholders help you?

Stakeholders could help us identifying properly the materials from waste stream to set up our machines in order to get the maximum purity to ease recyclers their processes and thus achieve the best quality of their product.

What are the main obstacles experienced in the production of secondary raw material from plastics waste?

We do not produce secondary raw materials from plastics waste.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 11 - INTERVIEW TO MI-PLAST

Question

Answer

Why is MI-PLAST interested in EoW criteria for plastic?

As recycling is part of our core business, end of waste criteria must be of interest.

As a company, we are deeply involved in Bioeconomy and circular economy work. Our company was established 40 years ago and has been contributing to what is now known as a circular economy over this time. Now that circular economy is being pushed, we are interested in spreading this story to other companies and partners in eastern Europe, and EoW criteria would enhance this.

What is your experience in the local/regional/national legislation on waste recycling and 'end-of-waste'?

We have had very bad experiences and are not satisfied with how the current government is dealing with waste.

There is not enough focus on improving this issue. Two or three ministries are involved directly with 'end of waste', and they are not well organised. In addition, little is being done to encourage people and companies to recycle more, or to use bioplastics.

Indeed, the relationship can feel very one-sided. We are currently the only company in east and south-east Europe contributing to the Bioeconomy, and we are often asked to come and present ourselves and demonstrate good practices. On the other hand, however, it can be very hard to obtain the permissions required for recycling waste, and these need to be renewed every year or two.

Theoretically, national legislation is in line with European legislation. But in practice, it is different, and there is a great deal of corruption that must be dealt with. These obstacles are such, that we are incentivised to decrease activities in recycling, and instead focus on bioplastics which have

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

different end of waste recycling needs (although currently there is no industrial composing facility in Croatia).

How can you interact with these processes (regulatory process)?

There is no dialog with regulatory processes. Officials are not open to this.

What is your experience with the European legislation?

We have no experience. As above, national legislation is theoretically in line with European legislation, however, the experience of this is quite different.

Did you make use existing standards to assess the process chain and the final secondary raw material proprieties?

No. There are several standards which we should have, but these are not relevant for the business or asked for by its clients. The only criteria which matters in the national context is price.

How can other stakeholders help you?

Other stakeholders could help increase the pressure on our city, government bodies etc. to act on end of waste issues.

Currently, Croatia is sitting at the bottom of European tables on recycling waste, and it can be difficult to be motivated to act when few around you are showing support.

What are the main obstacles experienced in the treatment processes of plastics waste stream to obtain secondary raw materials?

The main obstacle is gaining the required permissions to collect and recycle non-hazardous plastic waste, as discussed above.

Beyond this, the national collection systems are not adequate. All kinds of plastics - PET, PP, PE - are mixed together, causing huge problems during reprocessing. With sorting, it is still possible to produce an excellent product, however, the price in the market is not high enough to make this process worthwhile.

As such, we mostly buy plastic waste from other countries where collection is better segregated, or buy production waste, which does not require as much energy

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

and water as reprocessing post-consumer waste.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

ANNEX 12 - INTERVIEW TO TARHAN PLASTIC CORPORATION

Question

Answer

What are your experiences/impressions about the production of secondary raw materials from plastic waste?

Granule and flake are produced from PE and PP, respectively. Production processes are as given:

- Screening
- Washing
- Hydrophilic stage
- Melting at 160-170°C
- Cutting stage
- Collection of products

What are your experiences/impressions about obtaining products from plastic waste?

Obtainable products can be listed as follows:

- Greenhouse cover
- Spare parts from granules in automotive sector
- Wastewater and rainwater collection pipes
- Fibres and filler from PET
- Toys and children's park

Low quality wastes which are collected to our company affect quality of secondary raw materials. Therefore, companies which use the secondary raw materials apply some chemical materials to improve raw materials quality. This situation is especially occurred in plastic bags.

What are your experiences/opinions about the legislative practices related to the acquisition of secondary raw materials or products from wastes?

Regulation on Packaging Waste Control of Ministry of Environment and Urbanization is implemented. It was stated that packaging wastes have to be given to licenced companies without charge. However, this rule has been changed with the new regulations. This situation contributed to an increase in waste collection amounts.

In Turkey, street collectors collect plastic packaging wastes. They sell the waste to the plastic companies.

	Document:	D6.4. Legislative barriers at EU level for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging		
	Author:	RINA Consulting S.p.A.	Versio	1
	Reference:	D6.4	Date:	17/12/18

Do you have any information about applications in the European Union regarding the acquisition of secondary raw materials or products from wastes?

The regulation is adapted from European Union.

Do you have the standards that you currently use to evaluate secondary raw material properties and processes? If so, what?

There are no specific standards to evaluate secondary raw material properties and processes.

During receiving of wastes to the plant, we pay attention to the amount of impurities and contaminants.

While selling of granules to companies as secondary raw material, they assess the moisture content and amount of impurities.

What are the main problems/obstacles in the production of secondary raw materials from plastic waste?

Packaging waste is not collected separately in Turkey. Although municipalities do separation, we face some problems in terms of impurities and contaminants. Metals and paper wastes damage the equipment and reduce performances of the processes. In addition to this problem, domestic wastes are another problem during production of secondary raw materials. Paper waste can cause problems during washing stage due to its structure.

What do you think about the end of waste and that their trade can be done like any raw material if the technical criteria specified by the legislation are met?

EoW can give great convenience in giving added value of wastes. However, this situation can be early for Turkey.

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ANNEX 13 - INTERVIEW TO VATAN PLASTIC

Question	Answer
What are your experiences/impressions about the production of secondary raw materials from plastic waste?	All PE films are produced and recycled in our company. Secondary raw materials are produced and used for our products.
What are your experiences/impressions about obtaining products from plastic waste?	Our experience in products made from plastic waste is positive. When the bill of material is properly set, there is no problem at all.
What are your experiences/opinions about the legislative practices related to the acquisition of secondary raw materials or products from wastes?	We have information about waste recycling within the scope of environmental legislation.
Do you have any information about applications in the European Union regarding the acquisition of secondary raw materials or products from wastes?	No
Do you have the standards that you currently use to evaluate secondary raw material properties and processes? If so, what?	Important tests in our own productions are also controlled in secondary raw materials. These are Melt Flow Index (MFI), ash ratio and moisture.
What are the main problems/obstacles in the production of secondary raw materials from plastic waste?	Due to ineffective separation of wastes at its source, separation of them before recycling processes have negative effects on time and labour.
What do you think about the end of waste and that their trade can be done like any raw material if the technical criteria specified by the legislation are met?	It is very positive progressions for plastic manufacturers.

